

CEN/CENELEC FGOoC

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Focus Group Organ-on-Chip Standardization Roadmap

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133 **1 Recommendations**

134 This roadmap document is the results of two years of work, 10 Focus Group meetings, numerous
135 Working Group (WG) meetings and the active participation of around 120 experts of the
136 CEN/CENELEC Focus Group Organ-on-Chip (FGOoC).

137 The following sections provide an overview of the recommendations for topics for
138 standardisation. This overview is based on the detailed analyses in the respective sections
139 outlined in the document, as well as on a centralized FGOoC survey for prioritisation. For the
140 survey, each WG was asked to assign an urgency level to 117 items, using a five-point scoring
141 system (see table in Annex C for the scoring). A pondered calculation was made to account for
142 consensus among WGs and level of importance of each item. The items were prioritized and
143 grouped into 10 different areas of interest for OoC standardisation (see Annex C). The three areas
144 of interest with the highest urgency for standardisation were 1) qualification of materials, 2)
145 sterilization, and 3) cell integrity, identity, function, all of which are clearly represented in the
146 respective sections below.

147 **Recommendation 1:** Terminology, ecosystem, interdependencies

148 Summary: WG1 was involved in the identification of terms in the OoC field that need
149 harmonization and uniform definition. In the context of the roadmap, a majority of the FGOoC
150 members agreed to use the definitions of the terms Organ-on-Chip and Microphysiological
151 Systems according to the ASTM F3570 – 22 - Standard Terminology Relating to
152 Microphysiological Systems. However, a more extensive discussion is required to reach full
153 consensus about these definitions. A list of 38 relevant terms related to OoC/MPS technology and
154 systems was created based on inquiries performed among the FGOoC members during the
155 development process of the roadmap.

156 Rationale: The field of OoC technology currently lacks a standardized set of terminologies and
157 symbols for elements of OoC systems. Terms such as ‘Organ-on-Chip’, ‘Microphysiological
158 Systems’, ‘complex in vitro models’, ‘NAMs’, and ‘context-of-use’ are defined differently across
159 various studies and discussions. OoC systems are currently not described with a uniform
160 technical-symbolic language. Standardized and consensus-based terminology and definitions,
161 complemented by uniform symbols, will facilitate clearer communication and collaboration
162 within the international OoC community, thereby accelerating progress in the field.

163 Recommendation: Develop standards documents that provide harmonized terminology and
164 definitions for key items and symbols in the OoC domain, thereby considering in particular the
165 relevant terms described in the roadmap.

Type	Scope
Standard ¹	Terminology and definitions
Standard	Symbols

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¹ An International Standard provides rules, guidelines or characteristics for activities or for their results, aimed at achieving the optimum degree of order in a given context. It can take many forms. Apart from product standards, other examples include: test methods, codes of practice, guideline standards and management systems standards [<https://www.iso.org/deliverables-all.html#IS>]

171 **Recommendation 2: Biosciences**

172 Summary: WG2 concludes that cell biology and biomaterials in OoC devices lack standards, but at
 173 the same time it would not be feasible to define standards or specifications in an evolving area.
 174 Therefore the WG advises to focus more on reporting guidelines.

175 Rationale: The field is rapidly evolving, there are numerous protocols available. There is no way
 176 to determine what would be the optimized approach. Establishing standards at this stage would
 177 be very restrictive for the organic development of the field. Having minimum reporting guidelines,
 178 will lead to more consistent and reproducible studies.

179 Recommendation: Work towards defining minimum reporting requirements for cells and
 180 biomaterials used in OoC systems. This should be done in alignment with existing initiatives in
 181 this domain.

Type	Scope
Technical Specification ²	Minimum reporting requirements for bioscience

182
 183 **Recommendation 3: Engineering**

184 Summary: WG3 was involved in analysis of all engineering aspects of OoC. The main problem to
 185 be solved creating an OoC system is the difficulty associated with the selection of appropriate
 186 hardware, installing, and operating it. For this it might help if the components and instruments
 187 were designed in such a way that plug and play installation is possible. Therefore, there should be
 188 compatibility between components and instruments.

189 Rationale: The engineering of OoC systems encompasses a wide range of aspects, from
 190 sterilization of components and systems, integration with existing workflows, documentation of
 191 materials used, to modular integration of components and operation in specific environments.
 192 Currently, these aspects lack standardisation, leading to inconsistencies and inefficiencies in the
 193 field. Standardizing these aspects will streamline the design, fabrication, and operation of OoC
 194 systems, facilitating reproducibility and comparability across different studies and platforms.

195 Recommendation: Develop comprehensive standards documents that address the key
 196 engineering aspects of OoC systems.

Type	Scope
Technical Specification	Measurement and qualification of materials
Technical Specification	Flow control
Technical Specification	Compatibility with existing lab infrastructure (microtiterplate workflow)
Standard	Microfluidic connection
Technical Specification	Reliability related aspects like leakage, material – liquid interaction, sterilization (method and control)

² A Technical Specification addresses work still under technical development, or where it is believed that there will be a future, but not immediate, possibility of agreement on an International Standard. A Technical Specification is published for immediate use, but it also provides a means to obtain feedback. The aim is that it will eventually be transformed and republished as an International Standard. [<https://www.iso.org/deliverables-all.html#IS>]

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Recommendation 4: Hardware parameters, experimental design and data management

Summary: A number of standards and/or guidelines already exist for aspects of experimental design and data management, but for the most part these have not been developed specifically for OoC.

Rationale: Standardized experimental design and data management practices will ensure the reliability and reproducibility of OoC studies. It will also facilitate the integration of OoC data with other computational modelling studies, enabling in vitro-in vivo extrapolation and the application of machine learning algorithms. Moreover, for OoC data to be used in decision making (including for regulatory science), it will be important to build a clear framework for defining the qualification of OoC models, including the context-of-use of the data being generated.

Recommendation: Evaluate how OoC is already covered in other laboratory practices and legal framework, find where specific standardisation approach is needed. Where these gaps are identified, develop documentation that outlines the specific requirements for experimental design and data management in OoC studies, as well as the framework towards qualification of OoC models and their data for specific contexts of use. This includes standards for aspects of experimental design including positive and negative controls, sample size and randomisation, and for data management the use of software and programming languages, documentation verifying the use of FAIR principles, guidelines for using statistical software tools and tests as well as data analyses, and reporting practices.

Type	Scope
Technical Specification	Study design – factors to be taken into account such as: positive and negative controls, sample size, randomisation, operators etc.
Technical Specification	The experimental protocol should be completely described such that it can be reproduced
Technical Specification	A standardised method to acquire and store data is crucial for subsequent data analysis and publication of results

Recommendation 5: User perspective and regulatory, legal and ethical aspects

Summary: OoC can be applied in various scientific fields, being used in various risk assessment and decision making scenarios, intersecting with numerous regulations. The scientific community must be transparent to the public as more understanding is gained of the broader impact, benefits and risks of OoC within personalised medicine, toxicology and other applications, so that the field may continue to move forward in a meaningful, and potentially transformational, way.

Rationale: The current state of OoC development does not completely align with existing regulations for medical devices and medicinal products. Furthermore, OoC devices are used for regulatory toxicology, necessitating validation and scientific assessment to comply with current requirements for test methods. Ethical considerations arise when using human and non-human animal models as defined in EU regulations. Lastly, pharmaceutical companies are increasingly using OoC-based methods for internal decision making during drug development and as human-based tools to support drug repurposing. However, data generated with OoC devices are very rarely included in dossiers submitted to agencies, limiting the impact of these technologies in the regulatory arena. Efforts will be needed to facilitate alignment, acceptance and integration into regulatory frameworks.

Recommendation: Develop documentation that outlines the specific requirements for the use of OoC devices in various application domains, and facilitate and enable the use of OoC-based methods for specific applications. This includes considerations for their application in medical decision-making, regulatory toxicology, and ethical implications. The involvement of regulatory

239 and policy experts is key to complement the expertise by developers and end-users in
 240 scientifically assessing OoC technologies for specific uses.

Type	Scope
Guidelines/guidance documents	Regulatory guidance for application of OoC in testing and repurposing medicines
Guidelines/guidance documents	Define a framework for regulations for OoC with diagnostic applicability
Guidelines/guidance documents	Define the framework for use of OoC models in regulatory toxicology of chemicals, biocidal products, cosmetic products or veterinary medicinal products
Guidelines/guidance documents	Defining a framework for fully protecting autonomy of patients or other donors of cells and tissues for OoC
	Consultation with the Medical Device Coordination Group (MDCG) to define the applicability of the IVDR to OoC and enable use and commercialisation in medical settings (e.g. as a diagnostic tool).
Guidelines/guidance documents	Provide guidance to industry on how to use use OoC-based methods to generate data for drug repurposing claims
Guidelines/guidance documents	Provide guidance to medical doctors and hospitals on the use of OoC-based methods to generate data for personalised medicine and definition of patient-specific drug treatment

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257 **2 Introduction and scope**

258 **2.1 Organ-on-Chip Technologies**

259 Organ-on-Chip (OoC) is a research field that focuses on advanced tissue culture models. The
260 history of OoC can be traced back to the development of micro-electro-mechanical systems
261 (MEMS) in the 1960s and 1970s, which enabled the fabrication of miniaturized sensors and
262 actuators on silicon chips. In the 1980s and 1990s, the similar fabrication technologies were used
263 to develop microfluidic 'lab-on-a-chip' devices that could perform various analytical functions on
264 small volumes of fluids. As lab-on-a-chip technology matured, scientists began exploring the
265 possibility of culturing living cells on these chips. The 2000s witnessed significant progress in cell
266 culture in microfluidic chips, and the devices were used to produce microenvironments that
267 mimic physiological conditions (e.g. in terms of gradients, strain and stress). In the mid-2000s, a
268 perceptual shift occurred in the field of microfluidic cell culture. Scientists recognized that the
269 functional integration of engineered devices and living tissues yielded models with an
270 unprecedented complexity. Since some of these models even recapitulated organ-level
271 functionality, the term 'Organ-on-Chip' was coined to describe them.(Huh et al., 2010)

272 OoC technology has opened new avenues for understanding human biology and disease,
273 discovering new drugs, testing drug safety and efficacy, evaluating health and food products like
274 cosmetics, and developing personalised medicine. OoC devices have also been used to test the
275 effects of environmental factors, such as air pollution, radiation and microgravity, on human
276 health. OoC technology is expected to contribute to the principle of 'Refinement, Reduction,
277 Replacement' ('3R') in animal-based research by offering an alternative avenue as well as
278 opportunities to improve the human relevance of research in human (patho)physiology,
279 toxicology and pharmacology.

280 **2.2 OoC as a Growing Field**

281 The field of OoC grew rapidly after 2010, not only with many academic research groups, but also
282 with established companies, which is reflected in a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 70%
283 from 2015 to 2020, and a projected CAGR of 31% from 2020 until 2030 to a total of 1.6 billion
284 USD.(Business Wire, 2016) The research activities have grown into a worldwide endeavour, with
285 research groups and companies on all continents. The companies in the field commercialized OoC
286 models by developing their own microfluidic systems, cell cultures and read-outs. The main
287 market for commercial OoC models is in disease modelling and pharmaceutical drug development,
288 with large pharmaceutical companies as end-users or customers.

289 Much research in academia and industry is also devoted to further developing and extending the
290 concept of OoC. Currently, development of the next generation of OoC technology focuses on e.g.
291 advanced disease modelling, personalisation, multiplexing, and combining multiple devices to
292 generate 'Body-on-Chip' systems. Many research groups worldwide are contributing to these
293 developments.

294 **2.3 The growing need for standardisation in the field of OoC**

295 As the field of OoC keeps growing, it becomes increasingly clear that the relative lack of standards
296 is impeding both the implementation and innovation of the technology. A lack of standards
297 negatively affects reproducibility and comparability of results, making it more difficult to promote
298 active use of this data by companies and regulatory bodies. Moreover, the lack of standards also
299 hampers interoperability of different OoC components and systems, thereby slowing down
300 innovation and scalable manufacturing.

301 Several consortia recognized this issue and developed position papers outlining the collective
302 vision of numerous stakeholders regarding the need for standardisation to advance the OoC
303 field.(Piergiorganni, Leite, et al., 2021) Notably, the EU H2020 Organ-on-Chip In Development

304 (“ORCHID”) project identified standardisation as a crucial element for the progression of OoC
305 technologies at the European level.(Mastrangeli et al., 2019) Similarly, the transatlantic think tank
306 for toxicology (t4) summarized the views of 46 international stakeholders on the challenges faced
307 by the OoC community, identifying standards as tools to support qualification and achieve
308 regulatory acceptance.(Marx et al., 2020)

309 Based on this groundwork, the OoC community begun to actively involve organizations for
310 standards development in their work to discuss collaborative actions. Notably, the European
311 Commission’s Joint Research Centre (JRC) together with the European Committee for
312 Standardization and the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization (CEN and
313 CENELEC) made orchestrated efforts to push towards concrete actions for standardisation in OoC.
314 JRC and CEN and CENELEC, supported by the European Organ-on-Chip Society (EUROoCS),
315 organized the ‘Putting Science into Standards’ (PSIS) 2021 workshop, which brought together
316 stakeholders from academia, industry, and regulatory agencies,(Piergiovanni, Leite, et al., 2021)
317 thereby taking a key step in the process towards standardisation for OoC.(Piergiovanni, Jenet, et
318 al., 2021)

319 Standardisation can facilitate the definition of common terminology, specifications, protocols,
320 methods, metrics, and criteria for OoC design, fabrication, characterization, operation, analysis,
321 and reporting. Standardisation can also enable the development of reference materials, quality
322 control procedures, best practices, guidelines, and regulatory frameworks. By establishing a
323 common ground for OoC development, standardisation will not only promote reproducibility,
324 robustness and qualification, it can also stimulate the creation of new models and platforms.

325 **2.4 Scope of this document and the Focus Group OoC**

326 Based on the multi-stakeholder call for action in the aforementioned PSIS workshop, CEN and
327 CENELEC decided to establish a Focus Group on Organ-on-Chip (FGOoC) to (1) systematically plot
328 the landscape of standards for OoC and to (2) define a roadmap on OoC standardisation for the
329 coming years. Starting in March 2022, the goal of the FGOoC was to establish how standards can
330 contribute to designing, developing, fabricating and testing OoC models, in a way to improve their
331 reproducibility, reliability, comparability and validity, finally leading to significant improvements
332 in their development and implementation. In this roadmap document, the FGOoC aims to draft an
333 overview of the landscape of standards that are relevant for the domain of OoC. This includes the
334 identification of existing standards or standardisation initiatives, as well as recommendations on
335 the priorities and opportunities for drafting new standards in the coming years.

336 The primary audience for this roadmap is the (inter)national community of organizations and
337 stakeholders that will participate in standardisation of OoC. The roadmap will also be of interest
338 to researchers and industry professionals working in the field of OoC, regulatory agencies, funding
339 bodies, and other stakeholders who are interested in the development and application of OoC.

340 Enabling technologies and topics that are included in the scope of the roadmap include
341 microfluidics, (stem) cell biology, biomaterials, tissue engineering, data management,
342 bioanalytical techniques, and ethical and regulatory aspects. These topics are included because
343 they are integral to the development and application of OoC, and because they can help to define
344 best practices for designing, fabricating, and testing OoC models. In contrast, topics that are
345 excluded from the scope of the roadmap, or only discussed indirectly, include broader topics such
346 as omics, artificial intelligence, drug discovery, clinical diagnostics and regenerative medicine.
347 Although related to the application of OoC, these topics are not directly relevant to the
348 development of best practices for designing, fabricating, and testing OoC models. Moreover, the
349 focus of FGOoC was on identifying standards and providing a roadmap for the overall domain of
350 OoC, rather than on focusing on specific models, organs, or applications.

351 The following aspects of OoC standardisation will be covered in the roadmap document.

- 352 — First of all, the document will discuss the main relevant terms and their definitions
353 (including references) for OoC. This is essential to establish a common language
354 that can be used by the OoC community.
- 355 — The roadmap will also give an overview of the OoC ecosystem and address the
356 interdependencies between various stakeholders, including researchers, industry
357 professionals, regulatory agencies, and funding bodies, and how these
358 interdependencies impact the development and implementation of OoC.
- 359 — The roadmap will also focus on best practices for bioscience-related aspects of
360 OoC, including the source, selection and culture of cells, the use of stem cells and
361 extracellular matrix proteins, as well as the design and use of culture media.
- 362 — In addition, the roadmap will address the engineering aspects of OoC, such as the
363 design and fabrication of microfluidics, laboratory equipment, and
364 microelectronics, including materials selection, fabrication techniques, and
365 quality control.
- 366 — The roadmap will identify important aspects of experimental design and data
367 management. This includes the development of standardized protocols for
368 experimental design, as well as repositories for OoC data and the use of reference
369 compounds to facilitate comparison of OoC results across different experiments
370 and laboratories for qualification and validation.
- 371 — Finally, the roadmap will take into account the user perspective of OoC, as well as
372 the regulatory, legal, and ethical aspects of their development and use. The
373 regulatory landscape for OoC, including the role of regulatory agencies, in the
374 adoption and use of this innovative technology will be addressed, as well as legal
375 and ethical considerations related to in vitro diagnostics regulations (IVDR),
376 intellectual property (IP), informed consent, and privacy.

377 **2.5 Process and workflows of drafting this roadmap**

378 The FGOoC consists of experts from different fields of activity, including OoC development and
379 use, who contributed from various perspectives and areas of expertise. Main stakeholders
380 involved are related to: 1) research, including fundamental or applied research in university
381 settings and commercial R&D; 2) industry, including both developers from sub-systems or
382 suppliers and end-users; and 3) non-governmental and governmental European or member state
383 organisations, institutions, and research and technology organizations.

384 The outcome of the FGOoC is this roadmap, which is primarily an advisory document for the CEN
385 and CENELEC Technical Board, but is expected to also provide a reference point for the field of
386 OoC as a whole. The roadmap indicates which standards must be developed and in what structure.
387 The text of the roadmap has been developed in five Working Groups (WGs), focusing on different
388 subtopics: WG1 Terminology, ecosystems, interdependencies, WG2 Biosciences, WG3
389 Engineering, WG4 Experimental design and data management, and WG5 User perspective and
390 regulatory, legal and ethical aspects. The interaction between the different WGs is illustrated in
391 Figure 1.

392 The roadmap was drafted in a bottom-up process. The state of the art was investigated for each
393 subtopic; already published standards were listed and opportunities for standardisation were
394 identified by the participating stakeholders in the dedicated WGs. These opportunities were then
395 prioritized according to importance, dependencies, and probability of reaching consensus. The
396 draft text of the roadmap was reviewed multiple times by the FGOoC. Furthermore, input was

397 received from interested international parties. In total around 120 experts contributed to the
398 roadmap, in ten plenary FG meetings and around 90 monthly meetings in total for the five WGs.

399 The FGOoC is facilitated by NEN, the Royal Netherlands Standardisation Institute. As a national
400 standardisation institute, NEN plays a pivotal role in European standardisation by facilitating
401 technical committees tasked with developing and maintaining standards crucial for various
402 industries. NEN's primary responsibility lies in coordinating these committees, ensuring that
403 experts from relevant fields collaborate effectively to establish consensus-based standards. This
404 involves organizing meetings, managing communications, and overseeing the drafting and
405 revision processes to align with European and international standards frameworks.

406 NEN serves as a link between national and European standardisation bodies, facilitating
407 collaboration and harmonization of standards across borders. In connection to NXTGEN Hightech,
408 a Dutch initiative aimed at fostering innovation in next-generation technologies, NEN provides
409 expertise and guidance in the development of standards specific to OoC technologies. These
410 standards are essential for ensuring the reliability, reproducibility, and safety of OoC platforms,
411 thereby accelerating their adoption and facilitating their integration into research, development,
412 and industrial applications across Europe. Through its involvement in NXTGEN Hightech and
413 dedication to advancing standardisation in cutting-edge fields like OoC, NEN reinforces Europe's
414 position as a leader in innovation and promotes the growth of a robust and competitive European
415 market.

416 The working groups (WG 2-5) are aligned along a conceptual experimental timeline, which is laid
417 out to answer an initial research question of interest (top panel of Figure 1). The WGs defined up
418 to three sub-topics, covering across the WGs all relevant topics from planning to execution of an
419 experiment, data storage, and regulatory aspects.

420 The WGs are based on a conceptual mapping of the field of OoC (bottom panel of Figure 1). The
421 foundation of all work in the field lies in having a clear understanding of the full ecosystem as well
422 as a well-defined, shared terminology (WG1). Based on this foundation, a functional OoC model
423 integrates biological components, including living cells and tissues, as well as engineered
424 components and subsystems, and both are addressed in their respective WGs (WG2, WG3, resp.).
425 The functional OoC models then form the basis for experimental studies, in which they are
426 operated according to experimental protocols, with defined parameters, to generate relevant data
427 (WG4). The generated data are to be used in multiple contexts, that include legal, ethical
428 regulatory aspects (WG5). Similarly, the biological and technical components of an OoC model
429 (particularly its human cells) can also be prone to regulation (WG5).

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Figure 1: Interplay of Working Groups

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441 2.6 Standardisation

442 *Standardisation plays a crucial role in virtually every aspect of modern society, from ensuring*
 443 *interoperability and safety to facilitating international trade and innovation. At its core,*
 444 *standardisation involves establishing a set of guidelines, specifications, or criteria that products,*
 445 *processes, or practices must meet. This process is vital for harmonizing practices across industries*
 446 *and regions, promoting efficiency, quality, and reliability.*

447 *In fields such as technology and manufacturing, standards enable different systems and components*
 448 *to work together seamlessly, fostering compatibility and reducing the risk of incompatibility issues.*
 449 *For example, standards like USB, HDMI, and Wi-Fi ensure that devices from different manufacturers*
 450 *can connect and communicate effectively, regardless of their origins.*

451 *The process of creating standards involves various stakeholders, including industry experts,*
 452 *regulators, consumer advocates, academia, and government representatives. Consensus-building is*
 453 *a fundamental aspect of standardisation, as it ensures that standards are widely accepted and*
 454 *implemented. The consensus-building process typically involves extensive collaboration, negotiation,*
 455 *and sometimes compromise.*

456 *Standards often have a direct impact on European legislation and the internal market. EU directives*
 457 *and regulations frequently reference standards as a means to ensure compliance with established*
 458 *requirements and to support the free movement of goods and services within the EU. By aligning*
 459 *standards with legislative objectives, European standardisation organizations contribute to the*
 460 *development of a cohesive regulatory framework that fosters innovation, competitiveness, and*
 461 *consumer protection across the EU member states.*

462 *The process of developing European Standards involves a structured approach primarily facilitated*
 463 *by CEN and CENELEC, where members, including the National Standardisation Bodies and National*
 464 *Committees, predominantly drive the initiatives. Occasionally, proposals for standards may originate*
 465 *from the European Commission or other stakeholders.*

466 *Upon sufficient interest from CEN and/or CENELEC members to participate in the development*
 467 *process, the responsibility is delegated to the respective Technical Committee (TC), focusing on the*
 468 *relevant field. National mirror committees comprising stakeholders determine the national*
 469 *contributions to the standard's development. Additionally, alongside CEN and/or CENELEC*
 470 *members, Technical Committees also accommodate observers, including ISO/IEC members,*
 471 *European Commission/EFTA, European partners such as Annex III organizations, external European*
 472 *industry associations, and other affiliated bodies.*

473 *Subsequently, upon the evaluation and approval of the standard proposal, it advances to the drafting*
 474 *stage, characterized by consensus-building. Upon finalizing the draft standard, it undergoes a public*
 475 *enquiry accessible to all interested parties. Following the conclusion of the enquiry, votes and*
 476 *comments on the standard are assessed, determining whether the draft is published or requires*
 477 *further refinement before undergoing formal voting. Alternatively, standards may be developed*
 478 *internationally at ISO, truly establishing a global standard. The process and principles of*
 479 *standardisation remain the same.*

480

481 3 Terms and Definitions

482 The following definitions for OoC and microphysiological systems have previously been used in
 483 the literature and are used in the context of this roadmap. Other terms requiring formal definition
 484 are listed in Annex A.

485 NOTE The exact definitions are still subject to discussion in the field. Their use in the context of the
 486 roadmap does not imply that these represent a consensus definition.

487 **3.1**
488 **Organ-on-Chip**
489 a subset of microphysiological systems that replicates one or more aspects of an organ's in vivo
490 dynamics, functionality, structure, and/or (patho)physiological response(s) of multiple cell types
491 integrated within a non-biological platform

492 **3.2**
493 **Microphysiological systems**
494 fit-for-purpose devices, containing one or more engineered organ(s), organ substructures, and/or
495 functional organ unit(s) in a controllable microenvironment

496 Note to entry An MPS represents one or more aspects of the organ or organ system's dynamics,
497 functionality, and/or (patho)physiological response such as responding to biologic, mechanical,
498 electromagnetic (light and/or radiation), or pharmaceutical stimuli in vivo. Ideally, an MPS has the capacity
499 to be monitored under real time. MPS platforms may comprise mono-cultures, cocultures of multiple cell
500 types, maintenance of explants derived from tissues/organs, and/or inclusion of organoid cell formations.

501 **3.3 List of available standards**

502 — ASTM F3570 – 22 - Standard Terminology Relating to Microphysiological Systems

503 — ISO 10991:2023

504 **4 Terminology, ecosystem, interdependencies**

505 **4.1 Introduction**

506 The landscape of standardisation in OoC is highly complex, with multiple domains and a very
507 diverse group of stakeholders with many interrelationships in different application fields.
508 Standardisation can only be achieved by a concerted effort of all stakeholder groups that form the
509 OoC ecosystem. The European OoC roadmap, mentioned earlier, developed in the ORCHID project,
510 defines the building blocks of the processes from initial development to the final application and
511 use of OoC models. These building blocks include specification, qualification, standardisation,
512 production and upscaling, and adoption of these innovative systems. Many different actors are
513 involved in these processes. The interaction and a collective dialogue among all stakeholders in
514 these processes are essential to realize robust, reproducible, easy to use, standardized, qualified
515 and validated fit-for purpose OoCs, that meet the need for better models. EUROoCS, the European
516 Organ-on-Chip Society, acts as a catalyst to build this community further and bridge the gap
517 between the different actors.

518 **4.2 Actors**

519 As shown in Figure 2 six different categories of actors can be identified in the OoC field, each with
520 a specific role and position in the circular workflow from new solutions for unmet needs to the
521 use of standardized and validated end products. The separate groups are described below.

522 **4.2.1 R&D-Scientific Community**

523 The R&D-Scientific Community consists of scientists, researchers and developers from both non-
524 profit and commercial organizations and consortia.

525 — **Academia and knowledge institutes:** Including (technical) universities,
526 university medical centers and universities of applied sciences develop new ideas
527 and technologies, that form the basis for novel/advanced OoC models. They have
528 a central role as a breeding place for providing and training the next generation
529 of researchers and teaching them the skills needed to design and use OoC

530 technology. Most devices developed in these settings remain at a proof-of-concept
 531 level and do not yet offer the ease-of-use, manufacturability and throughput
 532 necessary for widespread application. For this reason, it is important that
 533 scientists from academia collaborate with end users to understand their needs
 534 and interact with the supplier industry to bridge the valley of death by translating
 535 their inventions into marketable products. Academics can also be end users of
 536 OoC models, applying them to the biomedical research, where tools able to model
 537 complex, mechanistic phenomena are crucial to better understand health and
 538 diseases. To advance science and promote an increased use of OoC technology, it
 539 is important that not only results, but also methods and protocols, are published
 540 in (open access) journals.

541 — **Scientific societies and consortia:** Among them in the OoC field is EUROoCS, that
 542 brings together all actors involved. EUROoCS has partnered with the International
 543 Society for Stem Cell Research (ISSCR) to be able to use Stem Cell Reports as the
 544 home journal. The ISSCR, in partnership with global stakeholders, is currently
 545 developing research standards on stem cells that can be adopted worldwide. In
 546 Europe, other consortia/societies on OoC include hDMT (Dutch Organ-on-Chip
 547 Consortium), ISOoC (Italian Organ-on-Chip Society) and the Nordic Organ-on-a-
 548 Chip Network. On the global level the international MPS Society (iMPSS) has
 549 recently been established. During the pandemic the NC3Rs MPS CoRe Working
 550 Group was born aiming to help coordinate global efforts to use MPS/OoC for
 551 assessing the safety and efficacy of potential novel therapeutics for infectious
 552 diseases, starting from COVID-19, through building connections between
 553 technology developers and end-users.

554 — **Commercial actors:** Including companies and CRO/service -based research, such
 555 as Small Medium Enterprises (SMEs), start-ups and spin-offs, that are focused on
 556 bringing their products to the market via the process of proof-of-concept
 557 development, prototyping and testing. These companies are commercial
 558 providers and vendors of ready-to-use devices and assays (B2C marketing), and
 559 suppliers (biotech, micro/nanotech, high-tech) of different components (B2B
 560 marketing) of OoC systems. The latter components can be combined by system
 561 integrators into open technology platforms, that can be customized for a specific
 562 application. As indicated in this roadmap, both roads for the development of
 563 ready-to-use devices and open technology platforms are interconnected. Early
 564 interaction with the manufacturing companies in the development process is
 565 required for setting up the pilot line and related factory for the production and
 566 upscaling of the products. Suppliers of peripheral instrumentation (imaging,
 567 electronics, robotics equipment) form another important group of companies,
 568 required for the use of OoC in practice and compatibility with laboratory
 569 equipment.

570 — **Industry associations and fora in the MPS field:** Provide a venue for
 571 appropriate collaboration and data sharing to facilitate the industry
 572 implementation and qualification of MPS models. In particular, the IQ MPS
 573 Affiliate is a not-for-profit organization devoted to raising awareness, advancing
 574 the science and supporting the implementation of MPS in drug discovery. The
 575 North American 3Rs collaboration (NA3RsC MPS Initiative) aims to increase the
 576 adoption of MPS technologies through stakeholder engagement. Related
 577 organizations include EFPIA (European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries
 578 and Associations) and EPAA (European Partnership for Alternative Approaches

579 to Animal Testing). Relevant fora for the standardisation of OoC are the SiLA
580 Consortium, Animl (data standards), and SLAS (microplate standards).

581 4.2.2 End users

582 End users of OoC models include those industries that adopt the equipment and OoC-based assays
583 to support the development and the regulatory authorization of new medicines or consumer
584 products, such as the pharmaceutical, food, cosmetics and chemical industry. CROs and biotech
585 industry with a fee-for-service model for testing drugs for pharmaceutical companies are also
586 envisioned as end users of test methods based on OoC technologies. Academia use the models for
587 biomedical research, to get insight into the mechanisms of disease or as a basis to propose new
588 therapies. Healthcare providers can use personalized OoC models (patient-on-chip) to define the
589 best treatment for each individual patient.

590 4.2.3 Governance

591 Among the governance organizations are the overarching institutions with policy makers,
592 regulatory authorities and standardisation bodies, that have a crucial role in the approval and
593 adoption of OoC for different purposes.

594 — **Standardisation organizations:** Stimulate and support the development of
595 standards. In the process of OoC standardisation all relevant stakeholders are
596 involved, including developers, suppliers, regulatory bodies and end users. The
597 European committees for standardisation, CEN and CENELEC, established a
598 FGOoC, that is supported by the Dutch Normalization Institute NEN to develop
599 this roadmap for OoC standardisation, followed by the development of the
600 standards defined. The FGOoC and the Organ/Tissue on a Chip (O/ToC)
601 Engineering and Efficacy Standards Working Group at NIST (National Institute of
602 Standards and Technology in the US) are exploring the opportunities to bridge the
603 gap between their efforts in Europe and USA. CEN and CENELEC collaborate with
604 international organizations for standardisation (ISO, IEC, ASTM, ANSI) to align the
605 activities regarding the development of (international) standards.

606 — **Regulatory or notified bodies and agencies:** Responsible for the authorization
607 of new medicines, devices or consumer products in the respective geographical
608 part of the world for which they are responsible. In Europe, the EMA (European
609 Medicines Agency) is in charge of the evaluation, under the central authorization
610 procedure, and supervision of pharmaceutical products. The European
611 Commission is the authorising body for all centrally authorised product, who
612 takes a legally binding decision based on EMA's recommendation (European
613 Medicines Agency, 2024a). While the majority of new, innovative medicines are
614 evaluated by EMA and authorised by the European Commission in order to be
615 marketed in the EU, most generic medicines and medicines available without a
616 prescription are assessed and authorised at national level in the EU. A medical
617 device may be placed on the market or put into service only if it complies with the
618 Medical Device Regulation or, whenever appropriate, with the In Vitro Diagnostic
619 Medical Device Regulation. The conformity assessment is made, for devices of risk
620 class above the lowest classification class, by notified bodies, i.e. conformity
621 assessment bodies assessed, designated and notified by the Member states (art.
622 35 MDR), by means of a specific authority ('authority responsible for notified
623 bodies'). Other agencies are responsible for safety of food (EFSA), chemicals
624 (ECHA), food and drugs (FDA (US)), China Food and Drug Administration), or have
625 a broad spectrum of safety management (PMDA - Pharmaceuticals and Medical
626 Devices Agency (Japan)). Some other international organisations (OECD, ICH) are
627 involved in the development of new tools, standards, policy and/or approaches to

628 assess the safety, quality and performance of regulated products. The FDA
629 Modernization Act and the policy of the EMA 3Rs Working Party emphasize the
630 increasing possibilities for collaboration and interaction between regulators and
631 other stakeholders in the OoC field. A notified body is an organisation designated
632 by an EU country to assess the conformity of certain products before being placed
633 on the market. These bodies carry out tasks related to conformity assessment
634 procedures set out in the applicable legislation, when a third party is required.

635 — **Qualification and validation centers:** Play an essential role in the independent
636 qualification of OoC to ensure the reproducibility and reliability of a particular
637 model for (regulatory) decision-making. ECVAM and its international partners
638 have an important role in coordinating development, validation and regulatory
639 acceptance of alternative methods and approaches. In Europe, the European
640 Union Network of Laboratories for the Validation of Alternative Methods (EU-
641 NETVAL) has been established by ECVAM to provide technical support to
642 validation studies, designed to assess the reliability and relevance of alternative
643 methods that have a potential to replace, reduce or refine (3Rs) the use of animals
644 for scientific purposes. In the US, the Texas A&M Tissue Chip validation (TEX-VAL)
645 Consortium have been established to provide a way to test and validate OoC
646 devices, and thereby promote the adoption of this technology by the broader
647 research community.

648 4.2.4 Information managers

649 Information managers have a role in creating optimal awareness regarding OoC developments
650 and new results, and in stimulating the use of these models by widespread communication.

651 — **Editors of scientific journals:** Important actors in the OoC field regarding the
652 publication of research methods and results obtained with animal-free models. A
653 discussion between editors and the scientific community is necessary to explore
654 options to adjust the publication policies, since some journals still require
655 evidence for the research results based on animal experiments in order to justify
656 publication.

657 — **Repository managers:** Structure the organization of databases containing data
658 about OoC, such as test and qualification results for different applications and
659 context of use, but also specifies on the specific test method and protocol applied.
660 They manage the access and interaction of users with the database and can
661 support in maximizing its value and promoting good reporting and reusing of
662 scientific results.

663 4.2.5 Funders

664 Both public and private sources are necessary to fund research groups and start-ups in the OoC
665 field. Among the public funders are the European Commission (EU funding programmes) and
666 national governmental funding agencies (NCATS, research councils), that are becoming
667 increasingly interested in supporting new research approaches. In the private domain charities,
668 health funds, and patient organizations are providing grants for OoC research to advance scientific
669 knowledge and reduce the number of animals used for testing. The necessary capital for
670 technology transfer and production upscaling is provided by Venture Capital firms and Angel
671 investors.

672 **4.2.6 Civil Society**

673 The promise of OoC technology to solve societal challenges, such as a reduction of the number of
674 animal experiments, the improvement of drug development and the identification of effective and
675 personalized treatments has raised the interest of many societal stakeholders. These include
676 animal protection and animal welfare organizations, such as the Humane Society International,
677 but also patient organizations. An important stakeholder is the general lay public that can raise a
678 societal voice to decrease or even replace animal testing and gets quickly excited about the
679 potential of OoC. A careful communication of recent achievements and ongoing developments on
680 OoC models is required to avoid the risk of overselling or overpromising and to keep expectations
681 realistic.

682 **4.3 Interrelationships**

683 In an optimal OoC workflow from idea to use (Figure 2) all actors described above have their
684 specific roles, tasks and responsibilities, and collaborate already from the start to define unmet
685 needs and develop new ideas. End users in particular are essential to prioritize the missing tools
686 and the contexts of their use. Once funding is available, the design, specification, proof of concept
687 and prototype can be performed by researchers from the R&D-Scientific Community. The
688 prototypes can vary from ready-to-use devices to flexible open technology platforms. Alignment
689 between the suppliers of components, system integrators and manufacturers, and collaboration
690 with the suppliers of peripheral equipment, are required to guarantee the scaled production of
691 robust and reproducible fully operational OoCs. The next necessary step is the assessment of the
692 scientific validity of the prototypes. Depending on the context of use, this evaluation will be carried
693 out by the end users themselves, by independent Tissue Chip Testing Centres or by the regulatory
694 authorities. The industrial partners/manufacturers will then start up the pilot production,
695 followed by large-scale production including assembly of the components of the model. The final
696 step is product standardisation and marketing authorization (if applicable), at the regional,
697 national or global level. Feedback from the end user to the developers for improvement or
698 additional functionality of the OoC, or discussion with the other actors about new unmet needs,
699 closes the loop of the circular OoC workflow.

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Organ-on-Chip (OoC) - Actors

Civil society	Governance	Investors/funders	R&D - Scientific community	Information managers	End users
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> General public Patient organizations Other advocacy groups (e.g. animal welfare) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policy makers Institutions Authority/regulators Standardization organizations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public Private 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Academia/consortia/scientific societies (Bio)technology industry/associations/fora 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Journal editors Repository managers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Healthcare providers Pharmaceutical industry Chemical industry Food industry Cosmetic industry Contract research organizations Academia (Bio)technology industry

706

Organ-on-Chip (OoC) – Workflow

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708

Figure 2 - OoC Actors and Workflow

709 NOTE The various actors involved in the design, realization and implementation of a successful OoC
 710 project are grouped according to their role in the upper part of Figure 2. The lower part of Figure 2 shows
 711 a circular workflow where needs and new ideas are proposed and discussed with R&D and the scientific
 712 community, leading after a multi-step process to use by end users, who in turn provide feedback to achieve
 713 continuous improvement. The realization and implementation of the workflow requires standardisation of
 714 the processes involved, which are included here in the light blue area. The extent of standardisation depends
 715 on the particular needs and goals of each project.

716 **5 Biosciences**

717 **5.1 Introduction**

718 This chapter focuses on the identification of existing standards for biological inputs of OoC models.
 719 Biological inputs include aspects related to cell and tissue sources and standards, 3D matrices and
 720 2D coatings to culture cells and biophysical/biochemical cell culture conditions. For all these
 721 topics, the WG first gathers ongoing initiatives and/or available standards to be used as starting
 722 points, and eventually identify gaps towards the definition of a roadmap. As a general remark, in
 723 this chapter the identified topics are approached with an “agnostic” perspective (i.e. not focusing
 724 on a specific context of use) in order to provide a broader starting point at the service of other

725 chapters. The following topics are going to be discussed: cell sources, biomaterials, and cell culture
726 conditions.

727 **5.2 Cell and Tissue sources**

728 The scope of this subtopic is to define and identify possible existing standards for cells used in
729 OoC systems. Topics include, but not necessarily limited to, cell type (primary, pluripotent stem
730 cell, cell line), cell/tissue isolation, cell source (commercial, patient-derived, biobanks etc.),
731 species, quality control (karyotyping, phenotyping, mycoplasma testing), and reporting criteria
732 for the topics. This subgroup primarily focuses on key characteristics of cells that can be
733 determined without knowledge on their use i.e. pre-experimental.

734 Cells used in OoC devices are a key source of variability in device performance. Initially, OoC
735 devices were used with immortalised cell lines but with advances in stem cell technology, primary
736 cell sources are widely applied for increased physiological relevance along with donor-to-donor
737 differences inherent to human samples. As the use of physiologically relevant cell sources
738 increase, it is imperative that the appropriate quality control criteria and sufficient information
739 on the cells are reported for the appropriate evaluation of results obtained from OoC devices.

740 Several standards for the use of cells in vitro have been identified. Despite these standards being
741 available, it is often not clear if they are applied when used in OoC systems. Moreover, at present,
742 there is no single official standard covering all cell sources or all aspects of good cell culture
743 practice. Moreover, different cell types will require very specific functional assays for validation.
744 Therefore, an exhaustive guide towards standardisation of cells used in OoC systems is
745 impractical. However, it is highly desirable that appropriate standards are followed, and minimum
746 reporting criteria are incorporated when describing cell used in OoC systems. This will provide
747 reviewers and regulatory authorities the necessary information for appropriately evaluating the
748 biological results obtained from OoC devices.

749 The key finding is the lack of a unified standard document on the different cells used in OoC
750 devices. The definition of a future set of standards covering all aspects of cell (pre-experimental)
751 including quality control procedures and minimum reporting guidelines are recommended. Some
752 of these recommendations, based on the currently available standards, are described in 5.2.1.

753 **5.2.1 Definitions**

754 Cell sources used in OoC devices include pluripotent stem cells (PSC), multipotent stem cells,
755 tissue slice cultures, primary cells, immortalised cells, and commercial cell lines (Wnorowski et
756 al., 2019).

757 — **Pluripotent stem cells (PSC):** PSCs are undifferentiated cells of embryonic or
758 somatic origin that can differentiate into cells of the three embryonic germ layers
759 (ectoderm, mesoderm, and endoderm) and have self renewing capacity (Romito
760 & Cobellis, 2016). There are various states of pluripotency that resemble different
761 states of the embryo, not just one. It is important to demonstrate what qualitative
762 and quantitative assays have been performed along with the markers that are
763 used to demonstrate the state of pluripotency of the cells. Induced pluripotent
764 stem cells (iPSCs) are a particular type of pluripotent stem cells obtained from the
765 conversion of somatic cells (such as skin cells) into embryonic-like cells through
766 a process known as reprogramming.

767 — **Multipotent stem cells:** (e.g. blood stem cell, mesenchymal stem cell). These are
768 undifferentiated cells considered to be able to self-renew and differentiate into all
769 cell types within one lineage (Khanlarkhani et al., 2016).

770 — **Tissue slice cultures:** Organotypic tissue slice culture systems represent in vitro
771 cultures of explants of patient- or animal-derived tissues – normal/pathology
772 associated (e.g. tumours) (He & Deng, 2022).

773 — **Primary cells:** These are cells freshly isolated directly from living organisms and
774 maintained from growth in vitro. They enable researchers to study the
775 morphological, cellular, and functional behaviour of the tissue. Standard protocols
776 have been established to isolate epithelial, endothelial (and endothelial
777 progenitors (EPCs), fibroblasts, and immune cells from human, mouse, and rat
778 tissue. Primary cells should be characterised according to best practice (e.g. For
779 Mesenchymal Stem Cells– International Society for Gene and Cell Therapy
780 (ISGCT) guidelines (Dominici et al., 2006))

781 — **Immortalised cells (Derived in house):** They derive from human or animal
782 sources and have been manipulated to proliferate indefinitely in vitro and can
783 thus be cultured for long periods of time. This immortalisation can be induced
784 through genetic engineering or can be because of isolation from sources that are
785 chromosomally abnormal or that carry mutations that enable continuous cell
786 division. For reproducibility, it is important that cell line identity is reported
787 according to best practice (ANSI, 2022).

788 The following should be considered when using cells:

789 — A **master cell bank** (an aliquot of a single pool of cells that has been prepared
790 from the selected cell clone under defined conditions, dispensed into multiple
791 containers, and stored under defined conditions) should be generated prior to
792 experimental work.

793 — When setting up a biobank, **Standard Operating Procedures** (SOPs) should be
794 used in all aspects of the biobanking process, from procurement, shipment and
795 safety to processing and storing. The key aspects to consider when setting up a
796 biobank are discussed in ISO 20387:2018.

797 — Each cell source has **different requirements for validation** which should be
798 considered (see standards in 5.2.2.).

799 5.2.2 List of available standards

800 Several standards are already in place that outline the need and provide guidance for
801 standardisation of cells used for in vitro studies. However, the available standards do not always
802 cover all cell sources described above and are not directly related nor directly referring to OoC. A
803 full list of available standards is presented in Annex B.

804 — **Good In vitro Method Practices (GIVIMP)**(OECD, 2018)

805 In the past several decades, there has been a substantial increase in the availability of in vitro test
806 methods for evaluating chemical safety in an international regulatory context. To foster
807 confidence in in vitro alternatives to animal testing, the test methods and conditions under which
808 data are generated must adhere to defined standards to ensure resulting data are rigorous and
809 reproducible. Good In vitro Method Practices (GIVIMP) for the development and implementation
810 of in vitro methods for regulatory use in human safety assessment aims to help reduce the
811 uncertainties in cell and tissue-based in vitro method derived chemical safety predictions. GIVIMP
812 provides guidance for test method developers and end users of resulting data on key elements of
813 in vitro methods. GIVIMP tackles ten important aspects related to in vitro work: (1) Roles and

814 responsibilities, (2) Quality considerations, (3) Facilities (4) Apparatus, material and reagents, (5)
815 Test systems, (6) Test and reference/control items, (7) SOPs, (8) Performance of the method, (9)
816 Reporting of results, (10) Storage and retention of records and materials.

817 GIVIMP(OECD, 2018) is a guidance document from the OECD for test method developers and end
818 users of resulting data on key elements of in vitro methods. The cell and cell sources are not the
819 key focus of this guidance document. However, as a part of the Annex, GIVIMP provides guidance
820 on good cell culture practice for cells in general and for stem cells and stem cell-derived models

821 — **ISSCR guidelines for stem cell research and clinical translation** (International
822 Society for Stem Cell Research, 2023)

823 The international society for stem cell research identifies quality standards and outlines basic core
824 principles for the use of tissue and pluripotent stem cells. The standards initiative from ISSCR aims
825 to define standards for basic, preclinical, and clinical research. As of August 2023, the ISSCR
826 standards cover basic and preclinical research while the standards for clinical research are under
827 development. These guidelines only cover stem cells and not all cell sources that may be used in
828 OoC devices.

829 This document identifies quality standards and outlines basic core principles for the laboratory
830 use of both tissue and pluripotent human stem cells and the in vitro model systems that rely on
831 them. Overall, the emphasis of this document is creating a set of recommendations that, when
832 taken together, establish the minimum characterization and reporting criteria for scientists,
833 students, and technicians in basic research laboratories working with human stem cells.

834 — **Guidance on Good Cell Culture Practice (GCCP)**(Price A & Coecke S, 2011)

835 The GCCP is a chapter in Cell Culture Techniques that addresses issues related to cell culture
836 including quality assurance; recording and reporting; safety, education, and training; and ethics.
837 This guideline is not from a specific standardisation body but covers broad aspects related to cell
838 culture. The first guideline published in 2011 was then updated (GCCP 2.0)(Pamies et al., 2022)
839 to incorporate recent advances.

840 The use of various in vitro systems is expanding dramatically not only in basic research, but also
841 to meet regulatory requirements for chemicals and products of various kinds. Further significant
842 developments are certain to result from the use of in vitro systems for high throughput screening
843 in pharmacology and toxicology. Because the maintenance of high standards is fundamental to all
844 good scientific practice, and is essential for maximising the reproducibility, reliability, credibility,
845 acceptance and proper application of any results produced that guidelines has been developed to
846 define minimum standards in cell and tissue culture, to be called GCCP. The scope of the document
847 has been broadly defined, to include systems based on cells and tissues obtained from humans
848 and animals, and issues related to the characterisation and maintenance of essential
849 characteristics, as well as quality assurance; recording and reporting; safety, education and
850 training; and ethics. This GCCP Guidance lists a set of six principles intended to support best
851 practice in all aspects of the use of cells and tissues in vitro, and to complement, but not to replace,
852 any existing guidance, guidelines or regulations.

853 — **Guidelines for the use of cell lines in biomedical research** (Geraghty et al.,
854 2014)

855 Like the GCCP above, this guideline is a scientific publication that addresses several aspects of cell
856 culture and provides advice on legal and ethical requirements for cells. However, this guideline is
857 solely aimed at cell lines and does not cover other cell sources.

858 Cell-line misidentification and contamination with microorganisms, such as mycoplasma,
859 together with instability, both genetic and phenotypic, are among the problems that continue to
860 affect cell culture. Many of these problems are avoidable with the necessary foresight, and these
861 Guidelines have been prepared to provide those new to the field and others engaged in teaching

862 and instruction with the information necessary to increase their awareness of the problems and
863 to enable them to deal with them effectively. The Guidelines cover areas such as development,
864 acquisition, authentication, cryopreservation, transfer of cell lines between laboratories,
865 microbial contamination, characterisation, instability and misidentification. Advice is also given
866 on complying with current legal and ethical requirements when deriving cell lines from human
867 and animal tissues, the selection and maintenance of equipment and how to deal with problems
868 that may arise.

869 — Biobanking

870 Scientific research using cell lines has contributed greatly to the understanding of human health.
871 Cell cultures are increasingly used to complement studies using animal models. Although cell lines
872 are important research tools, potential problems have recently been identified. Cell lines have
873 unique characteristics and behaviour that can change as they continue to be passaged. The
874 original phenotype (e.g. expression of specific biomarkers) can be lost or new characteristics or
875 behaviour (e.g. development of tumorigenicity) may develop. It is important to minimize
876 passaging to retain the original characteristics that were present when the cell line was first
877 established. Other problems such as contamination, either with microorganisms or another cell
878 line, and misidentification can also arise. Cultures can become contaminated during cell line
879 establishment or later when cultures are passaged. These problems are often not visible by eye
880 and require specific testing to be detected. To help address these issues, the research community
881 has called for an international effort to create standards for biobanks. The ISO/TC 276 relates to
882 the standardisation in the field of biotechnology processes. The topics include biobanks,
883 bioresources, bioprocessing, analytical methods, and data validation and integration. In this
884 technical committee needs and gaps in standardisation are identified regarding these topics in the
885 field of biotechnology. ISO 20387:2018 was published to provide an overarching standard for
886 biobanks. ISO 21709:2020 provides additional technical specifications for biobanks that handle
887 mammalian cell lines. Such biobanks can demonstrate their competence in biobanking by
888 complying with the specifications within this document, in addition to the requirements
889 prescribed in ISO 20387.

890 ISO 21709:2020 aims to meet the current demand for standardized PSC procedures of biobanks
891 and builds on international consensus agreed by PSC resource centres. This document specifies
892 the establishment, maintenance, characterization, storage and distribution requirements for
893 mouse and human PSCs, providing a general guideline for both biobanking and fundamental
894 research of PSCs. See also ISO 24603:2022.

895 5.3 Biomaterials

896 The scope of this subtopic is to identify the most used **type of biomaterials** for OoC, focusing on
897 both 3D matrices (i.e. scaffolds and hydrogels) and 2D coatings.

898 For each type of biomaterial, **critical characteristics** (e.g. biocompatibility, fabrication method,
899 mechanical properties, architecture, biochemical properties, compatibility with OoC/substrate)
900 are listed and briefly described. As a deeper level of detail and to provide examples, for each type
901 of biomaterial, **specific examples are listed and briefly described, classified according to**
902 **biomaterial origin**: i.e. synthetic, natural, hybrid and decellularized or cell/tissue-derived
903 matrices.

904 There is growing appreciation of the role that the extracellular environment plays in regulating
905 cell behaviour. Mechanical, structural, and compositional cues, either alone or in concert, can
906 drastically alter cell function. Biomaterials have been developed and implemented to present
907 defined subsets of these cues for investigating countless cellular processes as a means of
908 understanding morphogenesis, aging, and disease (Caliari & Burdick, 2016). Extracellular
909 matrices (ECM) not only provide the necessary physical support, tensile strength and scaffolding

910 for cells, but also serves other functions such as presenting bioactive signals to cells and acting as
911 a reservoir for growth factors and other soluble factors to govern cellular fate processes including
912 adhesion, attachment, proliferation, differentiation and apoptosis. In vivo, cells attach to proteins
913 and carbohydrate moieties present in the ECM. Once cells are isolated from tissue and removed
914 from the native matrix, differentiated cells rapidly lose important characteristics when cultured
915 without an adequate supportive microenvironment such as a substrate coating or a feeder layer.
916 It has been shown that in culture cells growing on ECM demonstrate enhanced proliferation and
917 differentiation potential.

918 Significant advances in biomaterials have offered great opportunities to facilitate the construction
919 of tissue/organ model systems with higher fidelity by integrating with microscale technology and
920 stem cell biology. A range of biomaterial systems have been developed toward this goal, and
921 among them the most interesting in the OoC field include **hydrogels, scaffold and 2D coatings**.

922 Main gaps have been identified for hydrogels (mechanical properties, architecture, degradation,
923 crosslinking, chemical composition, sterilization). The possibility to introduce a hydrogel
924 precursor in a OoC setup and to perform its crosslinking in-site is a critical parameter when
925 planning the use of hydrogels for OoC. Also upon crosslinking and integration within the system,
926 stability of the hydrogel may be affected by the microscale and the presence of physical stimuli in
927 the system (e.g. the hydrogel may have to resist to fluid flow). All these parameters should be
928 considered and may require adjustment to standard protocols applied optimized for different
929 applications (e.g. described in ASTM F2150-19 for regenerative medicine applications).

930 Regarding scaffold, many individual scaffold materials are well described and characterised, with
931 some relevant standards in place. A critical aspect that has not been addressed is the impact of
932 integration into a system with fluidic shear force and mechanical stress. This may also impact
933 absorption of molecules and the ability to test biological function or toxicity of agents.

934 Functional 2D coating are well characterized in literature. For example, coating of polystyrene is
935 well established as most widely used substrate for 2D cell culture (as reviewed by (Lerman et al.,
936 2018)) (even if we could not find any available standards). Nevertheless, conclusions cannot be
937 drafted regarding the use of coating within OoC without understanding which materials are used
938 to fabricate OoC (indeed protocols to perform functional coating may be or not available and
939 reproducible for different materials). Efforts will need to be addressed in translating available
940 protocols for coating macroscale substrates into miniaturized setup (with the hypothesis that OoC
941 will be mainly fabricated with materials for which functionalization protocols are available).

942 **5.3.1 List of available standards**

943 — ASTM F2739 – 19 Standard Guide for Quantifying Cell Viability and Related
944 Attributes within Biomaterial Scaffolds

945 — ASTM F2150-19 Standard Guide for Characterization and Testing of Biomaterial
946 Scaffolds Used in Regenerative Medicine and Tissue-Engineered Medical Products

947 — ASTM F2038-18 Standard Guide for Silicone Elastomers, Gels, and Foams Used in
948 Medical Applications Part I & II Formulations and Uncured Materials

949 — ASTM F2315-18 Standard Guide for Immobilization or Encapsulation of Living
950 Cells or Tissue in Alginate Gels

951 — ASTM F748-16 Standard Practice for Selecting Generic Biological Test Methods
952 for Materials and devices

953 — ASTM F3142-16 Standard Guide for Evaluation of in vitro Release of Biomolecules
954 from Biomaterials Scaffolds for TEMPs

955 — ASTM F3354-19 Standard Guide for Evaluating Extracellular Matrix
956 Decellularization Processes

957 **5.3.2 Hydrogels**

958 Hydrogels are water-swollen networks of polymers. Hydrogels have emerged as a promising
959 option for cell culture since they mimic salient elements of native extracellular matrices (ECMs),
960 have mechanics similar to those of many soft tissues, and can support cell adhesion and protein
961 sequestration. Hydrogels can be broadly classified as either natural (e.g. collagen, fibrin, alginate,
962 matrigel), synthetic (e.g. polyacrylamide, polyethylene glycol) or hybrid materials (e.g. hyaluronic
963 acid, polypeptides). Of note, a recent review discussed the application of hydrogels in OoC (Liu et
964 al., 2019). In the following section, we reported considerations on the selection of hydrogel for
965 OoC applications, based on analysis performed on the state of the art and available standards.
966 Although characterization of hydrogels requires consideration of the individual composition and
967 application the hydrogel will be used for, there are common generic requirements that can be
968 summarised as follows.

969 — **Mechanical properties**

970 Hydrogel mechanical properties are important for the stability of the material in culture and may
971 also influence cellular mechanotransduction, which in turn has consequences for cellular
972 behaviours like spreading, migration, and stem cell differentiation. Comprehensive reviews of
973 hydrogel mechanical characterization techniques are available in literature (Oyen, 2014). While
974 mechanical properties of hydrogels are well described in a research setting, especially for
975 commercially available hydrogels, how mechanical properties of hydrogels are changing within
976 OoC setup is not yet systematically addressed.

977 — **Architecture**

978 The mesh size, or molecular porosity, of the hydrogel is typically on the nanometer scale and can
979 influence nutrient flux throughout the matrix. It is correlated to hydrogel swelling behavior and
980 mechanical properties, since lower swelling and higher modulus indicate a smaller mesh size.
981 Details on the characterization of hydrogel swelling ratio and mesh size can be found in several
982 research papers (Peppas et al., 2000). Still characterization of this aspect is rather fragmented and
983 highly dependent on the specific type of hydrogel. A systematic way to characterize architecture,
984 particularly related to the experiment requirements, is missing. Notably, this parameter may be
985 cause of high experimental variability.

986 — **Degradation**

987 Hydrogel degradation can lead to changes in mechanics and swelling over time, which in turn
988 affect cell behaviors such as motility, spreading, and traction force generation. Hydrogels typically
989 degrade through either hydrolytic or enzymatic mechanisms, where hydrolysis occurs throughout
990 the entire hydrogel and enzymatic degradation is local to the presented enzyme. It is important to
991 note that even hydrogels that would be considered nondegradable on the time scale of most cell
992 experiments, may eventually degrade. Degradation and relative method to measure it are well
993 described in available standards applied to a different application (e.g. ASTM F2150-19). We
994 anticipate that application in OoC setup may alter this parameter due to the different timescale and
995 related time course of phenomena. We envision necessity of additional work to fill this gap.

996 — **Crosslinking method**

997 Forming hydrogels for cellular experiments typically involves either encapsulation of viable cells
998 within the material or fabrication of substrates using molds that are later seeded with cells (the
999 latter point is covered in the functional coating section). Hydrogel formation involves the

1000 transition of liquid precursor solutions into solid materials, which can be achieved using either
1001 physical (noncovalent) or chemical (covalent) crosslinking to assemble the hydrogel components.
1002 The chosen crosslinking strategy can have a significant impact on cell viability. It is important that
1003 the polymerization time and reagents be designed so that cell encapsulation occurs in a
1004 cytocompatible manner. Gelation also needs to occur fast enough to prevent the settling of cells
1005 during the encapsulation process. Kinetics of formation and relative methods to characterize it
1006 are well described in available standards applied to different applications, i.e. tissue engineering
1007 (ASTM F2150-19) and medical devices (ASTM 2038-18 Part I). Also, standards referring to
1008 specific hydrogels are available (e.g. ASTM F2315-18 for alginate). However, it is anticipated that
1009 application in OoC setup may alter this parameter due to the different size scale and related time
1010 course of phenomena. We envision necessity of additional work to fill this gap.

1011 — **Biocompatibility**

1012 Biocompatibility is linked to the kinetics of formation and degradation described above, and not
1013 only to the material itself. The ASTM F2739-19 (Standard Guide for Quantifying Cell Viability and
1014 Related Attributes within Biomaterial Scaffolds), describes test methods used to quantify cell
1015 viability and related attributes on non-porous or within porous hard or soft 3D synthetic or
1016 natural-based biomaterials, such as ceramics, polymers, hydrogels, and decellularized
1017 extracellular matrices. The test methods also apply to cells seeded on porous coatings. Thus, this
1018 standard covers all the types of biomaterials described in this chapter. It is anticipated that
1019 application in an OoC setup would not drastically alter this parameter, thus defining a good
1020 starting point.

1021 — **Biological properties**

1022 Some materials interact with cells through integrin–ligand interactions (for example, collagen,
1023 fibrin, polypeptides) or other cell surface receptors (for example, HA), while others are considered
1024 more inert (for example, PEG, polyacrylamide). Biological properties and relative method to
1025 characterize it are well described in available standards applied to a different application (e.g.
1026 ASTM F2150-19). We anticipate that application in an OoC setup would not drastically alter this
1027 parameter, and application in regenerative medicine is anyway more stringent in terms of
1028 biological properties and compatibility thus defining a good starting point.

1029 — **Chemical composition**

1030 Chemical composition of hydrogels is a key parameter that defines previously cited characteristics
1031 and strongly influence reproducibility. While natural matrices, like Matrigel, may lead to the low
1032 reproducibility of engineered tissues/organs (given to a poorly reproducible and defined
1033 composition), chemically defined hydrogels can serve as suitable matrices to improve the
1034 reliability of chip-based tissue models by more precisely controlling the matrix composites in
1035 cellular microenvironment. This parameter is crucial and poorly described in literature, especially
1036 related to OoC applications.

1037 — **Sterilization**

1038 For cell encapsulation, the precursor solutions must be sterilized before hydrogel formation.
1039 Attention should be paid in choosing a technique that will not degrade, denature, or otherwise
1040 alter hydrogel physical properties. Sterilization protocols and related issues are well described
1041 (even if we could not find standards available) for some commercially available hydrogels, which
1042 are typically provided pre-sterilized or may include specific sterilization instructions. A review
1043 provides insights on conventional and emerging technologies for hydrogels sterilization (Bento et
1044 al., 2023). The ASTM standard F2038-18 Part II on Silicone Elastomers, Gels, and Foams Used in
1045 Medical Applications partially addresses sterilization of gels, but without a direct focus only
1046 related to application in medical device and not including cell-laden hydrogels, which are the most
1047 relevant for OoC applications. Overall, description of how to maintain hydrogel sterility also in the

1048 presence of cells (i.e. non impacting biocompatibility) and or to translate sterility protocols to OoC
1049 setups is not well covered in the state of the art.

1050 **5.3.3 Scaffolds**

1051 Scaffolds can be defined as natural or synthetic biomaterials that possess characteristics
1052 appropriate for replacement of extracellular matrix (ECM) in 3D, including mechanical and
1053 biochemical features that support cell adhesion, polarisation and phenotype (Osório et al., 2021).
1054 Surface treatment or cell patterning techniques are employed to influence
1055 adhesion/proliferation/differentiation/migration of cells, which can also be spatially segregated
1056 where appropriate. Scaffolds can be broadly classified as either natural (e.g. based on collagen,
1057 chitosan, alginate, gelatine, decellularized matrix), synthetic (e.g. polycarbonate, ceramic, silicon
1058 based organic polymer Polydimethylsiloxane) or hybrid materials. In the following section,
1059 considerations of the key characteristics that should be considered when choosing a scaffold for
1060 OoC applications (based on analysis performed on the state of the art and available standards) are
1061 reported.

1062 — **Biocompatibility**

1063 For general biocompatibility considerations, see section 5.3.2 Hydrogels. Of note, many of the
1064 materials used for scaffolds are also used for the fabrication of consumables in research and
1065 medical devices, and have been subject to biocompatibility testing and certification, as described
1066 in available standard ASTM F748-16. The potential for batch to batch variation, along with
1067 presence of poorly defined animal-derived aspects (where relevant) should be considered.
1068 Moreover, there is a series of standards setting out critical requirements and associated test
1069 methods for materials and matrices used in scaffolds, e.g. alginate, chitosan salts and hyaluronan.
1070 For example, ASTM F3142-16 is a Standard Guide for Evaluation of in vitro Release of
1071 Biomolecules from Biomaterials Scaffolds for TEMPs.

1072 — **Mechanical properties and architecture**

1073 ASTM published two standards on Silicone Elastomers, Gels, and Foams Used in Medical
1074 Applications (ASTM F2038-18 Part I & Part II) to address formulation and the fabrication process.
1075 ISO standards are available for all the main plastics used with moulding and extrusion processes
1076 e.g. polycarbonate, PMMA, polystyrene, polyethylene, acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene and
1077 polypropylene. Surface treatment or cell patterning techniques can be employed to influence
1078 adhesion and phenotype of cells and facilitate spatial segregation where appropriate. While
1079 mechanical properties of scaffold are well described in existing standards, how mechanical
1080 properties may change within OoC setup is not yet systematically addressed. Elasticity; oxygen
1081 permeability, etc must be tuneable to characteristics of the target organ and adapted to the
1082 microscale.

1083 — **Biochemical properties**

1084 Absorption of molecules circulating in the medium can compromise accuracy of the results. This
1085 has been studied in relation to PDMS, but may apply to several scaffolds of both natural and
1086 synthetic origin. To this regard, no standards exist in terms of test methods, suitable measurement
1087 units and performance criteria (Piergiovanni, Leite, et al., 2021). This is particularly relevant in
1088 toxicity or efficacy studies, where the effective concentration of a test compound is crucial to
1089 accuracy of results on the biological response. Small molecules can also be sequestered by
1090 coatings or bind to proteins/lipids in the medium.

1091 — **Sterilization**

1092 For general sterilization considerations, see section 5.3.2. Hydrogels.

1094 As an additional discussion for scaffolds, specific missing points for decellularized based scaffold
1095 (dECM-based scaffold) should be considered. The preparation of dECM-based biomaterials
1096 consists of two main steps, including the decellularization of a tissue or organ and terminal
1097 sterilization of the dECM, respectively, and both steps are highly effective in obtaining a
1098 biomaterial with the desired properties. DECM-based biomaterials encompass mixtures of
1099 various biomolecules that regulate cell adhesion, proliferation, migration, and differentiation,
1100 such as glycosaminoglycans, adhesion proteins (i.e. laminin, integrin), and structural proteins (i.e.
1101 collagen). Therefore, the selected decellularization and sterilization methods should have a
1102 minimal negative impact on the biochemical and morphological composition as well as
1103 mechanical properties of the decellularized matrix, as described both in literature (Yildiz et al.,
1104 2007) and in available standard ASTM F3354-19.

1105 5.3.4 2D Coatings

1106 **Functional coatings** for cell culture are structural proteins / protein-like substances that have
1107 adherent capabilities and increase cell-substrate interactions in a culture dependent
1108 environment. Biodegradable synthetic polymers such as poly-L-Lysine have been used to provide
1109 coatings that promote the attachment of various anchorage dependent cell types. Natural
1110 polypeptide-based cell attachment factors such as collagen and fibronectin have been effectively
1111 utilised for culture in certain cell lines and primary cell culture. A guide to the composition and
1112 functions of the extracellular matrix is provided by (Karamanos et al., 2021). Of note, an explicit
1113 focus on the precise documentation of coating details (i.e. coating components, amount, volume
1114 of coating, coating period, washing steps, storage after coating) is essential to ensure
1115 reproducibility in general and thus also in OoC applications.

1116 In the context of coatings, it is important to also consider the use of surface treatment to prevent
1117 cell attachment like for spheroids formation. Here, examples of **cell-repellent coating** can be
1118 found in large scale bioreactors and medical devices. In this context, multiple strategies have been
1119 adopted like PEG coatings, Pluronic F-127, certain hydrogels or fluorinated polymers. Note that in
1120 the choice of a specific coating will depend on the application, the type of cell used and the length
1121 of the expected culture in the system as well as the possibility to affect biomolecular adsorption
1122 of the drug tested.

1123 The most important techniques are wet chemical coating, electrospinning, dip-coating and spin-
1124 coating as physically coat substrates (Song et al., 2020); plasma treatment to create a range of
1125 hydrophilic surface finishes that enhance cell adhesion (North et al., 2010; O'Sullivan et al., 2020);
1126 Layer by-layer (LbL) assembly (Fukuda et al., 2018; Matsusaki et al., 2012).

1127 For general biocompatibility considerations, see section 5.3.2 Hydrogels.

1128 5.4 Cell culture conditions

1129 The goal of this subtopic is to identify and share existing standards on the use of media for OoC
1130 culture, focusing on media composition, antibiotic and growth factor use. It is intended to be used
1131 as a guide for researchers who are willing to deepen their understanding on OoC culture.
1132 Regarding the media composition, the level of definition of the media will be considered (i.e.
1133 defined, undefined, semi-defined), as well as the use of animal-free reagents, specific growth
1134 factors and antibiotics.

1135 Moreover, state of the art on different culture conditions within the OoC field are analysed, with a
1136 focus on environmental conditions, physical stimuli, scaling and waste accumulation.

1137 Of note, given the very novel nature of the OoC technology, to date not many standards or
1138 guidelines have been published. Hence, this sub-topic has been drafted with the aim of creating a
1139 checklist/guideline to be followed when OoC experiments need to be set up.

1140 **5.4.1 Cell culture media**

1141 Cell culture media for differentiation purposes are not yet standardised and laboratories
1142 developing cell culture models generate daily their own “homebrew” formulations based on what
1143 was successful in their hands. The result is that multiple different formulations have been utilised
1144 and published for the same cell type or organoid model. While multiple medium formulations may
1145 support growth of the same model, its phenotype and/or genotype may be altered when changing
1146 media. Standardisation on this topic is challenging because of the vast variety of media that are
1147 usually designed on the basis of the different cell culture conditions.

1148 OoC may be composed of single or multi-cell cultures. Depending on the number and type of cells
1149 present, the culture medium may vary. Critical parameters such as viability and functional
1150 phenotype for each cell type should be considered.

1151 Owing to the complexity and requirements of specialised and non-specialised cells there is, as of
1152 today, no common medium that suits all culture conditions.

1153 Documentation is important to ensure reproducibility and standardisation in the OoC field.

1154 — Based upon single type or multi cell type cultures, media specific for certain cell type is often
1155 combined. The used ratios should be documented.

1156 — Documentation of used commercial media, batch and lot numbers

1157 — If homemade media are used, consistent and detailed documentation is required including
1158 batch and lot numbers of individual components, (complete) medium storage, storing
1159 temperatures and preparation

1160 While individual components can be well described, the combination of different media is not
1161 standardized. Medium standardisation is a challenging issue, as the development of the field will
1162 quickly outgrow these standards and might hamper innovation. However it is highly
1163 recommended that media compositions are correctly and systematically addressed in the OoC
1164 field to maximize innovation.

1165 — **Media composition**

1166 Mammalian cell cultures require specialised media. Culture medium is a liquid nutrient consisting
1167 of a mixture of base medium, serum and regulatory factors.

1168 The three basic classes of media are basal medium, reduced-serum medium and serum-free
1169 medium, which differ in their requirement for supplementation with serum. Serum, such as foetal
1170 bovine serum (FBS), is vitally important as a source of growth and adhesion factors, hormones,
1171 lipids and minerals for the culture of cells in basal media. However, using serum in media has
1172 several disadvantages including high cost, specificity, variability between suppliers, and
1173 unwanted effects such as stimulation or inhibition of growth and/or cellular function on certain
1174 cell cultures.

1175 The majority of cell lines grow well in a **basal medium**, supplemented with bovine serum, subject
1176 to batch and source variability, or with an alternative chemically defined additive. Liquid and
1177 powder forms are available from various suppliers, examples include Minimal Essential Medium
1178 (MEM), Dulbecco’s MEM (DMEM), Roswell Park Memorial Institute (RPMI) 1640 amongst others.
1179 These media contain carbohydrates, salts, vitamins, amino acids and a pH buffer system (Gruber
1180 & Jayme, 1994; Ham, 1982; D. W. Jayme & Blackman, 1985).

1181 Many mammalian cell lines can be continuously maintained on a relatively simple medium such
1182 as MEM supplemented with serum, and a culture grown in MEM can probably be just as easily
1183 grown in DMEM or Medium 199. However, when a specialised function is expressed, a more

1184 complex medium may be required. Information for selecting the appropriate medium for a given
1185 cell type is usually available in published literature and may also be obtained from the source of
1186 the cells or cell banks.

1187 If there is no information available on the appropriate medium for a specific cell type, it is
1188 preferable to choose the growth medium and serum empirically, or test several different media
1189 for best results. In general, a good place to start is MEM for adherent cells and RPMI-1640 for cell
1190 suspensions.

1191 — **Reduced-serum media** are basal medium formulations enriched with nutrients
1192 and animal-derived factors, which reduce the amount of serum that is needed.

1193 — **Serum-free medium** (SFM) circumvents issues with the use of animal serum by
1194 replacing the serum with appropriate nutritional and hormonal formulations. Serum-free medium
1195 formulations exist for many primary cultures and cell lines, including recombinant protein
1196 producing lines of Chinese Hamster Ovary (CHO), various hybridoma cell lines, the insect
1197 lines Sf9 and Sf21 (*Spodoptera frugiperda*), and for cell lines that act as hosts for viral
1198 production (i.e. 293, VERO, MDCK, MDBK). One of the major advantages of using serum-free
1199 medium is the ability to make the medium selective for specific cell types by choosing the
1200 appropriate combination of growth factors (Brunner et al., 2010; D. Jayme et al.,
1201 1997). Information for selecting serum-free media is available at [www.fcs-](http://www.fcs-free.org)
1202 [free.org](http://www.fcs-free.org) (van der Valk, 2022).
1203

1204 **5.4.2 Use of antibiotics in OoC cell culture**

1205 Contamination from bacteria, fungi, mycoplasma and yeast are a serious and frequent issue in cell
1206 culture that has to be avoided. This can lead to false results, and at some stage they can irreversibly
1207 and completely destroy the cells in culture. The physiological temperature and humidity in the
1208 incubator, as well as the nutrients in the medium, provide excellent conditions for the growth of
1209 contaminating microorganisms. This can be prevented by adding antibiotics and anti-mycotics to
1210 the cell culture media. However, in order to guarantee reliability and reproducibility of cell culture
1211 findings, the use of antimycotic- and antibiotic-free culture media is recommended (Farzaneh,
1212 2021; Hassan & Ahmad, 2020). In vitro properties of cells including their proliferation, genetic
1213 stability, differentiation or survival, have been shown to be altered by these compounds.

1214 Moreover, genome-wide analyses have identified antibiotic-induced changes in gene expression
1215 and regulation (Figure 3).

1216

Beta-lactam antibiotics (penicillin)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Alteration in protein synthesis ▶ Inhibition of cell proliferation
Aminoglycosides (streptomycin, kanamycin, gentamycin)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Reduction of protein synthesis ▶ Decreased ATP levels ▶ Cytotoxicity
Polyene macrolides (amphotericin B/fungizone, nystatin)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Cell membrane disturbance ▶ Cytotoxicity
*Note: These changes are dosage and cell type dependent.	

1217

1218

Figure 3 - Effects of antibiotics on cell cultures (Kuhlmann, 1995)

1219 Other studies have demonstrated that adding Primocin® to the tissue washing solution of patient-
1220 derived organoids, is able to eliminate the risk of microbial contamination in cultures, and that
1221 the use of Pen/Strep negatively impacts organoids growth (Marinucci et al., 2021).

1222 Although performing studies with antibiotics may be advantageous in terms of contamination and
1223 cell survival, these additional molecules within the medium may affect cell response. Hence,
1224 during experiments aimed at determining the effect of a particular drug molecule, it should be
1225 evaluated whether the use of antibiotics affects cell response to the therapy. If it does, the study
1226 should be performed without antibiotics to obtain the most appropriate and reliable readout from
1227 the OoC.

1228 **5.4.3 Testing for Contamination**

1229 While contamination with microorganisms such as bacteria or fungi is immediately noticeable
1230 with a microscope, contamination with other microorganisms such as mycoplasma can remain
1231 undiscovered, if not specifically tested for. Mycoplasma-contaminated cell cultures are rather
1232 infrequent but may show undesirable functional changes in experiments. For the testing of such
1233 microbes, various companies offer kits based on PCR or ELISA.

1234 Cross-contamination, which is the unwanted introduction of foreign cells into an existing culture,
1235 and cell line misidentification are also problems that must be taken seriously (Almeida et al., 2016;
1236 American Type Culture Collection Standards Development Organization Workgroup ASN-0002,
1237 2010; Cabrera et al., 2006). If it remains undiscovered, a researcher could work with an entirely
1238 different cell line than the initial one without noticing, which renders all results of cell culture
1239 assays invalid. In several papers it has been shown that the penicillin–streptomycin (Pen/Strep)
1240 cocktail inhibits the sphere-forming ability of cancer cells in suspension culture, though it has no
1241 impact in monolayer culture. This effect is correlated with a significant decrease of cancer stem
1242 cells, which hold self-renewal potential.

1243 Detecting microbial and viral infections, including mycoplasma, in cell cultures is crucial for
1244 maintaining the integrity of experiments and ensuring reliable results. No standards have been
1245 identified in what concert contamination with microorganisms, however general considerations

1246 have been proposed to ensure a proper evaluation and prevention of contamination in culture
1247 media.

1248 — Regular monitoring: Perform routine testing to monitor for contamination
1249 regularly.

1250 — Quality control: Utilize positive and negative controls in testing procedures.

1251 — Regular and thorough testing is essential for early detection and mitigation of
1252 microbial and viral contaminations.

1253 — Commercial services: Consider outsourcing to specialized laboratories for
1254 comprehensive testing. It is crucial to tailor the detection methods based on the
1255 specific requirements and characteristics of the cell culture system.

1256 **5.4.4 Environmental conditions**

1257 Environmental conditions in a culture provide the physical and chemical parameters intended to
1258 allow the cells to be cultured in the best and/or more physiologically-relevant conditions, which
1259 can be replicated in vitro. Thus, they should be adjusted according to the needs of the cultured
1260 cells (primary, immortalised, human or animal cell lines). The parameters under consideration
1261 are:

1262 — **Gas Composition**

1263 The design of OoC materials should reflect the varying oxygen permeability seen in different
1264 organs. This not only helps replicate the organ's natural environment but also ensures accurate
1265 cellular responses. Importantly, foaming of a medium that contains serum or proteins (e.g.
1266 albumin) refers to the formation of bubbles or foam in the liquid culture medium. This can occur
1267 due to various reasons, such as excessive agitation, introduction of air during handling, or the
1268 presence of surfactants. In cell culture, particularly when using serum-containing media,
1269 excessive foaming can be problematic as it may introduce air bubbles into the culture, potentially
1270 leading to mechanical stress on cells or affecting the reliability of experimental results. Therefore,
1271 it will be important to minimize bubbling of gas into the media, especially during OoC
1272 experiments, to prevent foaming, air bubble introduction, and potential damage to cells. If needed,
1273 it may be necessary to use anti-foaming agents.

1274 — **pH**

1275 Different organs exhibit distinct pH environments. In OoC, it is crucial to dynamically control pH,
1276 replicating the diverse pH conditions observed in physiological and pathological states. It will
1277 therefore be important to establish dynamic pH control strategies, considering the variations
1278 across different organs and disease states. Part of this is to adjust bicarbonate buffer
1279 concentration and CO₂ levels accordingly. OoCs cultured outside traditional incubators may lack
1280 precise control over CO₂ levels. Using CO₂-independent buffering systems like HEPES will ensure
1281 stable and physiologically relevant pH conditions.

1282 — **Temperature**

1283 Physiological relevance is vital for OoC experiments to accurately mimic in vivo conditions.
1284 Careful temperature control, whether inside or outside an incubator, is necessary for meaningful
1285 results. Therefore, it is essential to ensure that OoCs are kept at 37°C or a physiologically-relevant
1286 temperature, either inside an incubator or using auxiliary equipment when cultured outside.

1287 — **Humidity**

1288 The high volume-to-area ratio in OoC systems can lead to rapid evaporation in static cultures.
1289 Managing humidity or opting for perfusion helps counteract this effect, ensuring stable culture
1290 conditions. Evaporation challenges in static OoC cultures can be addressed by maintaining high
1291 humidity environments or considering perfusion to ensure a constant supply of media. The unique
1292 microscale environment of OoCs requires special attention to the volume-to-area ratio. Strategies
1293 should be employed to maintain consistent humidity levels, particularly in static cultures. It
1294 should be recognized that the high volume-to-area ratio in OoC systems could lead to rapid
1295 evaporation in static cultures, and measures should be implemented to counteract this effect.

1296 — **Physical stimuli**

1297 In replicating physiological conditions within OoC platforms, standardizing mechanical and
1298 electrical stimuli is paramount. Mechanical forces, such as shear stress and compression, crucial
1299 for tissue development, present challenges in terms of compatibility with real-time imaging and
1300 scalability. Despite various technological solutions, the absence of specific standards hinders
1301 result comparison and clinical relevance assessment. To address this, future efforts should
1302 prioritize the development of standardized guidelines, facilitating the use of well-defined and
1303 clinically relevant mechanical and electrical stimuli in OoC studies.

1304 — **Perfusion circuits**

1305 Perfusion circuits are integral to OoC devices, yet the lack of specific standards poses challenges
1306 in implementing and maintaining these systems. Whether unidirectional or bidirectional,
1307 recirculating or single-pass, standardisation is crucial for ensuring reproducibility and reliability.
1308 Specific guidelines should address key considerations like medium replenishment, waste removal,
1309 and challenges associated with distinct perfusion strategies. The absence of comprehensive
1310 standards highlights a critical area for future exploration within the OoC community, aiming to
1311 enhance the standardisation and reliability of experiments involving perfusion circuits.

1312 — **Scaling**

1313 Extreme miniaturisation of in vitro organ and OoC models, without appropriate scaling, can cause
1314 significant structural reorganisation and changes in organ proportions, and this is particularly
1315 important for toxicity and drug screening assays, metabolic studies and PK/PD modelling.
1316 However, scaling remains a significant challenge: the size of the organ, the flow and shear in each
1317 organ module and the total volume of medium must all be scaled to physiological dimensions.
1318 Disproportionately scaled multi-OoC devices do not properly replicate organ-organ interplay and
1319 affect the residence time of medium in the recirculation, thus introducing bias into the
1320 experimental outcome. Currently there are several techniques that have been adopted to
1321 determine the best scaling processes: direct, allometric, multifunctional and residence time-based
1322 scaling, each with its own advantages and disadvantages. Nevertheless, none of them correctly
1323 emulates all the in vivo features in mini-organ models (Leung et al., 2022). Hence, the aim of the
1324 experiment will determine the type of scaling to be adopted.

1325 — **Waste accumulation**

1326 In vitro, every cell type needs a narrow pH range (within 0.2-0.4 pH units) of its optimum to grow.
1327 The production of lactic acid should not exceed the buffering capacity of the medium, as lowering
1328 the pH can inhibit cell growth. High ammonium concentrations as a by-product of glutamine
1329 catabolism can be toxic to cells, causing cytosol vacuolisation and subsequent cell death.
1330 Exchanging the medium prevents these waste product accumulation effects.

1331 However, after every medium exchange the cell secretome is removed and the cells are stimulated
1332 to rebuild their communications network by generating fresh molecules. This effort could
1333 negatively influence their behaviour and not represent their natural state. The influence of

1334 medium exchange has for example been investigated by measuring actin microfilament structure
 1335 directly before and after medium exchange. Such exchange led to a rapid disturbance of stress
 1336 fibre formation and disconnection of cell-cell contacts. Frequent medium exchange is also
 1337 economically detrimental, as medium can contain expensive additives such as growth factors and
 1338 animal serum. Medium exchange cannot however be avoided as lack of nutrients and waste
 1339 accumulation would lead to cell death (Vis et al., 2020).

1340 **5.5 Recommendations**

1341 **5.5.1 Quality controls**

1342 Quality controls steps during the culture and maintenance of cells is a key undertaking and
 1343 without appropriate quality control measures in place, the derived scientific data from OoC
 1344 systems may be affected. Three key areas of quality controls are identified and must be considered
 1345 at different timepoints throughout cell culture.

1346 — **Cell integrity and identity**

1347 Contamination of cells in culture with other widely used cell lines is reported to occur frequently
 1348 and therefore, regular validation of cell identity is critical. Short tandem repeat (STR) typing is the
 1349 main method to determine the exact cell type. Several commercially available molecular methods
 1350 that are used to assessing identity of cell lines is listed in the table below (Table 1).

Species	Assays	Consensus Standard Method	Commercially Available Kit	Commercial Service	Comparative Data
Human	STR	ASN-0002	Yes	Yes	ATCC, DSMZ, JCRB, NCBI**
	SNP	No	Yes	Yes	(Liang-Chu et al., 2015 ^[35]) (Yu et al., 2015 ^[36]) NCBI
Mouse	STR*	No	No	Yes	Unpublished
	SNP	No	Yes	Yes	(Didion et al., 2014 ^[37])
African green monkey	STR*	No	No	No	None
Chinese hamster ovary	STR*	No	No	No	None
Rat	STR*	No	No	No	None
Species-level identification	CO1 DNA barcode	ASN-0003	Yes	Yes	Barcode of Life Data System, NCBI**
	Species-specific primers	No	No	Yes	None needed

1351
 1352 **Table 1: Current status of SNP, STR, and DNA barcode technologies as standard methods for**
 1353 **assessing the identity of cell lines from different species (OECD, 2018)**
 1354

1355 For pluripotent stem cells, it is also important to validate the genomic integrity of the cells in use.
 1356 Commonly used method for validating genomic integrity of PSCs is karyotyping that can help
 1357 monitor chromosomal stability and avoid use of PSCs with genetic abnormalities.

1358 — **Cell function**

1359 As culture conditions may influence the differentiation status and thereby their function, it is
 1360 important to test if the cellular phenotype is maintained prior to incorporation in the OoC. For
 1361 instance, the functionality of liver cells in a pharmacological context of use, could be tested by
 1362 CYP450 activity which is a key player in the metabolism of drugs and xenobiotics. Moreover, when

1363 culturing cells from frozen vials, it is recommended that at least 3 vials are initiated and include
 1364 quality monitoring on the cell viability, proliferation, and specific functional activity for that cell
 1365 type.

1366 — Cell contamination

1367 In addition to contamination of cells with commonly used cell lines, there is potential for
 1368 contamination with microorganisms. Contamination with bacterial and fungal sources are usually
 1369 visible by eye. In addition, unexpected changes in the colour of the culture media or increased
 1370 turbidity could provide key clues to these contaminants. On the other hand, contamination with
 1371 mycoplasma is not immediately evident and these contaminants can have a significant effect on
 1372 cell function. Several commercial assays are available for mycoplasma testing as shown in table
 1373 below (Table 2). In addition to these sources, some cells may contain endogenous viruses that can
 1374 result in the secretion of viral particles or antigens. Although these are not normally considered
 1375 contaminants, they may influence readouts when cells are co-cultured. Regardless of the source
 1376 of contamination, standard operating procedures must be in place to discard positive samples and
 1377 clear the laboratories of the potential source.

Method	Sensitivity	Advantages	Disadvantages
Indirect DNA stain (e.g., Hoechst 33258) with indicator cells (e.g., 3T3)	High	Easy to interpret because contamination amplified	Indirect and thus more time-consuming
Broth and agar culture	High	Sensitive	Slow and may require expert interpretation
PCR	High	Rapid	Requires optimisation
Nested PCR	High	Rapid	More sensitive than direct PCR, but more likely to give false positives
Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA)	Moderate	Rapid	Limited range of species detected
Autoradiography	Moderate	Rapid	Can be difficult to interpret if contamination is at low level
Immunostaining	Moderate	Rapid	Can be difficult to interpret if contamination is at low level
Direct DNA stain (e.g., Hoechst 33258)	Low	Rapid, cheap	Can be difficult to interpret

1378
 1379 **Table 2: Mycoplasma detection methods, their sensitivity, and advantages and**
 1380 **disadvantages** (OECD, 2018)

1381 5.5.2 Minimum reporting requirements for cells used in OoC systems

1382 Characterisation of the cell origin should be reported using ‘State of the art’ / best practice
 1383 approaches to confirm cellular phenotype for primary cells e.g. for mesenchymal stromal cells
 1384 (Dominici et al., 2006). Some key points of consideration are outlined below.

1385 — When using established cell lines: Undifferentiated status should be monitored by
 1386 quantitative marker analysis

1387 — When using new cell lines: In depth characterization is recommended (with well
 1388 documented techniques) where possible. In case of large panels of new lines, take
 1389 a subset and confirm pluripotency by differentiation assays. For remaining lines,
 1390 quantitative marker analysis monitoring undifferentiated status is minimally
 1391 recommended.

- 1392 — When using new cell lines and non-established methodologies: Confirmation of
1393 undifferentiated status and pluripotency should be comprehensive
- 1394 — Larger panel of undifferentiated status
- 1395 — Proof of capacity of differentiation into the three germ layers
- 1396 — Additional multi-parametric analysis recommended
- 1397 — For nomenclature and unique identification, the use of hiPSCreg is
1398 recommended.
- 1399 — Ensure well documented SOPs should be used throughout the isolation process.
- 1400 — Commercially available cell lines: product number, company, lot number,
1401 authentication certificates and time in culture should be reported. Cell lines
1402 should be authenticated routinely by Single Tandem Repeat (STR) analysis.
- 1403 — Primary, immortalized, or stem cell derived.
- 1404 — Maintenance conditions (passage number, culture-ware, growth factors, culture
1405 medium and coating if applicable)

1406 **6 Engineering**

1407 **6.1 Introduction**

1408 One of the core difficulties of creating an OoC system is the challenge associated with the selection
1409 of appropriate hardware, installing, and operating it. What are the best pieces of hardware to run
1410 OoC experiments on a controlled, reliable, and repeatable way? How to set up a system /
1411 experiment as efficiently as possible? For this it might help if the components and instruments
1412 were designed in such a way that plug and play installation is possible. Therefore, there should be
1413 compatibility between components and instruments. Interfaces (physical and "software/data")
1414 between the modules of the system should be standardized to ensure compatibility. Other
1415 potential topics for standardisation that would help the engineering of OoCs (i.e. sterilization
1416 techniques, material properties, etc.) are also explored here in this Engineering section. These
1417 other topics are complementary to interfacing standards, but may also be applied in OoC
1418 engineering contexts in which interfacing standards are not applied.

1419 It may be valuable to current standardisation efforts in OoC engineering to consider a "hot spot"
1420 of working conditions that has been identified in the adjacent field of microfluidics (ISO
1421 22916:2022). This "hot spot" describes working conditions of a large group of users and includes
1422 parameters of note such as: a pressure of 2 bar or less, a temperature of 4-50 °C, flow rates of
1423 1µl/min to 100 µl/min, water-based fluids containing biomolecular matter and, the fact that some
1424 parts might also need to withstand harsher conditions during cleaning and / or sterilization. These
1425 conditions might be very similar to the working restriction for the hardware used in OoC, but this
1426 should be verified. Some additional OoC-specific working conditions will be discussed in the
1427 following sections.

1428 As a general note: Please be aware that the standardisation to be defined is not about defining the
1429 products, but only describing the requirements the products should meet to ensure compatibility.
1430 I.e. hardware standardisation is not so much about describing what the hardware should look like,
1431 but how to qualify its performance. Furthermore, due to the diversity in applications, specific
1432 requirements may apply only to certain classes.

1433 While this section covers standards relevant to the engineering of OoC systems, section 7.2 covers
1434 the related topic of standards relevant to hardware setup processes. Section 7.2 bears mention
1435 here as the parameters controlled by hardware setup processes may also inform engineering
1436 design decisions and therefore standards.

1437 **6.2 Material properties and information to be supplied by the manufacturer**

1438 In general, one should be able to rely on relevant material specific information from the supplier.
1439 For many material properties this is well covered, for instance optical and mechanical properties,
1440 hydrophilicity etc. However, OoC applications have some additional requirements, especially
1441 regarding issues related to materials in contact with the tissue or the fluid; for instance the used
1442 materials should not exhibit toxicity to cells and should not interfere with their functioning; they
1443 should be chemically stable and resistant to biodegradation. Standardisation is preferred in two
1444 manners.

1445 Firstly, standardisation of the description of the materials in respect to OoC relevant properties.
1446 This means that all these properties need good definitions, methods to measure them and
1447 methods to qualify materials. This does not mean that the supplier is expected to supply
1448 confidential information about the material itself or the manufacturing process as these are not
1449 relevant for the user.

1450 Secondly, standards on how to measure and qualify materials may be of interest. Existing ISO
1451 standards can be used as a reference, from which adaptations to OoC could be needed.

1452 For a more in-depth discussion on standardisation of biomaterials applied as cell culture
1453 substrates (i.e. hydrogels, scaffolds and functional biocoatings) see section 5.3. In this section we
1454 focus more broadly on materials that may be used by engineers in the context of OoC.

1455 **6.2.1 List of available standards**

1456 OoC requirements might be a mix or compromise between the material requirements for medical
1457 devices and those for implantable devices.

1458 A selection of existing standards for medical and implantable devices are listed below. Each cover
1459 some combination of: material performance requirements, material testing methods, or
1460 information reporting requirements. The listed standards have been loosely categorized based on
1461 whether they are applied to a specific class of material, or are more material agnostic.

1462 **Material Specific Standards:**

1463 — ASTM F2027, Standard Guide for Characterization and Testing of Raw or Starting
1464 Biomaterials for Tissue- Engineered Medical Products

1465 — ASTM F2212, Standard Guide for Characterization of Type I Collagen as Starting
1466 Material for Surgical Implants and Substrates for Tissue Engineered Medical
1467 Products (TEMPs)

1468 — ISO 3826 (all parts), Plastics collapsible containers for human blood and blood
1469 components

1470 — ISO 5832 (all parts), Implants for surgery — Metallic materials

1471 — ISO 5834 (all parts), Implants for surgery — Ultra-high-molecular-weight
1472 polyethylene

1473 — ISO 5838 (all parts), Implants for surgery — Metallic skeletal pins and wires

1474 — ISO 6474-1:2019, Implants for surgery — Ceramic materials — Part 1: Ceramic
1475 materials based on high purity alumina

1476 — ISO 7153-1:2016, Surgical instruments — Materials — Part 1: Metals

1477 **Material Agnostic Standards:**

1478 — ISO/TS 23565:2021, Biotechnology — Bioprocessing — General requirements
1479 and considerations for equipment systems used in the manufacturing of cells for
1480 therapeutic use

1481 — ISO 20417:2012, Medical devices - Information to be supplied by the
1482 manufacturer

1483 — ISO 16142-1:2016, - Medical devices — Recognized essential principles of safety
1484 and performance of medical devices — Part 1: General essential principles and
1485 additional specific essential principles for all non-IVD medical devices and
1486 guidance on the selection of standards

1487 — ISO 7405:2018, Dentistry — Evaluation of biocompatibility of medical devices
1488 used in dentistry

1489 — ISO 10993 (all parts), Biological evaluation of medical devices

1490 **6.2.2 Areas requiring standardisation**

1491 Below, we identify areas in which conforming to standards (existing or to be developed) might
1492 add immediate value to the field of OoC. The list of existing standards given in section 6.2.1 may
1493 already apply to some of the identified areas and could be consulted before developing OoC
1494 specific standards.

1495 Firstly, a standard specifying information the manufacturer should supply for a given product.

1496 Secondly, standards on how to measure and qualify materials. Existing ISO standards can be used
1497 as a reference, from which adaptations to OoC could be needed.

1498 The following topics should be included:

1499 — Leaching of material, for instance in the case of PDMS un-crosslinked oligomers,
1500 can be problematic for cell cultures as it can cause toxicity in cells and alter their
1501 behaviour.

1502 — Cleanliness of the surface, for instance residues from the fabrication process.

1503 — (Oxygen) permeability.

1504 — Biocompatibility.

1505 — Absorption.

1506 The topics above are more or less easily defined, with one notable exception. Biocompatibility is
1507 defined as the ability of a biomaterial to induce or not induce an appropriate host response in a
1508 specific application. It is often a relative quantity appreciated through a comparison of behaviour
1509 in relation to reference materials. Generally, it results from a set of interactions at the material-
1510 tissue interface (unstable extra-physiological situation). Depending on the nature of the device
1511 contact, different biological risks need to be evaluated:

1512 — Cytotoxicity, sensitization, irritation, material mediated pyrogenicity, acute
 1513 systemic toxicity, subacute/subchronic toxicity

1514 — Chronic toxicity/hemocompatibility/genotoxicity

1515 — Carcinogenicity

1516 6.3 Sensors and actuators in the Organ-on-Chip space

1517 Within the OoC space, actuators and sensors are commonplace and allow, for example: different
 1518 degrees of stimulation, automated recording of assays, flow generation, and flow measurement.
 1519 The following sections will present: sensors, actuators, the connection between the sensors and
 1520 the actuators and the measurement of fluids and flow.

1521 6.3.1 Sensors

1522 As OoCs technologies progress, the need for increased information output as well as better quality
 1523 control processes is leading to the integration of more sensors. This comes with increased cost
 1524 and complexity of OoC systems.

1525 There is a clear need for OoC-specific sensors, or sensors specifically adapted for OoC from other
 1526 fields. This can only happen when the supply chain is aware of this need and receives guidance
 1527 from the OoC community in the form of whitepapers, guidelines and standards.

1528 Important aspects for sensors to be used in OoC systems are:

Specification	Aspects to consider		
Measurement Accuracy:	Signal to noise ratio	Resolution	Repeatability and reproducibility
Calibration:	Method and frequency	Drift rate	Dependence on conditions
Measurement deviations:	Temperature and pressure dependence	Cross-sensitivities	Electronic interferences
Access to analyte	Transparency and sizing of optical window	Fouling of sensor surfaces	Membranes or coatings

1529

1530 6.3.2 Actuators

1531 Mechanical actuation is one of the key aspects and advantage of OoCs with respect to standard in
 1532 vitro models. The type of stimuli can range from shear stress, compression, shear strain, stretch
 1533 or a combination. To mimic this actuation, specialized equipment is being used. Note that the
 1534 current equipment is only a selection of the capabilities of mechanical stimulation, but this could
 1535 change due to the advancement in OoCs. The main technologies used are systems to generate
 1536 shear stress using a liquid or to apply active (compression, stretch, shear strain) mechanical forces
 1537 to the cells or 3D – cell structures. This aspect is covered by the section of this roadmap in section
 1538 6.3.4. Other equipment relies on parts that mechanically move onto the cells generating similar
 1539 type of stimuli as by the pressure systems. For both types of equipment, it is key to have a control
 1540 on the accuracy and the stability of the mechanical forces generated in the model. The technology

1541 to apply these forces and the requirements are very application specific, and less suitable for
1542 standardisation, especially while this field is so much in development.

1543 Some materials are stiffer than others, which might have an impact on the mechanical behaviour
1544 of the system. Specification of stiffness should be supplied by the material supplier. This aspect is
1545 covered further in section 6.2.

1546 One specific type of actuator that might need a bit more attention as it is currently probably the
1547 most used actuator by the OoC community are pumps. In OoC pumps have been used to apply well
1548 controlled flow to mimic blood circulation. Again, due to the diversity in OoC it might not be
1549 feasible to standardize these pumps, but it makes sense to standardize the information that a
1550 pump supplier should supply to the user, i.e. a product datasheet. The relevant technical
1551 information from the datasheet will enable end-users to compare the performance of the
1552 microfluidic pumps and to choose the most fitting pump for their application. Without a
1553 standardized datasheet, the comparison of the performance of different microfluidic pumps is
1554 often not possible due to the lack of similar information or divergent definitions of similar
1555 performance characteristics.

1556 It is also important to note that although the pumps may give an accurate output under ideal
1557 conditions it is difficult to determine whether the same type of flow rate is achieved after
1558 integration into a platform. This would need to be further investigated by the company supplying
1559 the platforms. Here, for example, the supplier should determine whether the flow measured after
1560 integration is expected to be consistent with the ideal output flow, or they should provide a
1561 datasheet which correlates the actual flow through given fluidic resistances with the one reported
1562 under ideal conditions. For the related topic of measuring flows, see section 6.3.4 below. The same
1563 process as for the flow would have to be performed for pressure-based actuators.

1564 **6.3.3 Connection of sensors and actuators to instrumentation**

1565 It is a challenge to effectively deploy sensors in complex applications like OoC, given the
1566 interoperability issues that may arise when attempting to integrate sensors from multiple
1567 vendors. Hardware compatibility, wired/wireless connectivity, and security are among the issues
1568 that need standardisation. In general, the sensors and instruments are selected based on their
1569 individual requirements and not necessarily guaranteed to work with each other smoothly. For
1570 this hardware and software standards are needed. The application specific operational
1571 requirements should be generalized to derive standard application layer interfaces between
1572 sensors and instruments.

1573 **6.3.4 Measurement of flows and fluids**

1574 Flow rate control is critical for most microfluidic applications and is often accomplished by
1575 external flow generators connected to the microfluidic chip. Four of the most common types of
1576 flow generators used are: peristaltic pumps; syringe pumps; pressure-driven flow generators and
1577 piezo electric pumps.

1578 Live flow monitoring can be achieved using flow sensors. An immense variety of flow sensors
1579 using different fields of physics are available. Not all of them are suitable for microchannel flows.
1580 Choosing the right microfluidic flow meter adapted to the flow regime and fluid is critical for
1581 accurate measurements. Apart from mechanical technology, there are many non-thermal flow
1582 measurement solutions available. Some of them involve optics, acoustics or electrochemical
1583 phenomena.

1584 In order to ensure the control of flow in an OoC device, it is necessary to have appropriately
1585 calibrated flow generators traceable to SI units. There are several flow generator measurement
1586 methods standardised for macro application which may be used for OoC as well.

1587 There are several factors that can influence the accuracy and stability in flow control, mainly: the
1588 chosen flow generator, the fluidic circuit, the liquid properties, and leakage. The flow rate can be
1589 considerably affected by leakage in the system, often this happens in the connecting points.
1590 Leakage can also occur in case of delamination of the chip, or when cracks appear due to
1591 overpressure or destructive modification of the chip material (due to over-heat for example).

1592 **6.3.5 List of available standards**

1593 — **Sensors**

1594 There are no standards for OoC specific sensors. There are, however, multiple standards for good
1595 measurement practices, and standards exist for the application of sensors for physical-, chemical-
1596 or biochemical parameters in adjacent application domains. Examples include:

1597 — ISO 14511:2019, Measurement of fluid flow in closed conduits – thermal mass
1598 flowmeter

1599 — ISO/TS 23367-1:2022, Nanotechnologies — Performance characteristics of
1600 nanosensors for chemical and biomolecule detection

1601 — ISO 14511:2019, Measurement of fluid flow in closed conduits – thermal mass
1602 flowmeters

1603 — **Connection of sensors and actuators to instrumentation**

1604 At this point there are no OoC specific standards available yet, inspiration might come from:

1605 CEN ISO/IEEE 11073 is an internationally adopted family of standards developed to enable
1606 complete connectivity between medical, healthcare, and wellness devices.

1607 — **Measurement of flows and fluids**

1608 There are some existing standards for flow control and leakage which can be used for OoC.
1609 However, it should be investigated if these are good enough or should be adapted

1610 Standards found by this group include:

1611 — IEC 60601-2-24:2012: Medical electrical equipment - Part 2-24: Particular
1612 requirements for the basic safety and essential performance of infusion
1613 pumps and controllers

1614 — AAMI TIR 101: Fluid Delivery Performance Testing For Infusion Pumps

1615 — ISO 4185:1980, Measurement of liquid flow in closed conduits - Weighing
1616 method

1617 As the number of non-OoC applications to which this topic is relevant is large, discovery of other
1618 standards is likely still needed

1619 **6.3.6 Areas requiring standardisation**

1620 — **Sensors**

1621 Standardisation of sensors should include:

1622 — Dead volume

- 1623 — Flow rates
- 1624 — Standard interface to enable easy and reliable integration of sensors in OoC
- 1625 systems, either tube based or tube less integration
- 1626 — Definition of sensor specifications
- 1627 — Reporting of accuracy and limitations of employed sensors

1628 Furthermore, the OoC community should specify what development in the area of sensors is
 1629 needed to be better equipped for use in particular applications. This should be stimulated through
 1630 white papers or guidelines.

1631 — **Actuators**

1632 Standardisation of actuators should include:

- 1633 — Naming,
- 1634 — Schematics/symbols,
- 1635 — Technology characteristics,
- 1636 — General working conditions,
- 1637 — Electronical characteristics,
- 1638 — Mechanical characteristics, and
- 1639 — Flow characteristics.

1640 Some of the topics are already being approached by the technical Committee ISO/TC 48
 1641 Laboratory equipment. However, the specific requirements, especially in regard to flow
 1642 characteristics, from the OoC community should also be explored.

1643 — **Connection of sensors and actuators to instrumentation**

1644 Introducing standards to ensure interoperability of sensors and actuators may be of value to both
 1645 users and producers. Users could benefit from a wider selection of compatible products to choose
 1646 from while producers may find unexpected markets for their products. Potential targets for sensor
 1647 and actuator interoperability standards include:

- 1648 — Physical hardware used for interfacing
- 1649 — Software
- 1650 — Wired/wireless interfacing
- 1651 — Security
- 1652 — Application layer interfaces

1653 — **Measurement of flows and fluids**

1654 Standardisation should focus on the measurement methods of flow generators. The following
 1655 elements should be included:

- 1656 — Flow generator
- 1657 — The microchip
- 1658 — The liquid properties
- 1659 — Leakage

1660 **6.4 Modular integration of a microfluidic system**

1661 Enforcing a standard set of OoC devices, or even a standard set of OoC fabrication pipelines seems
1662 counterproductive given the current state of the art. Devices are highly application specific,
1663 production volumes are relatively low, and the fabrication is often done in house by end users
1664 with all processes and materials chosen as seems fit.

1665 In this design paradigm, an often-taken practical way forward is to create the systems from a
1666 combination of inhouse specialized parts and off the shelf parts from external suppliers. Those
1667 suppliers cannot create different products for the many different applications, unless at high cost.
1668 Standardisation that facilitates the usage of components and subsystems for different applications
1669 might therefore be useful. Such standards come down to standards describing interfaces between
1670 (off the shelf) components and OoC system. Currently, there are two major approaches for
1671 integration of microfluidic based devices: 1) Connecting the components with tubes. 2) Placing
1672 the components on a chip or manifold.

1673 A tube-based concept offers maximal flexibility in terms of configuration, component selection
1674 and relative low investment, disadvantages are:

- 1675 — Large dead volume.
- 1676 — It takes some time for assembly.
- 1677 — Reliability concerns related to the high number of handmade connections.

1678 Often this approach is used in the development stage, while it is a relative low cost and flexible
1679 approach. Advancing from this to an industrialised concept often requires designing a manifold
1680 based construction, requiring a complete redesign and often needing another selection of
1681 components.

1682 The tube-based set up is especially complicated due to the diversity of tube connection systems.
1683 Connection systems in use are designed for other applications and requirements (for instance
1684 Luer for medical instruments and flat-bottom fittings for high pressure applications) and are, as a
1685 rule, either not reliable enough, have high internal volume, or are too expensive.

1686 The other approach, mounting components on a manifold, offers high reliability, low dead volume
1687 and, when a top-down approach is used, potentially a straightforward assembly. The
1688 disadvantages are inflexibility and the high start-up cost.

1689 The Microfluidics Association is currently discussing with a group of companies a modular
1690 fabrication process where the same base components can be used in a tube based and in a
1691 manifold-based variant. This would facilitate the transfer from research to industry, shortening
1692 the commercialization time. It offers flexibility in the design phase, while enduring seamless
1693 transfer to a more industrial concept.

1694 The tube-based system is based on a top-down connection system where each component is
1695 placed on an adapter and tubes are used between the adapters. The adapters have threaded holes
1696 for flat-bottom fittings for 1/16 inch tubes. This is a proven technology, making it less of a barrier
1697 to entry for the microfluidics community (as opposed to developing another connector) and the

1698 parts can be made at low cost. The fact that the tubing approach still uses top-down connections
 1699 offers a path towards further integration by the manifold approach, in which the components are
 1700 fixed on a manifold, without tubing (see below). For both approaches the same components can
 1701 be used, only the adapters and tubes are replaced by a manifold (Figure 4).

1702

1703 **Figure 4. Microfluidic interfacing for components in different phases of product**
 1704 **development**

1705

1706 The concept also allows for integration with microfluidic chips or sensors and adheres to ISO
 1707 22916:2022.

1708 Note that while OoCs are not necessarily microfluidic, microfluidic perfusion is very widely used,
 1709 in particular for systems designed towards coupling of several tissue models in series. Therefore,
 1710 whatever workflow is selected, microfluidics is likely to be an essential element of it.

1711 **6.4.1 List of available standards**

- 1712 — ISO 22916:2022, Microfluidic devices — Interoperability requirements for
- 1713 dimensions, connections and initial device classification.

1714 **6.4.2 Areas requiring standardisation**

1715 Potential targets for standardized interfacing include:

- 1716 — Heterogenous integration: interfacing between tubing-based and manifold-based
- 1717 systems
- 1718 — Tube based integration: Tube dimensions, type of connection of tubing to
- 1719 component.
- 1720 — Manifold based integration: footprint of the component, position of microfluidic
- 1721 ports, clamping system and exclusion zone.

1722 6.5 Hardware and Techniques from Existing Cell Culture Pipelines

1723 In this section we cover areas in which the existing hardware and techniques used in cell culture
1724 are relevant to OoC. The identified areas are either currently in use in the field of OoC or are
1725 expected to become relevant. Many of them may benefit from OoC specific standardisation.

1726 6.5.1 Sterilization quality

1727 Sterilization is important for OoC devices to avoid contamination in the biological cultures. The
1728 suppliers of systems and materials are responsible for this but need guidelines from the user
1729 community. Sometimes the part needs to be sterilized by the user, for instance when the part is
1730 reused. In that case the user should be able to follow the instructions for sterilization from the
1731 supplier. When the chip is expected to be used without an extra sterilization step after fabrication,
1732 the materials and fabrication tools should be sterilized to ensure aseptic cell culture conditions. It
1733 is an obligation for the OoC community to set rules for sterilization quality. This should include
1734 specifying appropriate sterilization techniques. Each of them has its own pros or cons and might
1735 have an influence on the part's materials. A few examples of techniques that can be used:

1736 — Sterilization by radiation: Radiation such as UV for 30 minutes can damage DNA
1737 and therefore be a good tool to sterilize objects.

1738 — 70% ethanol: Metal tools such as triceps can be sterilized by submerging in 70%
1739 ethanol, followed by airdrying.

1740 — Autoclavation: Moist heat sterilization is a procedure in which heated, high-
1741 pressure steam is used to sterilize an object (at 121-degree °C, 1.03 bar pressure
1742 for 15-20 minutes). You can sterilize labware, glass articles, pipettes, and culture
1743 media with the help of an autoclave. PDMS chips, tubing and connectors for OoC
1744 can be sterilized by autoclavation, however material properties will likely change.

1745 — Filter sterilization: (heat sensitive) liquids can be filter sterilized by the use of a
1746 syringe and filter membrane. Common filter sizes are 0.22µm and 0.45µm.

1747 — Gamma irradiation

1748 — Ethylene oxide treatments

1749 Suppliers and users should be aware that sterilization might have an influence on characteristics
1750 of the device; think of dimensions and surface quality of the device. It could also leave toxic
1751 residues. As OoC devices will be used in an aseptic environment, it is important to keep the
1752 material properties and sterilization possibilities in mind when engineering the devices.

1753 6.5.2 Incubators

1754 Control of physical cell culture parameters (pH, temperature, etc.) is essential to support the living
1755 material inside the OoC system. Large scale incubators that can encompass an entire OoC system
1756 or setup are a common way to achieve this. Alternative incubators to the common MRC incubator
1757 could be heating blocks or custom-made devices that control cell culture parameters or control
1758 parameters locally in the OoC devices.

1759 Regardless of the type of incubator, control over all the prescribed conditions for air, CO₂,
1760 temperature and humidity required for maintaining cells and tissues is essential. Secondly,
1761 connection with the peripheral equipment is an essential point to consider, i.e. the communication
1762 of pumps, sensors etc. Generally, incubators do not have integrated flow control facilities. This

1763 might have disadvantages and should be in the Roadmap as a potential issue. Another aspect to
1764 consider is the option of having multiple OoCs inside the incubator to facilitate parallel
1765 experiments to increase flexibility and throughput. Furthermore, ideally one would like to be able
1766 to do all possible experiments while the OoC device stays in the incubator. That might mean
1767 providing access to retrieve the biological material for further analysis and / or an optical window
1768 for visual inspection; sometimes even a microscope is inside the enclosure. It remains to be seen
1769 if the incubator should adhere to standard dimensions and tolerances already being used for
1770 common lab ware, such as multi-well plates, glass slides, coverslips and petri dishes.

1771 At this moment there are no specific standards for the incubators, however manufacturers do
1772 provide certificates in which they outline calibration, operating windows of temperatures, gas,
1773 etc.

1774 **6.5.3 Integration of microfluidics and microplate workflow**

1775 Most cell culture workflows are based on the use of microplates, also known as micro-well or
1776 microtiter plates. These microplates are highly standardized and system suppliers take well care
1777 that their instruments adhere to these standards. Different steps in the workflow run on different
1778 instruments (for instance incubators, readers etc.) Microplates offer a high throughput solution,
1779 based on massive parallelization of experiments and highly automated workflow that can be
1780 adapted to specific demands. OoC experiments, on the other hand, are typically lower throughput,
1781 but produce high content information about organ response to stimuli over long periods of time.
1782 Comparable to the way a well is part of a larger microplate, in OoCs, a micro-reaction-chamber
1783 (MRC) containing a model of the organ is a part of a larger fluidic system. In practice there are
1784 many mixed concepts, in particular microplates with microfluidics integrated.

1785 Common to both the microfluidic chips and the standard microplates used in the OoC field is that
1786 the cellular model (or the organ) is physically in a MRC. This MRC is usually connected to a fluidic
1787 system which can be supported by microfluidic connectors, pipetting robots or others.

1788 The lack of a standardized description of the MRC separates it from the used fluidic system (e.g.
1789 static, continuous flow, periodic flow) and the technology used for it (manual pipetting,
1790 microfluidic channels, pipetting robots, pumps, etc.).

1791 **6.5.4 Microplate limitations**

1792 Many systems in use rely on the existing ANSI SLAS 4-2004 (R2012) SBS micro plate format
1793 standard. This defines plate dimensions and allows inter-operability between common laboratory
1794 tools much as liquid handlers, imagers etc. However, other important aspects are undefined (such
1795 as orientation, numbering, plate flatness, plate nest, labelling, etc) which leads to inter-operability
1796 challenges. In addition, there is interest in evolving this standard to be more digital and smarter
1797 and this could better support the OoC community. Therefore, the integration of electronic
1798 connections in the plates to pumps and sensors should be considered. In case flow is required in
1799 a OoC system, requirements for the microplate to apply flow should be considered.

1800 **6.5.5 List of available standards**

1801 — **Sterilization**

1802 In the health care sector and for medical devices several standards for sterilization are available.
1803 The OoC community should study existing guidelines and standards for medical devices to check
1804 if these are applicable or should be adapted. These standards might be used as reference material
1805 or input for standards on OoC sterilization.

1806 — ISO/TS 22421:2021, Sterilization of health care products — Common
1807 requirements for sterilizers for terminal sterilization of medical devices in
1808 health care facilities

- 1809 — ISO 22441:2022, Sterilization of health care products — Common
1810 requirements for sterilizers for terminal sterilization of medical devices in
1811 health care facilities
- 1812 — ISO 11137, part 1-4 Sterilization of health care products — Radiation
- 1813 — ISO/TS 21387:2020, Sterilization of medical devices — Guidance on the
1814 requirements for the validation and routine processing of ethylene oxide
1815 sterilization processes using parametric release
- 1816 — ISO 11135 (all parts), Sterilization of health-care products — Ethylene oxide
1817 — Requirements for the development, validation and routine control of a
1818 sterilization process for medical devices
- 1819 — ISO 11138 (all parts), Sterilization of health care products — Biological
1820 indicators
- 1821 — ISO 11140 (all parts), Sterilization of health care products — Chemical
1822 indicators
- 1823 — ISO 7886 (all parts), Sterile hypodermic syringes for single use
- 1824 — ISO 8536 (all parts), Infusion equipment for medical use
- 1825 — ISO 8537:2016, Sterile single-use syringes, with or without needle, for insulin
- 1826 — ISO 13408 (all parts), Aseptic processing of health care products
- 1827 — ISO 17665-2:2006, Sterilization of health care products , Part 1:
1828 Requirements for the development, validation and routine control of a
1829 sterilization process for medical devices
- 1830 — ISO 17665-2:2006, Sterilization of health care products, Part 2: Guidance on
1831 the application of ISO 17665-1
- 1832 — ISO 17665-3:2006, Sterilization of health care products, Part 3: Guidance on
1833 the designation of a medical device to a product family and processing
1834 category for steam sterilization
- 1835 — **Microplates**
- 1836 The following existing standards on microplates were identified
- 1837 — ANSI SLAS 1-2004 (R2012): Footprint Dimensions
- 1838 — ANSI SLAS 2-2004 (R2012): Height Dimensions
- 1839 — ANSI SLAS 3-2004 (R2012): Bottom Outside Flange Dimensions
- 1840 — ANSI SLAS 4-2004 (R2012): Well Positions
- 1841 — ANSI SLAS 6-2012: Well Bottom Elevation
- 1842 — ANSI SLAS 4-2004 (R2012) SBS micro plate format

1843 **6.5.6 Areas requiring standardisation**

1844 — **Sterilization**

1845 Useful standards for OoC work could include:

- 1846 — Sterilization techniques to be used;
- 1847 — Which technique may be used on which material;
- 1848 — Minimum requirements per technique to ensure the sterilization quality and
- 1849 how is this quality measured.

1850 — **Incubators**

1851 A standard on incubators for OoC applications should include minimum requirements on design
1852 and functionality. This may include:

- 1853 — Providing access to retrieve biological samples;
- 1854 — Optical window;
- 1855 — Standard dimensions and tolerances;
- 1856 — Integrated flow control facilities.

1857 — **Microplates**

1858 There is a need to extend the existing standards on microplate format to accommodate OoC
1859 workflows, Opportunities include:

- 1860 — Orientation
- 1861 — Numbering
- 1862 — Plate flatness
- 1863 — Plate nesting
- 1864 — Labelling
- 1865 — Application of Flow
- 1866 — Electronic Connections

1867 **6.6 Bioprinting**

1868 Bioprinting is a technique where bio-ink (biomaterial that contains cells) is used to fabricate a
1869 tissue construct that mimics the 3D geometry and structure of native tissues. These complex
1870 physiological constructs can be incorporated / printed into OoC devices. The incorporation of cells
1871 in a controllable manner (with respect to shear stress, and desired morphology, dimensions and
1872 direction), makes this technique attractive for use in fabrication of microfluidic systems.

1873 Examples of 3D bioprinting techniques used in fabrication of microfluidic devices are:

- 1874 — Extrusion based
- 1875 — Multi-material bioprinting

1876 — Co-axial bioprinting, and

1877 — Laser assisted bioprinting/SLA (photocurable inks)

1878 Often the bio-ink is used in fluidic form and crosslinked using: UV radiation, or a chemical or
1879 enzymatic crosslinker. Bioprinting systems can contain one single nozzle or multiple nozzles. For
1880 OoC devices 3D printing is furthermore used in research to generate 1D, 2D and 3D printed PDMS
1881 chips that can be used to bioprint cell-laden structures in or for printing sacrificial inks to generate
1882 hollow channels within the bioprinted construct. Bioprinting is widely used in the fabrication of
1883 microfluidic chips for vasculature-on-chip, lung-on-chip, heart tissue-on-chip, liver-on-chip,
1884 kidney-on-chip, cancer-on-chip, and BBB-on-chip.

1885 As many different approaches are taken, reproducibility is low and there is a lack of
1886 standardisation. Bioprinting fidelity is limited by printing accuracy and resolution, bioink
1887 materials, printhead size and printing speed.

1888 Guidelines for reporting details are, at this stage, more important than standardisation of the
1889 various techniques. For example, reporting guidelines would be useful for: crosslinking,
1890 needle/nozzle production, methacrylation of bioink, bio ink viscosity, shear stress level etc.
1891 should be documented to enable reproducibility.

1892 **6.6.1 List of available standards**

1893 No standards are currently available for bioprinting.

1894 **6.6.2 Areas requiring standardisation**

1895 As this field is very much in development, opportunities for standardisation are limited. It might
1896 make sense to take the first step towards standardisation by: writing guidelines, formulating
1897 quality standards, and generating techniques to compare systems/methods of bioprinting.

1898 — **Standardisation Requirements for printers:**

1899 — Dimensional Reproducibility

1900 — Resolution

1901 — Multimaterial printing (creating architectural compartments, with different
1902 cell and biomaterial types placed in discrete locations relative to each other)

1903 — Compatibility to substrates (dimensional)

1904 — **Requirements for bioink:**

1905 — Materials available

1906 — Crosslinking methods

1907 — Compatibility to substrates (biophysical)

1908 — Translucency

1909 — Viscosity

1910 — Protocols / biological CAD

1911 **6.7 Recommendations**

1912 The following list of engineering topics with potential for standardisation was created based on:
1913 the research/discussions used to generate in the previous sections, extensive discussions with
1914 external experts, and the list of hardware items benefitting from standardisation as presented in
1915 in section 6.5.6. The list is presented in order of priority, where priority was determined by a
1916 survey of 170 OoC experts. Sub points (a, b, c, etc...) were generated by discussion among the
1917 focus group members when reflecting on the survey results. The following list is therefore
1918 complementary to the rest of this section on engineering, but also has some overlapping
1919 information.

- 1920
- 1921 1. Describing rules for sterilization quality guidelines.
 - 1922 a. What sterilization techniques are currently being used by the OoC community?
 - 1923 b. What standards exist for sterility or sterilization techniques in other fields (e.g.
1924 cell biology, medicine, food production)
 - 1925 c. What are the criteria by which sterilization is tested?
 - 1926 2. Making clear definitions of OoC applications.
 - 1927 a. List of OoC applications
 - 1928 3. Standards that would help to integrate microfluidics based OoC with the standard
1929 microplate workflow.
 - 1930 a. Describe standard microplate workflows.
 - 1931 b. How does microfluidics fit in these workflows.
 - 1932 4. Defining what material properties are relevant for OoC and should be reported by the
1933 suppliers of materials and components.
 - 1934 a. What are the relevant material properties?
 - 1935 b. How are these properties characterised / measured? Including batch – batch
1936 reproducibility.
 - 1937 c. Are these measurements covered by ISO standards?
 - 1938 5. Standards for modular integration of a microfluidic system, including making
1939 microfluidic connections.
 - 1940 a. Bring interested suppliers together to reach consensus.
 - 1941 b. Define operational conditions for such system / requirements.
 - 1942 c. Define connection methodology that fits best to the requirements.
 - 1943 6. Setting standards for connection of sensors and actuators to instrumentation.
1944 See point 5 a, b, and c.
 - 1945 7. Making guidelines for the measurement of flows and fluids, leakages etc.
1946 This topic is covered by the MFMET project, results will be published soon. See
1947 www.mfmet.eu
 - 1948 8. Standards that would help to integrate microfluidic based OoC devices in incubators.
 - 1949 a. Define classes of environmental conditions based on temperature, humidity, gas
1950 composition and time to operate inside the incubator. Can they be linked to
1951 certain applications?
 - 1952 b. Are existing methods for testing and reporting durability with respect to
1953 humidity and temperature sufficient? Or are new standards needed?
 - 1954 9. Setting clear requirements for OoC sensors (dead volume, flow rates, etc.) and a standard
1955 interface to enable easy and reliable integration of sensors in OoC systems, either tube
1956 based or tube-less integration. See point 5 a, b, and c.
 - 1957 10. Creating a set of symbols for the hardware elements used, to visualize a OoC system /
1958 experiment setup.

- 1959 a. What symbols from existing standards can be used in OoC?
1960 b. What other symbols are currently being used by the community?
1961 c. Create a list of useful symbols.
1962 d. Give examples how such symbols can be used to visualize an experimental setup.
1963 11. Working on microplate limitations / missing standards
1964 12. Setting quality standards for bioprinting
1965 13. Development of one standard way to parameterize micro-reaction-chambers
1966 a. What are the distinguishing characteristics of micro-reaction-chambers?
1967 b. How are these characteristics measured
1968 c. Are there classes of comparable micro-reaction-chambers and can they be linked
1969 to certain applications?

1970 **7 Hardware parameters, experimental design and data management**

1971 **7.1 Introduction**

1972 OoC provide improved physiological relevance, and thus offer great potential for application in a
1973 number of areas. However, OoC models, and therefore experiments, are complex integrated
1974 systems comprised by biological and engineering components, with inherent multiple factors to
1975 consider and control, as these could potentially confound the results and/or introduce variability.
1976 It is therefore important to identify, account for, and control these factors to ensure the
1977 conclusions drawn from OoC experiments are robust and reproducible (Cairns et al., 2023). Such
1978 factors can include fit-for-purpose hardware aspects, including flow rate and mechanical stimuli,
1979 as well as experimental aspects such as cell source and analytical techniques, but also
1980 experimental design features such as control groups and power. Furthermore, all the data
1981 generated from OoC experiments, both biological and technical data, must be carefully
1982 documented and evaluated for accurate interpretation, (computational) analysis, and
1983 reproducibility. This includes documenting details of the hardware and data collection methods
1984 in addition to the more commonly recorded parameters from *in vitro* studies such as cell number
1985 or cell viability. As such, the aim of this WG is to identify the need for standards for these three
1986 broad aspects of biological experiments using OoC: **hardware parameters, experimental
1987 design, and data management**. Adopting standards in these areas will ensure the generation of
1988 robust and reproducible data. Specifically, they will:

- 1989 — Ensure the production of reproducible experimental data across laboratories and
1990 operators
1991 — Enable wider adoption of MPS/OoC technology
1992 — Help demonstrate the improved predictivity of these models over current ‘gold
1993 standards’/state-of-the-art, such as animal models or other simpler cell-based *in
1994 vitro* assays.

1995 **7.2 Hardware parameters that directly impact experimental data**

1996 While the manufacture of OoC-associated hardware, and the required standards for this, are
1997 documented in Section 5, this chapter refers specifically to the requirement for standards for
1998 measuring and documenting parameters controlled by hardware that have a direct impact on the
1999 experimental results. These could be from OoC-specific hardware, or other hardware important
2000 for the OoC experiment, such as incubators. Standards for recording such parameters before,
2001 during and/or after an OoC experiment, to demonstrate the hardware processes are as specified
2002 are necessary to ensure reliability and robustness. For example, where a specific flow rate is

2003 required for an OoC experiment, a standard procedure for measuring and recording the actual
 2004 output is important; any discrepancy in the flow rate could have an impact on the experimental
 2005 results, and thereby the conclusions drawn, ultimately impacting the robustness and
 2006 reproducibility of the data if such discrepancies are not accounted for.

2007 **7.2.1 List of available standards**

2008 There are some existing standards of relevance to this section (Guidance Document on Good In
 2009 Vitro Method Practices (GIVIMP)(OECD, 2018);ISO 13485:2016 Medical devices - Quality
 2010 management systems - Requirements for regulatory purposes), which may be able to be applied,
 2011 in part, or be used to guide OoC-specific standards.

2012 **7.2.2 Areas requiring standardisation**

2013 Below is a list of aspects of **Hardware Setup Processes** that would benefit from standardisation.

2014 — **Incubator Conditions (Temperature, humidity, CO₂/other gas levels)**

2015 It is important that conditions inside an incubator are carefully controlled to ensure optimum cell
 2016 growth and viability. It is important that the temperature, CO₂ and humidity level the incubator is
 2017 set to, and the actual values are the same. To verify this, the temperature, CO₂ and humidity levels
 2018 of the incubator should be recorded independently, and the values recorded at defined points
 2019 throughout the experiment using calibrated instruments. The type of instrument and calibration
 2020 standards, as well as a SOP for the frequency and number of replicates of readings to be recorded,
 2021 are required. National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) and/or ISO guidelines for the
 2022 type of instrument and calibration procedure may exist, but an SOP for recording incubator
 2023 temperature, CO₂ and humidity during an OoC experiment needs to be defined. Furthermore, an
 2024 acceptable range needs to be defined, which may be cell type and/or OoC-specific.

2025 — **OoC Hardware**

2026 Pressure can be applied to certain OoC devices to mimic stretching e.g. breathing motion of a lung.
 2027 Gas and liquid flow to the cells in an OoC device can also be controlled. Flow can also be applied
 2028 to induce shear stress. As such, these parameters may not be present in all OoC experiments, but
 2029 where they are, they should be independently verified to ensure the output matches the setting
 2030 on the hardware.

2031 Flow sensors (gas or liquid) are available, possibly with associated standards for operation and/or
 2032 calibration, as discussed in section 6.3.4, but SOPs for using these in an OoC experiment, including
 2033 the frequency and number of replicates of readings to be recorded, are required.

2034 Oxygen saturation is an important parameter typically driven from the incubator. In complex OoC
 2035 systems, oxygen saturation requirements may vary throughout the different components. SOPs
 2036 are required how the oxygen saturation levels are controlled and monitored in OoC systems.

2037 SOPs are also required for the following aspects that influence experimental results, such as leak-
 2038 tightness of tubing and other characteristic quality management.

2039 Some OoC devices incorporate mechanical stimuli, to improve the physiological relevance; the
 2040 different types of mechanical stimuli applied to OOC systems include shear flow, compression, and
 2041 stretch/strain. These are reviewed in (Kaarj & Yoon, 2019). SOPs to record the level of mechanical
 2042 stimulus the cells are subjected to are required.

2043

Area that needs standardisation	What is missing/needed
Incubator	

Temperature	NIST and/or ISO guidelines for the type of thermometer and calibration procedure may exist, but an SOP for recording incubator temperature during an experiment needs to be defined.
CO ₂ /other gas levels	NIST and/or ISO guidelines for the type of gas analyser and calibration procedure may exist, but an SOP for recording incubator CO ₂ or other gas levels during an experiment needs to be defined.
Humidity	NIST and/or ISO guidelines for the type of hygrometer and calibration procedure may exist, but an SOP for recording incubator humidity levels during an experiment needs to be defined.
OoC hardware	
Pressure	SOP for controlling and monitoring pressure in OoCs
Flow rate	SOP for controlling and recording of flow rates needs to be defined.
Mechanical stimuli	SOP for controlling and recording of mechanical stimuli, such as pressure or shear stress, needs to be defined.
Leak-tightness of tubing	SOP for verifying of leak-tightness of tubing and connections needs to be defined.
O ₂ saturation	SOP for controlling and recording of oxygen saturation needs to be defined.

2044 7.3 Experimental Design

2045 Experimental design refers to how to set up an experiment, including technical, operational and
2046 biological aspects.

2047 Experimental design is a critical component of conducting biological experiments as it ensures
2048 that the results obtained are accurate, precise, and reproducible (intra-/inter-laboratory). State-
2049 of-the-art experimental designs for biological experiments typically involve careful consideration
2050 of sample size, statistical power, and control groups (biological controls), as well as selection of
2051 appropriate biological materials and measurements. For instance, when designing experiments
2052 using cell-based in vitro assays, factors such as cell source, culture conditions, and passage
2053 number must be carefully monitored and documented to minimize experimental variability.
2054 Similarly, the selection of appropriate analytical techniques, such as transcriptomics or
2055 proteomics, can be critical for obtaining accurate and meaningful results. There are challenges in
2056 achieving optimal experimental design, including variability, instability and bias in biological
2057 systems, lack of standardized protocols, and ethical considerations when working with living
2058 organisms. The ARRIVE guidelines are a resource for best practice in designing and reporting
2059 animal studies (<https://arriveguidelines.org/arrive-guidelines>)(Percie du Sert et al., 2020).
2060 Regarding in vitro studies, the OECD published a Guidance Document on Good in vitro method
2061 practices (GIVIMP; [https://www.oecd.org/env/guidance-document-on-good-in-vitro-
2062 method-practices-givimp-9789264304796-en.htm](https://www.oecd.org/env/guidance-document-on-good-in-vitro-method-practices-givimp-9789264304796-en.htm))(OECD, 2018) and recently a set of
2063 recommendations has been published for what to include when publishing in vitro studies
2064 (RIVER; <https://osf.io/preprints/metaarxiv/x6aut/>)(The RIVER working group, 2023).
2065 However, these are for in vitro studies generally, and do not refer specifically to OoC. Regarding
2066 OoC studies, two publications refer to experimental design, specifically for the experimental set

2067 up (Cairns et al., 2023) or automated imaging of OoC (Peel et al., 2019), and another recent
2068 publication presents a technical framework for enabling high quality measurements in New
2069 Approach Methodologies (NAMs), of which OoC are one type (Petersen et al., 2023). However,
2070 broad guidelines and/or standards for experimental design of OoC studies are not yet available.
2071 Therefore, the aim of this section is to identify and define standards for the experimental design
2072 and execution of biological OoC experiments. Overall, the establishment of standardized protocols
2073 for experimental design and execution would enhance the reliability and translatability of OoC
2074 experiments, thereby enhancing confidence in, and adoption of, these models.

2075 The identification and definition of standards for experimental design and execution of biological
2076 OoC experiments can have several specific use cases and applications. For instance, these
2077 standards can be used to improve the drug discovery process by enabling accurate and
2078 reproducible assessment of drug efficacy and toxicity. Additionally, OoC models can be used for
2079 disease modelling, which can aid in the development of new therapeutics and personalized
2080 medicine. Standards for experimental design can also be applied in the field of regenerative
2081 medicine, where OoC models can be used to develop and test new tissue-engineering strategies.

2082 **7.3.1 Areas requiring standardisation**

2083 All aspects of setting up an experiment require standardisation to ensure the generation of robust
2084 and reproducible data. These have been divided into the following aspects: Biological
2085 characterisation, Compound characterisation, Study design, and the current status of
2086 standardisation of these will be discussed in the following subsections.

2087 — **Biological characterisation**

2088 — **Number of cells and/or cell viability:** To be able to reproduce and compare
2089 data the number of cells is of great importance. How cells are counted
2090 depends on type of cells, e.g. hepatocytes are binuclear and hence cannot be
2091 counted on all cell counting instruments (Friedrich & Gilbert, 2023). The
2092 viability of the cells also needs to be assessed, both before the start of an
2093 experiment and during the time course of the experiment to make sure the
2094 system is viable all through the incubations. Viability tests also depends on
2095 type of cells and type of experiment, cell viability after thawing is typically
2096 done with trypan blue exclusion test which cannot be used to test viability on
2097 formed organoids. For viability during experiment a soluble marker such as
2098 lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), which leaks out in the medium could be used,
2099 whereas at the end of an experiment disruptive measures such as ATP
2100 concentration could be of greater value. Viability marker is also dependant on
2101 the type of OoC which is used, e.g. if it is a flow-through or a recirculating
2102 system. It is important that SOPs are defined, and where standard procedures
2103 already exist for cell counting and viability measures exist, that these are
2104 followed, however it is important that the approach taken is chip, organ and
2105 CoU-dependent; how to count and measure viability of cells in OoC should not
2106 be standardised.

2107 **Recommendation:** Develop a list of available methods and
2108 recommendations in which settings they are applicable.

2109 — **Baseline characteristics of cells or organoids in OoC, cell specific**
2110 **functionality:** As in any in vitro experiment the details about cells or cell
2111 lines, such as identity, source, pre-characterisation etc, need to be clearly
2112 stated. This is well described in the RIVER recommendations but what would
2113 be useful is a more detailed description of how to characterise functionality
2114 of the cells/organoids and how well they represent the native cell or tissue.

2115 Such characterisation could consist of molecular readouts (e.g. gene
 2116 expression patterns) but where possible functional characterisation is also
 2117 aspirational. Cell specific functionality could be e.g. albumin secretion from
 2118 hepatocytes, TEER values on barrier forming cells, or beat rate on cardiac
 2119 organoids. Cell-specific functionality is needed to demonstrate that cells
 2120 under the control settings react as expected (Baudy et al, 2020, Lab-on-Chip).
 2121 Time points for such measurements are dependent on type of experiment, if
 2122 it is a short- or long-term experiment, but also depends on the type of
 2123 measurement (eg if it is disruptive, if it is secreted into the medium). As such,
 2124 SOPs for recording the baseline characteristics of the cells/organoids in the
 2125 OoC should be established, and where standard procedures are in place for
 2126 particular methods, these should be followed, however it is important that
 2127 the approach taken is chip, organ and CoU-dependent; what baseline
 2128 characteristics to record, and how should not be standardised.

2129 **Recommendation:** develop a list of available methods for the most common
 2130 cell types and recommendations in which settings they are applicable

2131 — **Compound characterisation**

2132 There are a number of aspects relating to compound characterisation that should be recorded to
 2133 ensure data can be interpreted and analysed effectively: compound identity and purity, fractions
 2134 of unbound compounds in media and non-specific binding to chip surface, stability in media over
 2135 time, method of sample collection, material of collection tube and storage conditions to ensure
 2136 minimal loss of compound/analyte.

2137 An SOP for recording the compound characterisation should be established, and where standard
 2138 procedures are in place for particular methods, these should be followed, however it is important
 2139 that the approach taken is chip, organ and CoU-dependent; how to record these aspects should
 2140 not be standardised.

2141 **Recommendation:** develop an SOP for the recording of aspects of compound characterisation
 2142 listed above

2143 — **Study Design**

2144 Below is a list of aspects of experimental design that would benefit from standardisation.

2145 — **Appropriate positive and negative controls for each arm:** A well-designed
 2146 experiment should include positive and negative controls (where possible)
 2147 and the inclusion of reference item(s), which benchmark the response of the
 2148 test system to the test (OECD GIVIMP), as appropriate. Considerations of what
 2149 to include and report are well defined for in vivo (ARRIVE guidelines) and in
 2150 vitro studies including NAMs (OECD, 2018; Petersen et al., 2023; The RIVER
 2151 working group, 2023). For OoC studies, there are some publications that
 2152 include guidelines on drugs/compounds to test for (i) specific applications
 2153 (PK, PD, Tox, Safety, Efficacy) used e.g. in ADME-related applications (Fowler
 2154 et al., 2020) or (ii) per specific organ (e.g. (Baudy et al., 2020). However, these
 2155 are not available for all organs or applications, and developing a list of
 2156 standard test compounds for organ- or application-specific effects would
 2157 ensure consistency in the evaluation of organ models and new compounds,
 2158 thereby increasing confidence in OoC.

2159 **Recommendation:** develop a standard list of positive and negative controls
 2160 for specific organs and applications

2161 — **Sample size (number of experimental units):** Sample size relates to the
2162 number of experimental units in each group. Both the ARRIVE and RIVER
2163 guidelines outline clearly how to define experimental and biological units,
2164 and how these should be decided on and reported. While not directly for OoC
2165 studies, these guidelines are applicable to such studies. To ensure correct
2166 inclusion and reporting, it would be useful to have examples of the
2167 appropriate experimental unit allocation for different MPS. Publications by
2168 (Cairns et al., 2023; Peel et al., 2019) define the experimental unit in their
2169 specific OoC studies, which could be used for guidance, but more are needed.
2170 Moreover, it would also be useful to have guidance on how to account for the
2171 possibility of a low n for some MPS owing to the complexity leading to a small
2172 maximum n in any one study. Power analysis demonstrating the study is
2173 appropriately powered for the given number of samples/experimental units
2174 will be important to include.

2175 **Recommendation:** develop OoC-specific guidance on allocation of n/EU in
2176 OoC studies, including how to ensure robust experimental design when the
2177 maximum n is low.

2178 — **Operators:** OoC studies typically require multiple operators owing to the
2179 technical complexity of the systems limiting the number of chips that can be
2180 reliably handled by one operator at any given time. Consequently, multiple
2181 operators will be required to handle the chips for a given time point, and
2182 different operators may be required over the course of a study due to
2183 practical/staffing limitations. This can introduce variability and/or bias into
2184 the experiment and therefore needs to be carefully controlled and
2185 standardised within an OoC study to ensure robust and reproducible data.
2186 Randomisation of the operators to conditions/chips needs to be carefully
2187 considered and included in the standard guidance on randomisation (see
2188 ‘Randomisation’ section); for example, if two operators are performing the
2189 experiment, control and treated chips should be distributed between the
2190 operators so as not to confound treatment effects with operator effects.

2191 **Recommendation:** develop standard guidance on considerations regarding
2192 the need for multiple operators in a study to ensure the study is robust.
2193 Moreover, randomisation of the operators to conditions/chips and across
2194 timepoints needs to be considered and included in the standard guidance on
2195 randomisation (see ‘Randomisation’ section). It is not appropriate to
2196 standardise the number of operators, since this will vary depending on a
2197 number of factors such as the chip system being used and the size of the study.

2198 — **Randomisation:** Randomisation is a strategy to minimise potential
2199 confounders through appropriate distribution of experimental variables. The
2200 process for randomisation is well defined (ARRIVE, RIVER) but limited
2201 applications of this to OoC studies have been reported (Cairns et al., 2023,
2202 Peel et al., 2019). OoC studies tend to have more potential confounders than
2203 standard in vitro studies, such as multiple operators (OoC studies typically
2204 have multiple operators – see ‘Operators’ section), pump control units, and
2205 multiple chips. As such, standard guidance on how to apply randomisation to
2206 OoC studies with differing and often multiple technical variables is needed to
2207 protect against technical effects.

2208 **Recommendation:** develop OoC-specific standard for randomisation across
 2209 different OoC platforms accounting for multiple types of technical and
 2210 biological variable

2211 — **Sampling time points:** The ARRIVE guidelines document that it is important
 2212 to describe what was measured, particularly when this can be done in
 2213 different ways. This will be especially important for OoC studies, which will
 2214 have different methods for accessing and sampling cells/media. Moreover,
 2215 depending on the size of the OoC study, samples may need to be collected by
 2216 multiple operators within a single study, thus randomisation of operator to
 2217 samples/sample time points will be important and should be considered as
 2218 part of the standards on randomisation outlined above. Other things
 2219 important to consider would be the sample collection process (including
 2220 details such as mixing, temperature, maximum time for collection, labelling
 2221 procedure), minimal sample volume necessary for valid results, the
 2222 timeframe for analysis and thereby storage, including tube material (to
 2223 minimise compound/analyte binding). Regarding the test method for
 2224 downstream sample analysis, the Technical Framework Publication
 2225 (Petersen et al, 2023) calls out the need to incorporate one-time preliminary
 2226 control experiments, periodic control measurements (e.g. daily, weekly, or
 2227 monthly), and in-process control measurements (performed each time an
 2228 assay is performed) into a method. This would be important for OoC studies,
 2229 particularly when sampling is repeated over multiple timepoints. In this
 2230 context, part of the guidance should consider whether samples should all be
 2231 processed together at the end, or separately at each time point.

2232 **Recommendation:** clear standard guidance/SOP on sampling from OoC
 2233 studies, accounting for different types of chip, multiple operators and often
 2234 small sample volumes. In particular, the process for collecting the sample,
 2235 including tube storage material and storage conditions/times should be
 2236 included.

2237 **7.3.2 Conclusion**

2238 The below table summarises the areas requiring standardisation (Table 3).

Area that needs standardisation	What is missing/needed
Positive and negative controls	A standard list of positive and negative controls for specific organs and applications
Sample size (experimental units)	Develop OoC-specific guidance on allocation of n/EU in OoC studies, including how to ensure robust experimental design when the maximum n is low
Operators	Where there are multiple operators, guidance on randomisation of the operators to conditions/chips and across timepoints needs to be considered and included in the standard guidance on randomisation (see ‘Randomisation’ section)
Randomisation	Randomisation across different OoC platforms accounting for multiple types of technical and biological variable

Sampling time points	Accounting for different types of chip, multiple operators and often small sample volumes. In particular, the process for collecting the sample, including tube storage material and storage conditions/times should be included
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2239 **Table 3: Areas that need standardisation**

2240 **7.4 Data Management**

2241 This topic applies to activities relating to data from OoC experiments including the day-to-day
 2242 activities and final results. Biological data produced by OoC devices, including prolonged data
 2243 collection, as well as technical data must be carefully documented and evaluated for accurate
 2244 interpretation and reproducibility. This requires data management and complex analyses (e.g.
 2245 computational modelling) covering aspects such as:

2246 **Experimental protocol:** describing materials, e.g. pump and other hardware specifications,
 2247 brand name of incubators, and **compound aspects** such as supplier, product and lot number,
 2248 information on solubility, stability, binding specificity, lipophilicity, unbound fraction and non-
 2249 specific binding to platform, time-concentration profiles either intracellular or extracellular in
 2250 media and **other aspects** such as number of operators and details on chip/sample collection (e.g.
 2251 date and time) and details on methods following a structured, transparent, accessible reporting
 2252 strategy such as “STAR methods”, applied by journals in the Cell Press family.

2253 **Technical/operational aspects:** describing activities related to acquisition, organization and
 2254 storage of raw data as well as analysis and reporting/disseminating results, providing templates
 2255 for specific applications or organ-chips including formats of documents (e.g. doc(x), xls(x), ppt,
 2256 pdf or any future formats).

2257 Although standardisation on the data acquisition is of great interest, the results obtained are
 2258 usually generated with equipment that are meant for biological purposes as overall and not
 2259 specific for the OoCs. However, standardisation allows that the large amount of produced data can
 2260 be integrated and reused by the scientific community either after publication or when exchanged
 2261 with partners. The FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability)
 2262 provide a guide for scientific data management and stewardship. Concretely, this means using
 2263 rich, highly structured, and interlinked metadata, stored in indexed and accessible repositories;
 2264 data should be open to everybody who has the right to access, complying with GDPR and
 2265 respecting IP rights and confidentiality of the data where needed. To ensure the interoperability
 2266 of the data, the corresponding metadata should have multiple attributes, following relevant
 2267 minimal information guidelines, to describe the content of the datasets and the context in which
 2268 they were recorded, including the biological source material. The storage of data could be
 2269 performed using a Laboratory Information Management System (LIMS). These systems consist of
 2270 a software that allows you to effectively manage samples and associated data. This method is
 2271 widely adopted in pharma and in GMP and GLP processes and should be adopted when
 2272 performing OoC studies.

2273 **Computational Modelling of OoC Data:** The computational modelling of data obtained from
 2274 Organ-on-a-Chip experiments currently lacks standardized approaches, which is a critical gap in
 2275 the field. This absence of standards affects the development, reporting, and reproducibility of
 2276 computational models used to interpret OoC data and the potential translation to in-human
 2277 situations.

2278 There is a need for guidelines on developing computational models for OoC data. This includes
 2279 methods for integrating biological data with physical and chemical parameters, considering the
 2280 unique microenvironment of each organ chip. A standard approach would facilitate the
 2281 comparison of results across different studies and enhance the predictive power of these models.

2282 Clear guidelines are essential for reporting outcomes of computational models, such as estimated
2283 parameters and graphical visualizations. Standards should dictate the level of detail required to
2284 ensure transparency and enable other researchers to validate and build upon published findings.

2285 The reproducibility of computational models is currently hindered by a lack of standardized
2286 coding practices and validation procedures. There is a pressing need for guidelines that cover
2287 good coding practices, model verification, and validation processes. This would ensure that
2288 models are not only reproducible but also qualified for specific applications in OoC research.

2289 The selection of software and tools for data analysis (e.g. open-source like R) should adhere to
2290 best practices in software engineering and data science. Guidelines should recommend open-
2291 source tools where possible, to facilitate sharing and collaboration within the scientific
2292 community.

2293 Encouraging collaborative frameworks that bring together biologists, engineers, and data
2294 scientists can foster the development of robust, standardized computational models. Such
2295 collaborations can lead to the establishment of shared repositories of models and data, further
2296 advancing the field.

2297 Incorporating a standardized approach to computational modelling in OoC experiments is crucial.
2298 It will not only enhance the reliability and comparability of the results but also significantly
2299 contribute to the advancement of OoC technologies and their applications in drug development
2300 and disease modelling.

2301 **7.4.1 List of available standards**

2302 — STAR methods (Marcus, 2016)

2303 — FAIR guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship
2304 (Wilkinson et al., 2016)

2305 — MIQE guidelines, scope is very narrow but could be a good starting point for
2306 reporting guidelines (Bustin et al., 2009)

2307 — PRO-MaP (Leite et al., 2023)

2308 — RIVER (Reporting In Vitro Experiments Responsibly) (The RIVER working group,
2309 2023)

2310 — ISO 20691:2022, Requirements for data formatting and description in the life
2311 sciences

2312 — ISO 27001:2022 Annex A Control 8.28, This specific control in ISO 27001
2313 emphasizes the development and implementation of secure coding processes. It
2314 includes considerations for secure coding principles during new coding projects,
2315 software reuse operations, and the use of development tools. Security testing is
2316 recommended during and after development, and there is a focus on ensuring
2317 security in the production environment.

2318 — ISO/IEC 15408 (all parts): For more information on IT security evaluation,
2319 organizations are recommended to refer to ISO/IEC 15408.

2320 This collection of recommendations and standards are not specific for OoCs but contain general
2321 principles that are also applicable for OoCs. A critical analysis of these principles is required to
2322 come to standardised data management and reporting for OoCs.

2323 **7.4.2 Areas requiring standardisation**

- 2324 — Standards that define the use of software and programming languages, e.g. open-
2325 source like R, Python
- 2326 — Documentation verifying the use of FAIR
- 2327 — Guidelines for using statistical software tools and tests as well as data analyses
- 2328 — Reporting practices – a description of what should be included

2329 **7.4.3 Recommendations**

2330 It was found that the currently existing guidelines and standards for data management and
2331 reporting in life science experiments serve as a good starting point for OoC applications, but for
2332 specific aspects of OoC experiments standardisation is required. The table below summarizes the
2333 identified areas that require standardisation (Table 4).

Area that needs standardisation	Identified Guidelines/Standards	What is missing/needed
Experimental Protocol		The followed protocol should be completely described such that it can be reproduced.
Not applicable	PRO-MaP	The guideline “Promoting Reusable and Open Methods and Protocols”(Leite et al., 2023), proposes to stimulate the sharing of methods and protocols, that can be re-used by other scientists.
Compound- and Other Aspects		Reporting of compound- and other aspects to improve traceability and comparison of experimental results.
Not applicable	STAR	The Structured, Transparent, Accessible Reporting strategy (Marcus, 2016) gives guidelines how to publish these aspects. For internal administration, additional standardisation may be required.
Data Acquisition, Organisation and Storage		A standardised method to acquire and store data is crucial for subsequent data analysis and publication of results.
Not applicable	ISO 20691:2022	Requirements for data formatting and description in the life sciences is
Use of statistical methods and -tools		Standardisation in the use of statistical methods and -tools needs further effort.
Data analysis via computational modelling		
Not applicable	ISO 27001:2022, ISO 27002:2022, ISO/IEC 27005:2022	Currently, no specific standards or guidelines exist for the computational modelling of OoC data. There is a need for development of such standards, including guidelines on reporting modelling outcomes and ensuring

		reproducibility and qualification. ISO standards like ISO 27001:2022, ISO 27002:2022, and ISO/IEC 27005:2022, though not specific to OoC, provide a foundation in good coding practices and information security management which could be adapted for OoC computational modelling.
Reporting and Dissemination of Results		
Not applicable	FAIR principles	Data sharing principles, a general principle that also applies for OoC, it is not specific.
Not applicable	MIQE guidelines	Minimum Information for Publication of Quantitative Real-Time PCR Experiments, narrow scope but a good starting point. (Bustin et al., 2009)
Not applicable	RIVER	The general recommendations for Reporting In Vitro Experiments Responsibly should be considered and further evaluated for applicability in OoC experiments. (The RIVER working group, 2023)

2334 **Table 4: Areas that need standardisation**2335 **7.5 Conclusion**

2336 **Hardware setup, experimental design and data management** are essential to produce
 2337 reliable, robust results from a biological system. Within the OoC area an additional layer of the
 2338 design of the hardware is added and with a clear standard for the design of an OoC experiment
 2339 the threshold for adapting these systems could be decreased.

2340 So far, no unified way of reporting biological or hardware data from OoC is present. This comprises
 2341 the data format and the type of data, e.g. biomarker levels on-chip or kinetics of investigated
 2342 compounds or biomarkers. Additionally, no information on the used hardware is systematically
 2343 stored and reported. This hinders technological adaptation in a wider community. Another aspect
 2344 that hampers the wider use of OoC experiments, especially in the industry, is lack of comparability
 2345 of data from different systems.

2346 Standardisation in life sciences has many benefits, including enabling comparable research,
 2347 complying with legislation, increasing patient safety, fostering innovation, and showing best
 2348 practices. However, the adoption of OoC technology in the industry has been slow due to a lack of
 2349 qualified assays with scientifically proven robustness, unclear applicability domains, and poor
 2350 experience with the technology. To ensure that OoC models are fit for purpose, the qualification
 2351 must include external aspects such as the availability of laboratory infrastructure, well-
 2352 documented SOPs, and strong technical support, in addition to the characterization of the model
 2353 and assay. Design specifications for OoC models must be based on the intended use or purpose.
 2354 For example, the design specifications of a Lung-on-a-Chip model to study pulmonary oedema will
 2355 be different from a Liver-on-a-Chip model aiming to predict drug-induced liver injury.

2356 Presenting a framework on data reporting from OoC biological experiments would enable
 2357 comparing on-chip performance across labs and operators, which would identify the best-in-class
 2358 chip for a specific application. It further provides a guideline on how to setup a biological

2359 experiment. Stored data from biological experiments and hardware in a unified database in
2360 combination with newly available machine learning and artificial intelligence algorithms may
2361 unlock unforeseen potential of these chips to impact the drug development process.

2362 An important extension of this concept is the development of digital twins through computational
2363 modelling. Digital twins, essentially detailed and dynamic computational representations of the
2364 physical OoC models and the emulated biology, can significantly enhance the understanding and
2365 predictive power of these systems. However, the creation and use of digital twins in the OoC field
2366 face challenges due to the lack of standardized computational modelling approaches and
2367 guidelines. As such, there is a pressing need for establishing standards in this area, including the
2368 development of guidelines for reporting modelling outcomes, ensuring reproducibility and
2369 qualification of these models. Incorporating good coding practices and adhering to relevant ISO
2370 standards like ISO 27001:2022, ISO 27002:2022, and ISO/IEC 27005 could provide a foundational
2371 framework for developing these computational models. The integration of computational
2372 modelling, particularly digital twins, into this framework, is a critical step toward achieving these
2373 goals and unlocking the full potential of OoC technology.

2374 With standards being applied, this lack of comparability could be overcome since the adoption of
2375 standards will ensure that all information is captured from all experimental aspects (biology,
2376 hardware, data, etc), else, the information about the experiment will capture only what the
2377 experimenter considers important. Following standardized guidelines will ensure that data from
2378 OoC can be reproduced and compared across labs and operators, leading to the substantial
2379 increase and build-up of relevant data in different areas (e.g. disease modelling, PK/PD modelling
2380 etc.). The increase in availability and understanding of the data from OoC experiments and the
2381 interpretation thereof would be a major advantage in presenting the data to e.g. regulatory
2382 agencies. Most importantly, a better understanding of OoC systems would be gained, enabling
2383 clinical applications and promoting the widespread use of OoC models.

2384 Standardizing experimental design in the OoC area is essential for reliable and comparable results.
2385 The lack of comparability of data from different systems is a major challenge in the wider use of
2386 OoC experiments, especially in the industry. The application of a clear standard for experimental
2387 design can help overcome this challenge and ensure that all relevant data are captured. This will
2388 enable data from these models to be reproduced and compared across labs and operators, leading
2389 to increased understanding and implications for the clinical setting. Furthermore, the integration
2390 of computational models, particularly digital twins, into this standardisation process is crucial.
2391 These models can significantly enhance the predictive accuracy and utility of OoC systems, making
2392 them more valuable for research and clinical applications. The development and standardisation
2393 of computational modelling approaches will be a key factor in realizing the full potential of OoC
2394 technology.

2395 **8 User perspective and regulatory, legal and ethical aspects**

2396 **8.1 Introduction**

2397 This chapter provides background information on the most relevant scientific applications of OoC
2398 technology, discussing potential implications within existing regulatory, legal and ethical aspects.

2399 In section 8.2, the use of OoC devices as tools to enable precision medicine is described. OoC can
2400 be used in internal decision-making to predict drug responses in specific organs, but also to screen
2401 candidate molecules for efficacy. Interestingly, OoC are also used to provide data for drug
2402 repurposing, complementing information from clinical trials.

2403 Considerations on the applicability of the Medical Device Regulation (MDR), In Vitro Diagnostics
2404 Regulations (IVDR) and Advanced Therapy Medicinal Products (ATMP) to OoC devices were made
2405 in section 8.3.

2406 Section 8.4 discusses the use of OoC as non-animal tools for regulatory use across different
2407 sectors. The paragraph includes some considerations on the scientific assessment that is
2408 necessary to comply with current requirements for test methods.

2409 This chapter ends with ethical considerations for the use of non-animal, human-based models in
2410 the EU context, with some specific considerations on OoC.

2411 **8.2 Use of OoC for medical purposes: diagnosis, treatment, drug repurposing**

2412 **8.2.1 Prediction of patient-specific drug response**

2413 To date, OoC technology has mostly been developed as a means to improve the drug discovery
2414 and preclinical development processes, to provide experimental data for the development of
2415 improved in silico models, and to support the replacement, refinement, and reduction of animals
2416 used for scientific purposes. In addition to these relevant goals, OoC promises to become an
2417 important technology for understanding variability in patients' response to drugs and for enabling
2418 precision medicine in clinical use.

2419 OoC models are increasingly populated with induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs)-derived cells,
2420 organoids or tissue biopsies. These models carry individual variations in genetics, physiology, and
2421 other biological factors, enabling a better understanding of the patient's disease and how they
2422 might respond to potential treatments (Peck et al., 2020). An OoC from a specific patient could be
2423 used to screen a range of drugs, drug combinations, and doses to identify which has the potential
2424 to be most effective in that patient. For example, a glioblastoma-on-chip model using patient-
2425 derived cells was shown to be predictive of patient-specific resistances for chemoradiation with
2426 temozolomide and could be used to determine drug combinations associated with more effective
2427 tumour killing (Yi et al., 2019). When multiple chips are seeded with cells from different donors
2428 representing different subpopulations or patients with a different comorbidity, OoC models might
2429 also be used to design and optimize drugs for specific subgroups, allowing patient stratification
2430 for targeted clinical trials (Ingber, 2022).

2431 Use of OoC technology for decision-making on the treatment of an individual patient would
2432 require qualification for the specific application to meet possible regulatory requirements. This
2433 brings new challenges to the field as no clear guidelines for these models to be accepted as tools
2434 for tailor-made treatment strategies currently exist. Recently the PERMIT (Personalized Medicine
2435 Trials) Group has presented 15 recommendations to improve the robustness of preclinical
2436 methods in translational research for personalized medicine (Fosse et al., 2023). These
2437 recommendations include the development of standards to characterize new models and methods
2438 in support of their qualification for prediction of the best personalized therapy for each individual
2439 patient. This will be an important step in establishing scientific credibility and building confidence
2440 in new technologies for preclinical personalized medicine within the regulatory science
2441 community.

2442 **8.2.2 Drug repurposing**

2443 Medicines repurposing (also known as drug repurposing, drug repositioning, drug recycling and
2444 therapeutic switching) describes the process of recognising new medical indications for a
2445 medicine with an existing marketing authorisation. The sponsor/manufacturer must seek
2446 regulatory approval to broaden the approved indications or expand the treatment population on
2447 the basis of new clinical evidence gathered, as indicated in the Regulation EC/1234/2008 and
2448 related guidelines from the European Medicines Agency (European Medicines Agency, 2024c).

2449 Although this is a very specific scenario, it represents a very practical and imminent application
2450 where OoCs could rapidly supersede conventional experimental approaches used to support
2451 medicines repurposing applications (e.g. in vivo animal studies). OoC systems have the potential

2452 to significantly improve the standard of evidence for such regulatory submissions, whilst also
2453 enhancing the safety of human clinical trials conducted to support them.

2454 Typically, this new evidence comprises in vivo proof-of-concept studies in relevant animal species,
2455 additional ad hoc clinical trials in patients and clinical evidence from off-label (i.e. use of a
2456 medicine for an unapproved indication or in an unapproved age group, dosage or route of
2457 administration) or compassionate use (Agency, 2024a)(i.e. medicinal products without a
2458 Marketing Authorisation that may be made available for compassionate reasons to a group of
2459 patients with a chronically or seriously debilitating disease or whose disease is considered to be
2460 life-threatening, and who cannot be treated satisfactorily by an authorized medicinal product).
2461 While there is an expectation that a substantial clinical-based evidence demonstrating the
2462 product's safety profile would already exist, additional non-clinical toxicology studies may be
2463 requested if the new treatment population is substantially different from the original one.

2464 OoC systems could be utilised to perform proof-of-concept studies to support the proposed new
2465 clinical application(s), allowing for clinically relevant evaluations of functional activity. OoC can
2466 also be used to further characterise the response to treatment which could lead to reduction of
2467 risks associated with human clinical studies by reducing sample size required, reducing study
2468 duration, and enhancing clinical outcome assessments.

2469 This is particularly relevant in relation to rare diseases where developers are faced with
2470 significant challenges around trial participant recruitment and retention, often leading to
2471 increased reliance on non-clinical proof-of-concept in determining the risk-benefit of the
2472 proposed treatment in such populations. Furthermore, whilst there are over 7000 rare diseases
2473 recognised by the EMA and FDA, it is estimated that less than 10% of these are actively being
2474 researched by developers due to lack of reflective animal models of disease (The Lancet Diabetes
2475 & Endocrinology, 2019). OoC will offer additional options and it is to be expected that over time
2476 drug repurposing applications for rare diseases will increasingly involve such new approaches.

2477 The EMA and FDA have openly stated (Han, 2023) that, going forward, they will strongly support
2478 utilisation of in vitro data to expand disease indications where there is a significant lack of drug
2479 development precedent. This regulatory openness to evidentiary alternatives and novel
2480 methodologies is welcome, and OoC systems are likely to figure very prominently in this area.
2481 However, adjusted regulatory guidance and standards will be required to encourage developers
2482 to widely adopt these alternative approaches.

2483 ***Real-case example** - A system composed of human induced pluripotent stem cell (iPSC)-derived*
2484 *motoneurons and human Schwann cells. Exposure to serum from MMN and CIDP patients led to*
2485 *increased autoantibody binding and activation of the classical complement cascade, a critical part*
2486 *of the immune system response. Additionally, patient-mediated serum exposure reduced conduction*
2487 *velocity and decreased action potential firing frequency in their functional model, recapitulating the*
2488 *clinical features observed in patients. The addition of TNT005, an antibody developed by Sanofi that*
2489 *inhibits the classical complement pathway, rescued neuronal function and restored spontaneous*
2490 *frequency and conduction velocity, which was supportive data used by Sanofi for their IND filing*
2491 *(Rumsey et al., 2022).*

2492 **8.3 Considerations on applicability of the Medical Device Regulation (MDR), In** 2493 **Vitro Diagnostics Regulations (IVDR) and Advanced Therapy Medicinal Products** 2494 **(ATMP) to OoC devices**

2495 **8.3.1 Medical Device Regulation (EU) 2017/745 (European Parliament and Council,** 2496 **2017)**

2497 An OoC with a direct medical purpose, would be functionally similar to a medical device (MD, see
2498 definition in Box 1). Just as in the case of MDs, the necessity of demonstrating its safety and efficacy
2499 is required before the device is used.

2500 BOX 1

The definition of ‘**medical device (MD)**’, as given by the [MDR 2017/745](#), is the following:

“Medical device’ means any instrument, apparatus, appliance, software, implant, reagent, material or other article intended by the manufacturer to be used, alone or in combination, for human beings for one or more of the following specific medical purposes:

- *diagnosis, prevention, monitoring, prediction, prognosis, treatment or alleviation of disease,*
- *diagnosis, monitoring, treatment, alleviation of, or compensation for, an injury or disability,*
- *investigation, replacement or modification of the anatomy or of a physiological or pathological process or state,*
- *providing information by means of in vitro examination of specimens derived from the human body, including organ, blood and tissue donations,*

and which does not achieve its principal intended action by pharmacological, immunological or metabolic means, in or on the human body, but which may be assisted in its function by such means.”

2501 Expressly, the MDR states in article 1(6)(1) that the MDR does not apply to "transplants, tissues
2502 or cells of human origin, or their derivatives, covered by Directive 2004/23/EC, or products
2503 containing or consisting of them; however this Regulation does apply to devices manufactured
2504 utilising derivatives of tissues or cells of human origin which are non-viable or are rendered non-
2505 viable." As OoCs require viable derivatives, the OoC is exempt from the scope of the MDR. Only in
2506 case an OoC is using its diagnostic capabilities through the “examination of specimens, including
2507 blood and tissue donations, derived from the human body”, a reference to the IVDR could be made
2508 (see section 8.3.3).

2509 **8.3.2 ATMP regulation (European Parliament and Council, 2007)**

2510 On the contrary, the regulation (EC) No 1394/2007 on Advanced Therapy Medicinal Products
2511 (ATMPs) could be applicable since it explicitly foresees the use of viable cells or tissues. Hence, an
2512 OoC partially meet the definition of either a ‘Somatic cell therapy medicinal product’ or a “Tissue
2513 engineered product’, provided that the cells (or tissues) used in the fabrication of the OoC itself
2514 are considered “engineered cells” (“engineered tissues”).

2515 More precisely, the OoC itself can be considered as a “combined ATMP”, owing to its multiple
2516 components (i.e. a physico-chemical and a biological component). Therefore, whereas the cells or
2517 tissues embedded in an OoC have been subject to substantial manipulation so that biological
2518 characteristics, physiological functions or structural properties relevant for the intended clinical
2519 use have been altered, the OoC itself should follow the ATMP regulation. The same applies
2520 whenever the OoC contains cells or tissues that are not intended to be used for the same essential
2521 function(s) in the recipient and the donor.

2522 However, this regulation only holds for products that are administered to the patients and thus
2523 are used inside the body. Thus, the ATMP regulation might apply to OoC once their scope is
2524 broadened to internal use in a patient.

The definition of **'Somatic cell therapy medicinal product'**, as given by Part IV of Annex I to [Directive 2001/83/EC](#)^z on the Community code relating to medicinal products for human use, is as follows:

'Somatic cell therapy medicinal product means a biological medicinal product which has the following characteristics:

(a) contains or consists of cells or tissues that have been subject to substantial manipulation so that biological characteristics, physiological functions or structural properties relevant for the intended clinical use have been altered, or of cells or tissues that are not intended to be used for the same essential function(s) in the recipient and the donor;

(b) is presented as having properties for, or is used in or administered to human beings with a view to treating, preventing or diagnosing a disease through the pharmacological, immunological or metabolic action of its cells or tissues.

For the purposes of point (a), the manipulations listed in Annex I to Regulation (EC) No 1394/2007, in particular, shall not be considered as substantial manipulations. For instance, "cell separation, concentration or purification" are not considered as substantial manipulations.

From Art 2(a) of the ATMP 1394/2007, the following definition applies:

'Advanced therapy medicinal product' means any of the following medicinal products for human use:

- a gene therapy medicinal product as defined in Part IV of Annex I to Directive 2001/83/EC,
- a somatic cell therapy medicinal product as defined in Part IV of Annex I to Directive 2001/83/EC,
- a tissue engineered product as defined in point (b)

From Art 2(b) of the ATMP Regulation, the following definition applies:

"Tissue engineered product" means a product that:

- contains or consists of engineered cells or tissues, and
- is presented as having properties for, or is used in or administered to human beings with a view to regenerating, repairing or replacing a human tissue."

From Art 2(c) of the ATMP Regulation, the following definition applies:

"Cells or tissues shall be considered 'engineered' if they fulfil at least one of the following conditions:

- the cells or tissues have been subject to substantial manipulation, so that biological characteristics, physiological functions or structural properties relevant for the intended regeneration, repair or replacement are achieved. The manipulations listed in Annex I, in particular, shall not be considered as substantial manipulations,
- the cells or tissues are not intended to be used for the same essential function or functions in the recipient as in the donor."

From Art 2(d) of the ATMP Regulation, the following definition applies:

"Combined advanced therapy medicinal product" means an advanced therapy medicinal product that fulfils the following conditions:

- it must incorporate, as an integral part of the product, one or more medical devices within the meaning of Article 1(2)(a) of Directive 93/42/EEC or one or more active implantable medical devices within the meaning of Article 1(2)(c) of Directive 90/385/EEC, and
- its cellular or tissue part must contain viable cells or tissues, or
- its cellular or tissue part containing non-viable cells or tissues must be liable to act upon the human body with action that can be considered as primary to that of the devices referred to."

2526

2527 **8.3.3 IVD Regulation (EU) 2017/7468**

2528 Regarding the case of OoCs with diagnostic functions, which also fall into the category of OoCs
2529 with a direct medical purpose, it can be stated that they can be functionally similar to an IVD (in
2530 vitro diagnostic) MD, according to the definition in Box 3.

2531 From this definition, the functional similarity of such a device to an OoC with diagnostic
2532 capabilities is evident, (e.g. for cases a, c, e and e). A companion diagnostic is an in vitro diagnostic
2533 test that supports the safe and effective use of a specific medicinal product, by identifying patients
2534 that are suitable or unsuitable for treatment. Also in this case, the functional similarity of such a
2535 device to an OoC with diagnostic capabilities is evident (e.g. for case a). A reference to its 'Annex
2536 VIII: Classification rules' may be useful as a guideline for risk class assignment of diagnostic
2537 devices, in view of a future regulatory framework for OoCs with diagnostic function.

2538

2539 **BOX 3**

The IVD Regulation defines (Article 2(1-2)):

(1) 'medical device' means 'medical device' as defined in point (1) of Article 2 of Regulation (EU) 2017/745;

(2) 'in vitro diagnostic medical device' means any medical device which is a reagent, reagent product, calibrator, control material, kit, instrument, apparatus, piece of equipment, software or system, whether used alone or in combination, intended by the manufacturer to be used in vitro for the examination of specimens, including blood and tissue donations, derived from the human body, solely or principally for the purpose of providing information on one or more of the following:

(a) concerning a physiological or pathological process or state;

(b) concerning congenital physical or mental impairments;

(c) concerning the predisposition to a medical condition or a disease;

(d) to determine the safety and compatibility with potential recipients;

(e) to predict treatment response or reactions;

(f) to define or monitoring therapeutic measures.

Specimen receptacles shall also be deemed to be in vitro diagnostic medical devices

The IVD Regulation also defines (Article 2(1-2)):

(7) 'companion diagnostic' means a device which is essential for the safe and effective use of a corresponding medicinal product to:

(a) identify, before and/or during treatment, patients who are most likely to benefit from the corresponding medicinal product; or

(b) identify, before and/or during treatment, patients likely to be at increased risk of serious adverse reactions as a result of treatment with the corresponding medicinal product;

2540 Regarding the applicability of the IVDR to OoC devices, it can be argued alternatively that OoC:

2541 — do not fall under the IVDR. An IVD MD, although being a particular type of MD, is
2542 still a medical device, as defined in the MDR. Hence, it cannot contain cells or
2543 tissues of human or animal origin, unless they are made non-viable, as implicitly
2544 stated in Annex VI of the IVDR, or.

2545 — do fall under the scope of the IVDR. The IVDR only requires that an IVD meets the
2546 definition of medical device, which is what the literal text of the definition of IVD
2547 requires under the IVDR (cf. art. 1(1)). Furthermore, the MDR provides that it
2548 does not apply to IVDs in article 1(6)(a) MDR.

2549 It must be noted that there is not yet any case law from the CJEU that addresses this matter. In
2550 order to dissipate any doubt about the possible applicability of the IVDR to OoCs, it is possible to
2551 ask for the opinion of the Medical Device Coordination Group (MDCG), established under Article
2552 103 of the MDR. The MDCG plays a strategic role also for IVD devices, see IVDR, Article 3. In
2553 particular, the consultation of the MDCG is necessary: (Art. 3.1) “Upon a duly substantiated
2554 request of a Member State, the Commission shall, after consulting the Medical Device Coordination
2555 Group established under Article 103 of Regulation (EU) 2017/745, by means of implementing
2556 acts, determine whether or not a specific product, or category or group of products, falls within
2557 the definitions of ‘in vitro diagnostic medical device’ or ‘accessory for an in vitro diagnostic
2558 medical device.’”

2559 **8.4 Use of OoC as alternative tools for regulatory applications**

2560 Regulatory toxicological testing is based on internationally agreed test guidelines, covering in vivo
2561 and in vitro test methods. These guidelines are internationally issued by organisations such as
2562 OECD (OECD, 2018) and ICH (International Council for Harmonisation of Technical Requirements
2563 for Pharmaceuticals for Human Use (ICH), 2024). Animal studies, whether for the development or
2564 production of new medicines, for physiological studies, for studying environmental effects or for
2565 the testing of chemicals or new food additives, must be carried out in compliance with EU
2566 legislation, which also includes compliance with the Directive 2010/63/EU on the protection of
2567 animals used for scientific purposes. The directive includes the principles of the Three Rs –
2568 Reduction, Replacement, Refinement – in the legal text. The term alternative includes those
2569 methods (assays, tests, methods, techniques, tools, strategies and approaches) that can:

- 2570 — Obtain the required information without the use of live animals.
- 2571 — Reduce the numbers of animals whilst obtaining the same level of information.
- 2572 — Refine the use of live animals to cause less pain, distress or suffering, or improve
2573 the welfare of the animals.

2574 An OoC could be considered as an alternative approach to evaluate toxicological properties for the
2575 compounds regulated in the following European regulations and directives, provided that their
2576 scientific validity is established.

Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 December 2006 concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH)
--

Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 on the classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures (CLP)
--

Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 October 2009 concerning the placing of plant protection products on the market

Regulation (EU) No 528/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2012 concerning the making available on the market and use of biocidal products

Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 November 2009 on cosmetic products

Directive 2001/83/EC of the European Parliament and of the council of 6 November 2001 on the Community code relating to medicinal products for human use

Regulation (EU) 2019/6 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2018 on veterinary medicinal products

2577

2578 The confidence in these test methods used in a regulatory context is gained through a scientific
2579 validation process, demonstrating the reliability and relevance of a particular approach, method,
2580 process or assessment for a defined purpose. Scientific validation is a prerequisite for regulatory
2581 acceptance but it is insufficient to guarantee regulatory acceptance (capability of a test method to
2582 provide answer to specific regulatory questions). Validation in multiple laboratories across
2583 regions to build a weight of evidence approach could support the efforts towards global
2584 harmonisation and regulatory acceptance.

2585 Several test methods, such as new approach methodologies utilising OoC technology, can be
2586 combined to produce a prediction model of adverse outcomes as Integrated Approaches to
2587 Testing and Assessment (IATA) to address a toxicity or biological effect of interest. Different
2588 requirements may be applicable depending on the application of the technology and complexity
2589 of the system, for example the weight and type of evidence needed to support single organ systems
2590 versus multi-organ systems.

2591 BOX 4

Some common toxicological endpoints are:

- Skin corrosion and irritation
- Serious eye damage/eye irritation
- Photo-induced toxicity
- Mutagenicity/genotoxicity
- Acute toxicity
- Skin sensitisation
- Repeated dose toxicity
- Carcinogenicity
- Reproductive and developmental toxicity
- Absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion (ADME)
- Toxicokinetics (TK)
- Cardiotoxicity
- Hepatotoxicity
- Nephrotoxicity
- Neurotoxicity

2592 It is possible to develop a battery of alternative tests, able to combine information from different
2593 test methods and integrating information from other sources. In these cases, a mechanistic based
2594 approached is recommended, for instance through the use of Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs).
2595 An AOP is an analytical construct that describes a sequential chain of causally linked events at
2596 different levels of biological organisation that lead to an adverse health or ecotoxicological effect.
2597 The AOP-wiki is a useful tool for collaborative AOP building (AOP-Wiki, 2024). Two valid
2598 examples of this approach are:

2599 — Thyroid validation study (Bartnicka J et al., 2021)

2600 — Developmental Neurotoxicity (Blum et al., 2023)

2601 Valid (but not validated by a validation body) methods can also be used to support regulatory
2602 decision making (e.g. pharmaceuticals) or as a decision-making tool (e.g. chemicals). Qualification
2603 is the term used in the medicinal domain to refer to the scientific assessment of the reliability and
2604 relevance for a specific context of use. An example of how qualified assays are evaluated can be
2605 found in Annex 2 of the ICH S5 (R3) guideline on reproductive toxicology (International Council
2606 for Harmonisation of Technical Requirements for Pharmaceuticals for Human Use (ICH), 2020),
2607 but many efforts are underway to bridge the regulatory needs and the OoC technological
2608 advancements. The EUROoCS Regulatory Advisory Board and the EC JRC created a catalogue of
2609 resources for developers and end-users to support validation and qualification of new
2610 technologies. The catalogue contains a curated list of relevant reading documents and a set of
2611 Frequently Asked Questions related to the main regulatory fields of interest (e.g. chemical, drug
2612 and food safety). Based on this list, a qualification framework and its practical implications were
2613 discussed by the stakeholder community (Piergiovanni et al., 2024).

2614 Support to OoC developers that want to pursue regulatory use is available at the European
2615 Medicines Agency (EMA), in the form of scientific advice to support the qualification of innovative
2616 methods for a specific intended use in the context of research and development into
2617 pharmaceuticals (European Medicines Agency, 2024b). Moreover, EMA Innovation Task Force
2618 offers the possibility for researchers/developers to interact with regulators at a very early stage
2619 of the innovation process, to better design qualification assessment for specific contexts of use
2620 (Agency, 2024b). A similar approach is also offered by FDA, through the IStand programme (U.S.
2621 Food & Drug Administration (FDA), 2024).

2622 Global harmonisation is key to the wider acceptance of the use of OoC for regulatory purposes, as
2623 varying requirements in different markets drive industry to develop large, risk-averse approaches
2624 to ensure global regulatory acceptance. However, there are no currently accepted global reporting
2625 standards that would support the wider application of OoC technology.

2626 **8.5 Ethical considerations for OoC use in the EU context**

2627 Standardized methods and technologies for the production of OoC will enable the development of
2628 these devices for preclinical, clinical and regulatory applications on a broad scale, allowing
2629 comparative studies between laboratories and applications across the research landscape.
2630 However, the wider adoption of these technologies will lead to a number of ethical considerations,
2631 relevant to the appropriate application domain, requiring standardized description or best
2632 practice to be defined. The breadth of ethical considerations that may arise in many areas of
2633 research is discussed in detail as part of the Horizon 2020 Programme self-assessment process
2634 (European Commission, 2024), however specific areas which may be relevant to OoC are
2635 summarised below.

2636 It should be noted that the regulations, directives and guidance in place from regulatory
2637 authorities and governing bodies provide a compliance framework for research activities.

2638 However, working in compliance does not deem a piece of research to be necessarily ethical. It is
2639 important that relevant ethical steering groups and advisory boards be in place to guide the varied
2640 ethical considerations that may emerge for the development and application of OoC technologies.

2641 **8.5.1 The use of animals and the 3Rs**

2642 OoC technology has created a promising opportunity for the replacement of animals in basic and
2643 applied research, through the provision of models that are faster, cheaper and more
2644 physiologically relevant where human tissues are used. The principles of the replacement,
2645 refinement and reduction of animals in research are embedded in the regulations that govern the
2646 use of animals in scientific procedures. Indeed, Directive 2010/63/EU specifies that wherever
2647 possible, scientifically satisfactory methods not entailing the use of live animals should be used
2648 for experimental or other scientific purposes. As the advancement in this area progresses, these
2649 technologies and their applications should be reviewed in order to identify where replacements
2650 are possible, to support the phasing out of animal procedures for research and regulatory testing
2651 (Zuang, V. et al., 2022).

2652 Where animal tissue and organs are used for the development of in vitro methods, the principles
2653 of refinement and reduction should be applied. It should be noted that, despite different attitudes
2654 and national perceptions on the use of animals in research in EU member states, it is generally
2655 desirable to replace the use of animals to protect human and animal health as soon as it is
2656 scientifically possible to do so (Directive 2010/63/EU (European Parliament and Council, 2010)).

2657 The European Union Reference Laboratory for alternatives to animal testing (EURL ECVAM) is
2658 tasked to promote the development and use of alternatives in the area of regulatory testing and
2659 biomedical research and coordinate the validation of non-animal methods, such as those that OoC
2660 technology may offer, in collaboration with the EU Network of Validation laboratories (EU-
2661 NETVAL).

2662 **8.5.2 The use of human tissues, cells and data**

2663 The integration of human tissues and cells supports the efforts to develop more physiologically
2664 relevant models for the improvement of science. The ethical principles outlined in the Declaration
2665 of Helsinki (DoH) provide the fundamental guidance for all parties involved in medical research
2666 using human subjects, tissues and associated data. The cornerstone of these principles is the
2667 absolute requirement of an Informed Consent either from the subjects or their legal
2668 representative allowing the particular intervention and the use of personal associated data, such
2669 as any information affiliated with biological material, according to the General Data Protection
2670 Regulation GDPR Regulation (European Parliament and Council, 2016). Guidance from the
2671 European Commission for the preparation of funding applications supports the identification and
2672 management of ethics issues that may arise from research and development, including the use of
2673 human cells and tissues, and is a useful framework to assess the multi-faceted ethical
2674 considerations of research. The EU Directive 2004/23/EC further sets the standards of quality
2675 and safety for the donation, procurement, testing, processing, preservation, storage and
2676 distribution of human tissues and cells. Furthermore, international, national or regional
2677 regulations or requirements also apply to specific topics. ISO 15189:2022 and other clinical
2678 standards are intended to apply first and foremost for entities handling human materials
2679 procured and used for diagnostic and treatment purposes.

2680 Specific considerations when using human tissues and cells for OoC technologies may include the
2681 agreed international Good Clinical Practice standard that applies when conducting research for
2682 clinical trials. Where human cells are genetically modified, the EC Good Practice on the assessment
2683 of GMO-related aspects (https://health.ec.europa.eu/document/download/62bc65ee-7f74-4b76-bdc3-07909ab177ee_en, 2024) should be implemented.

2685 The applications of OoC for drug delivery/development, personalized medicine and other clinical
2686 contexts lead to further ethical considerations in terms of the use, storage and labelling of human
2687 data. Following from the DoH, the *Declaration of Taipei* enacts the ethical principles and
2688 importance of protecting the dignity, autonomy, privacy and confidentiality of research subjects
2689 regarding health databases and biobanks. As a fundamental human right, data protection must be
2690 rigorously applied by the research community to meet and be compliant with the EU's 2016
2691 General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Developers are obliged to provide research subjects
2692 with what will happen to any personal data collected, and the data must be properly collected and
2693 stored. Furthermore, the reliance on computational support to manage the increasing volume,
2694 complexity and creation speed of data with minimal human intervention emphasizes the
2695 importance of the FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. These
2696 guidelines recommend how to improve the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and
2697 Reusability of digital assets, referring to both data (any digital object) and metadata (any
2698 information about digital objects), to support good data management. Using these guidelines to
2699 implement sound management of research data will ultimately support the advancement of
2700 discovery, innovation, knowledge integration and data reuse.

2701 **8.5.3 Commercial use of cells**

2702 The use of cells for commercial purposes is impacted by regulation over the use of human tissue,
2703 the regulation of pharmaceutical products or medical devices, and the influence of international
2704 legislation where a commercial product may be globally distributed. Importantly, the process of
2705 informed consent should include the potential uses of the tissue, particularly if there is a
2706 commercial objective or there is a possibility of a commercial outcome, which may impact the
2707 donation of tissues or cells. Furthermore, where donations are made as part of a medical diagnosis
2708 or treatment process, the commercial potential of the materials should in no way influence the
2709 application of good medical practice (Petrini, 2012). As both OoC and precision medicine
2710 technologies advance, a clear framework that can be used to govern the commercial use of cells
2711 would benefit both the developers and groups or individuals that donate tissue.

2712 **8.5.4 Ethical implications of specific OoC**

2713 The development of specific OoC systems may require particular ethical considerations. For
2714 example brain-on-chip or full body-on-chip systems raise questions regarding the potential
2715 development of consciousness or sentience of such models. Furthermore, as the brain is the
2716 carrier of personal identity, these models may require special status to consider the wider impact
2717 of their development and maintenance. These reflections may influence the conditions by which
2718 cells are donated and could be linked to informed consent, and the implications of broad consent
2719 (e.g. for biobanking purposes).

2720 OoCs developed for the purposes of developmental research or toxicity screening may mitigate
2721 ethical questions raised by the use of human tissues, but still raise innate ethical questions
2722 regarding the length of time, level of complexity, and level of protection that regulate such
2723 cultures. The OoC field is progressing at rapid pace and currently, without specific regulatory
2724 standards, it is important that the community determines which information is required to
2725 support informed decision-making that will ultimately protect patient autonomy (Thakar &
2726 Fenton, 2023).

2727 **8.5.5 Dual uses of OoC**

2728 Life science research is subject to the consideration of the dual-use dilemma wherein research is
2729 intended to provide a clear benefit but could be misapplied to do harm, whether through negative
2730 consequences to human health and safety, agriculture, the environment or national security (e.g.
2731 bioterrorism). The ethical implications and regulatory measures required are dependent on the
2732 identification of research that has potential to be misused (i.e. having a 'dual use' character)

2733 (Salloch, 2018). These discussions require input from the researchers, organisations, funders,
2734 regulators and governing bodies.

2735 **8.5.6 Ethical considerations – an international and community perspective**

2736 Further discussion/consideration may be warranted for international, global research. For
2737 example, the exchange of resources, biological material and data outside of the EU (and therefore
2738 outside the reach of EU laws and standards) may require further discussion or raise specific
2739 ethical issues such as the exploitation of research participants and local resources, risks to
2740 researchers and staff and research that is prohibited in the EU. Where research involves the
2741 transfer of cells and tissues to/from non-EU countries, researchers must be compliant with the
2742 provisions outlined in Directive 2004/23/EC and consider the requirements of GDPR and data
2743 transfer to non-EU countries. The European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies
2744 (EGE) works to integrate ethics at an international level and act as an independent, inter-
2745 disciplinary perspective on the ethical questions posed by scientific and technological innovation,
2746 and supports the upholding of the international ethics framework.

2747 Finally, these conversations must take place within and acknowledge the views of the broader
2748 community and public (Thakar & Fenton, 2023). The scientific community must be transparent to
2749 the public as more understanding is gained of the broader impact, benefits and risks of OoC within
2750 personalised medicine, toxicology and other applications, so that the field may continue to move
2751 forward in a meaningful, and potentially transformational, way.

2752

2753 **9 Conclusion and future outlook**

2754 This roadmap document is the results of two years of work, 10 Focus Group meetings, numerous
2755 Working Group meetings and the active participation of around 120 experts of the CEN/CENELEC
2756 Focus Group Organ-on-Chip (FGOoC).

2757 **Next steps**

2758 Having identified needs for standardisation on Organ-on-Chip above, a next question is how to
2759 organize the work such that on the one hand European interest is guarded and the work from the
2760 FGOoC is recognized and built upon. On the other hand fragmentation should be avoided, and the
2761 focus should be on Europe's position in a global market. This requires discussion and proposals
2762 at the European level, as well as global coordination with ISO, IEC, MFMET and other relevant
2763 standards-developing initiatives. The present document provides a base for such discussion,
2764 proposals and coordination.

2765 **Future outlook**

2766 The FGOoC advises the creation of a European Technical Committee Microphysiological Systems
2767 to focus European stakeholders and interest. Furthermore, it advises this TC to put forward the
2768 work program for adoption within the ISO standardisation community, in close connection with
2769 at least ISO/TC 276 Biotechnology and ISO/TC 48 WG3 Microfluidics. By choosing to standardize
2770 at the international ISO level rather than the European CEN/CENELEC level, stakeholders
2771 recognize the widespread interest in OoC standardisation across countries and the diverse
2772 initiatives already underway. This decision acknowledges the global value chain for OoC
2773 technologies and ensures that standards are developed with input from stakeholders worldwide,
2774 fostering innovation, interoperability, and safety in this rapidly advancing field.

2775 Through this international standardisation, stakeholders from various regions can collaborate to
2776 develop comprehensive standards that address the unique challenges and opportunities
2777 presented by OoC technologies. By leveraging international expertise and perspectives, these

2778 standards have the potential to drive harmonization, facilitate regulatory compliance, and
2779 accelerate the translation of OoC research into impactful applications for healthcare, drug
2780 discovery, and beyond.

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Annex A Terminology List

3077 WG1 has developed a terminology list based on a survey prior to and during the roadmap
3078 development process. Based on the results it is recommended to define the following terms in
3079 further standardisation activities.

3080 — Actuator

3081 — Biocompatibility

3082 — Biological material

3083 — Bioprinting

3084 — Contamination

3085 — Decellularized

3086 — Disease-on-Chip

3087 — Donor

3088 — Engineered cells

3089 — Hydrogel

3090 — Identity verification

3091 — Induced pluripotent stem cell (iPSC)

3092 — Informed consent

3093 — Interoperability

3094 — Leakage

3095 — Microfluidics

3096 — Microphysiological system

3097 — Micro-reaction-chambers

3098 — Multipotent stem cells

3099 — Organ-on-Chip

3100 — Passage number

3101 — Patient-derived primary cells

3102 — Pluripotent stem cell (PSC)

- 3103 — Primary cells
- 3104 — Primary culture
- 3105 — Reference compound
- 3106 — Reliability
- 3107 — Repeatability
- 3108 — Reproducibility
- 3109 — Sample
- 3110 — Scaffold
- 3111 — Stability
- 3112 — Standard operating procedure (SOP)
- 3113 — Tagging
- 3114 — Translatability
- 3115 — Validation
- 3116 — Verification
- 3117 — Viability

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Annex B Identified Available Standards

3119 This Annex lists all identified available standards.

3120 Chapter 3 Terms and Definitions

3121 — ASTM F3570 – 22 - Standard Terminology Relating to Microphysiological
3122 Systems

3123 — ISO 10991:2023, Microfluidics - Vocabulary

3124 Chapter 5 Biosciences

3125 Cell and Tissue Sources

3126 — Good In Vitro Method Practices (GIVIMP)

3127 — International Society for Stem Cell Research (ISSCR) guidelines

3128 — Guidance on Good Cell Culture Practice (GCCP)

3129 — Guidelines for the use of cell lines in biomedical research

3130 — ISO 20387:2018, Biotechnology - Biobanking - General requirements for
3131 biobanking

3132 — ISO 21709:2020, Biotechnology - Biobanking - Process and quality
3133 requirements for establishment, maintenance and characterization of
3134 mammalian cell lines

3135 — ISO 24603:2022, Biotechnology - Biobanking - Requirements for human and
3136 mouse pluripotent stem cells

3137 Biomaterials

3138 — ASTM F2739 – 19 Standard Guide for Quantifying Cell Viability and Related
3139 Attributes within Biomaterial Scaffolds

3140 — ASTM F2150-19 Standard Guide for Characterization and Testing of Biomaterial
3141 Scaffolds Used in Regenerative Medicine and Tissue-Engineered Medical
3142 Products

3143 — ASTM F2038-18 Standard Guide for Silicone Elastomers, Gels, and Foams
3144 Used in Medical Applications Part I & II Formulations and Uncured Materials

3145 — ASTM F2315-18 Standard Guide for Immobilization or Encapsulation of
3146 Living Cells or Tissue in Alginate Gels

3147 — ASTM F748-16 Standard Practice for Selecting Generic Biological Test
3148 Methods for Materials and devices

3149 — ASTM F3142-16 Standard Guide for Evaluation of in vitro Release of
3150 Biomolecules from Biomaterials Scaffolds for TEMP

3151 — ASTM F3354-19 Standard Guide for Evaluating Extracellular Matrix
3152 Decellularization Processes

3153 **Chapter 6 Engineering**

3154 — ISO 22916:2022, Microfluidic devices - Interoperability requirements for
3155 dimensions, connections and initial device classification

3156 **Material Specific Standards**

3157 — ASTM F2027, Standard Guide for Characterization and Testing of Raw or
3158 Starting Biomaterials for Tissue- Engineered Medical Products

3159 — ASTM F2212, Standard Guide for Characterization of Type I Collagen as
3160 Starting Material for Surgical Implants and Substrates for Tissue Engineered
3161 Medical Products (TEMPs)

3162 — ISO 3826 (all parts), Plastics collapsible containers for human blood and
3163 blood components

3164 — ISO 5832 (all parts), Implants for surgery — Metallic materials

3165 — ISO 5834 (all parts), Implants for surgery — Ultra-high-molecular-weight
3166 polyethylene

3167 — ISO 5838 (all parts), Implants for surgery — Metallic skeletal pins and wires

3168 — ISO 6474-1:2019, Implants for surgery — Ceramic materials — Part 1:
3169 Ceramic materials based on high purity alumina

3170 — ISO 7153-1:2016, Surgical instruments — Materials — Part 1: Metals

3171 **Material Agnostic Standards**

3172 — ISO/TS 23565:2021 Biotechnology — Bioprocessing — General
3173 requirements and considerations for equipment systems used in the
3174 manufacturing of cells for therapeutic use

3175 — ISO 20417:2012 Medical devices - Information to be supplied by the
3176 manufacturer

3177 — ISO 16142-1:2016, - Medical devices — Recognized essential principles of
3178 safety and performance of medical devices — Part 1: General essential
3179 principles and additional specific essential principles for all non-IVD medical
3180 devices and guidance on the selection of standards

3181 — ISO 7405:2018, Dentistry — Evaluation of biocompatibility of medical
3182 devices used in dentistry

3183 — ISO 10993 (all parts), Biological evaluation of medical devices

3184 **Sensors and actuators in the Organ-on-Chip space**

3185 — **Sensors**

- 3186 — ISO 14511:2019, Measurement of fluid flow in closed conduits – thermal mass
- 3187 flowmeter
- 3188 — ISO/TS 23367-1:2022, Nanotechnologies — Performance characteristics of
- 3189 nanosensors for chemical and biomolecule detection
- 3190 — ISO 14511:2019, Measurement of fluid flow in closed conduits – thermal mass
- 3191 flowmeters
- 3192 — **Connection of sensors and actuators to instrumentation**
- 3193 — **Measurement of flows and fluids**
- 3194 — IEC 60601-2-24:2012: Medical electrical equipment - Part 2-24: Particular
- 3195 requirements for the basic safety and essential performance of infusion
- 3196 pumps and controllers
- 3197 — AAMI TIR 101: Fluid Delivery Performance Testing For Infusion Pumps
- 3198 — ISO 4185:1980, Measurement of liquid flow in closed conduits - Weighing
- 3199 method
- 3200 **Modular integration of a microfluidic system**
- 3201 — ISO 22916:2022, Microfluidic devices — Interoperability requirements for
- 3202 dimensions, connections and initial device classification.
- 3203 **Hardware and Techniques from Existing Cell Culture Pipelines**
- 3204 — **Sterilization**
- 3205 — ISO/TS 22421:2021, Sterilization of health care products — Common
- 3206 requirements for sterilizers for terminal sterilization of medical devices in
- 3207 health care facilities
- 3208 — ISO 22441:2022, Sterilization of health care products — Common
- 3209 requirements for sterilizers for terminal sterilization of medical devices in
- 3210 health care facilities
- 3211 — ISO 11137 part 1-4, Sterilization of health care products - Radiation
- 3212 — ISO/TS 21387:2020, Sterilization of medical devices - Guidance on the
- 3213 requirements for the validation and routine processing of ethylene oxide
- 3214 sterilization processes using parametric release
- 3215 — ISO 11135 (all parts), Sterilization of health-care products — Ethylene oxide
- 3216 — Requirements for the development, validation and routine control of a
- 3217 sterilization process for medical devices
- 3218 — ISO 11138 (all parts), Sterilization of health care products — Biological
- 3219 indicators
- 3220 — ISO 11140 (all parts), Sterilization of health care products — Chemical
- 3221 indicators

- 3222 — ISO 7886 (all parts), Sterile hypodermic syringes for single use
- 3223 — ISO 8536 (all parts), Infusion equipment for medical use
- 3224 — ISO 8537:2016, Sterile single-use syringes, with or without needle, for insulin
- 3225 — ISO 13408 (all parts), Aseptic processing of health care products
- 3226 — ISO 17665-2:2006, Sterilization of health care products , Part 1:
3227 Requirements for the development, validation and routine control of a
3228 sterilization process for medical devices
- 3229 — ISO 17665-2:2006, Sterilization of health care products, Part 2: Guidance on
3230 the application of ISO 17665-1
- 3231 — ISO 17665-3:2006, Sterilization of health care products, Part 3: Guidance on
3232 the designation of a medical device to a product family and processing
3233 category for steam sterilization

3234 — **Microplates**

- 3235 — ANSI SLAS 1-2004 (R2012): Footprint Dimensions
- 3236 — ANSI SLAS 2-2004 (R2012): Height Dimensions
- 3237 — ANSI SLAS 3-2004 (R2012): Bottom Outside Flange Dimensions
- 3238 — ANSI SLAS 4-2004 (R2012): Well Positions
- 3239 — ANSI SLAS 6-2012: Well Bottom Elevation
- 3240 — ANSI SLAS 4-2004 (R2012) SBS micro plate format

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3242 **Chapter 7 Hardware parameters, experimental design and data management**

3243 **Hardware parameters that directly impact experimental data**

- 3244 — ARRIVE guidelines are a resource for best practice in designing and reporting
3245 animal studies
- 3246 — Guidance Document on Good In Vitro Method Practices (GIVIMP)
- 3247 — ISO 13485:2016, Medical devices - Quality management systems -
3248 Requirements for regulatory purposes

3249 **Data Management**

- 3250 — STAR methods
- 3251 — FAIR guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship
- 3252 — MIQE guidelines, scope is very narrow but could be a good starting point for
3253 reporting guidelines
- 3254 — PRO-MaP

- 3255 — RIVER (Reporting In Vitro Experiments Responsibly)
- 3256 — ISO 20691:2022, Requirements for data formatting and description in the life
3257 sciences
- 3258 — ISO 27001:2022 Annex A Control 8.28, Information security, cybersecurity
3259 and privacy protection - Information security management systems -
3260 Requirements
- 3261 — ISO 27002:2022, Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection
3262 - Information security controls
- 3263 — ISO/IEC 27005:2022, Information security, cybersecurity and privacy
3264 protection - Guidance on managing information security risks
- 3265 — ISO/IEC 15408 (all parts), Information security, cybersecurity and privacy
3266 protection - Evaluation criteria for IT security
- 3267 **Chapter 8 User perspective and regulatory, legal and ethical aspects**
- 3268 **The use of human tissues, cells and data**
- 3269 — ISO 15189:2022, Medical laboratories - Requirements for quality and
3270 competence

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Annex C Prioritisation for standardisation

WG 1 has set the prioritisation for standardisation chart below based on results from a survey to all WGs. This was prepared according to the protocol:

1. Each WG was asked to give input of possible items needing standardisation.
2. A list was prepared based on the items collected.
3. Each WG was asked to establish one urgency level from five possible for each prioritisation item. Five levels: 1-very important, 2-important, 3-neutral, 4-less important, 5-not important.
4. The results were collected and pondered based on the equation:
$$\text{Pondered value} = \sum \left(\frac{\# \text{ consensus}}{\text{level of importance}} \right) \times \# \text{ evaluations}$$
5. The priorities were organized in 10 major topics: Qualification of materials; Sterilization; Cell integrity, identity, function; Leakage; Study design; Interfaces; Fabrication related; Metrology; Symbols; and Software.
6. The pondered values were summed per topic.

The ranking presented in the table below was obtained from 256 scores on 117 items identified by the 5 WGs. 117 items were prioritized and grouped in 10 different areas of interest for OoC.

Indicates consensus about high priority/urgency for standardisation in this area							
Suggests consensus about high priority/urgency for standardisation in this area							
Suggests consensus about lower priority/urgency for standardisation in this area							
No clear indication of priority/urgency for standardisation in this area							
Item Number and Description	1. Very important	2. Important	3. Neutral	4. Less important	5. Not important	Number of evaluations	Ponderation
Qualification of materials							
012. Leaching of material, for instance in the case of PDMS un-crosslinked oligomers	3	1				4	13,0
011. Standards on how to measure and qualify materials	3		1			4	12,4
016. Absorption	2	2				4	10,0
015. Biocompatibility	2	1		1		4	9,3
018. What material properties are relevant for OoC users?	2	1			1	4	9,2
014. (Oxygen) permeability	1	3				4	7,0
010. Material properties and information to be supplied by the manufacturer	2	1				3	6,8
087. material of collection tube and storage conditions to ensure minimal loss of compound/analyte	1	1				2	2,5
061. Compatibility to substrates (dimensional)		2		1		3	1,7
063. Materials available		1	1	1		3	1,3
065. Compatibility to substrates (biophysical)		1	1	1		3	1,3
099. Hydrogels compatibility with OoC	1					1	1,0
100. Hydrogel Biocompatibility	1					1	1,0
109. Scaffolds compatibility with OoC (summary of the following items)	1					1	1,0
110. Scaffold Biocompatibility	1					1	1,0
112. Scaffold Biochemical properties	1					1	1,0
115. Functional coatings compatibility with OoC substrates	1					1	1,0

116. Functional coating Biocompatibility	1					1	1,0
082. Compound characterisation		2				2	1,0
083. test for compound identity and purity	1					1	1,0
062. Requirements for bioink		1				1	0,3
101. Hydrogel Mechanical properties/architecture		1				1	0,3
103. Hydrogel Degradation		1				1	0,3
111. Scaffold Mechanical properties and architecture		1				1	0,3
066. Translucency				1	1	2	0,2
Sterilization							
038. Minimum requirements per technique to ensure the sterilization quality	3			1		4	12,3
039. How is the effect of sterilization measured?	3			1		4	12,3
013. Cleanliness of the surface, for instance residues from the fabrication process	2	2				4	10,0
036. Sterilization techniques to be used	1	1		1	1	4	5,5
035. Sterilization quality	2					2	4,0
107. Hydrogel Sterilization		1				1	0,3
113. Scaffold Sterilization		1				1	0,3
Cell integrity, identity, function							
002. Cell integrity and identity	3					3	9,0
003. Cell function	3					3	9,0
004. Cell contamination	3					3	9,0
080. Biological characterisation: Number of cells and/or cell viability	1	2				3	4,5
081. Baseline characteristics of cells or organoids in OoC, cell specific functionality	1	1	1			3	4,1
005. Minimum reporting requirements for cells used in OoC systems	2					2	4,0
001. Quality controls steps during the culture and maintenance of cells	1					1	1,0
105. Hydrogel Biological properties	1					1	1,0
117. Cell type definition	1					1	1,0
Metrology							
098. Terminology	2					2	4,0
059. Resolution	1	1		1		3	3,9
041. Flow generator	1				1	2	2,1
067. Viscosity		2		1		3	1,7

020. According to what standards are these properties measured		2			1	3	1,7
022. Dead volume		1	2			3	1,4
023. Flow rates		1	2			3	1,4
043. The liquid properties		1	1		1	3	1,2
019. How are these properties characterized?		1		1	1	3	1,1
076. Shear stress	1					1	1,0
085. Stability in media over time,		2				2	1,0
070. Temperature	1					1	1,0
071. O2 saturation	1					1	1,0
050. Integrated flow control facilities			2			2	0,4
040. Measurement of flows and fluids		1				1	0,3
072. Pressure		1				1	0,3
074. Flow rate		1				1	0,3
073. Humidity			1			1	0,1
Interfaces							
024. Standard interface to enable easy and reliable integration of sensors in OoC systems, either tube based of tube less integration	2	1	1			4	9,4
026. Hardware	1	1			1	3	3,9
034. Manifold based integration: footprint of the component, position of microfluidic ports, clamping system and exclusion zone	1				2	3	3,3
048. Optical window		1	2			3	1,4
030. Standard application layer interfaces		1	1	1		3	1,3
025. Connection of sensors and actuators to instrumentation		2				2	1,0
032. Heterogenous integration: limited space for standardisation			1		2	3	0,6
031. Modular integration of a microfluidic system		1			1	2	0,6
033. Tube based integration: Tube dimensions, connection of tubing to component		1			1	2	0,6
021. Sensors			2			2	0,4
069. Hardware Setup Processes		1				1	0,3
028. Wired/wireless connectivity					1	1	0,1
Fabrication related							
037. Which technique may be used on which material	2			1	1	4	8,5

084. Fractions of unbound compounds in media and non-specific binding to chip surface	2					2	4,0
045. Integration of microfluidics and microplate workflow: TBD	1	1				2	2,5
060. Multimaterial printing (creating architectural compartments, with different cell types placed in discrete locations relative to each other)		2		1		3	1,7
058. Reproducibility of the bioprinted object is defined as the “standard deviation of the bioprinted item or channels in/for the OoC		1	1	1		3	1,3
104. Hydrogel Crosslinking method/kinetics of formation	1					1	1,0
057. Bioprinting		2				2	1,0
064. Crosslinking methods			2	1		3	0,9
049. Standard dimensions and tolerances			2			2	0,4
054. Plate flatness			2			2	0,4
055. Plate nest			2			2	0,4
Study design							
088. Study design	2	1				3	6,8
090. Sample size (number of experimental units) develop OoC-specific guidance on allocation of n/EU in OoC studies, including how to ensure robust experimental design when the maximum n is low	1	2				3	4,5
089. Appropriate positive and negative controls for each arm: develop a standard list of positive and negative controls for specific organs and applications		2		1		3	1,7
092. Randomisation: develop OoC-specific standard for randomisation across different OoC platforms accounting for multiple types of technical and biological variable		2			1	3	1,7
086. Method of sample collection		1	2			3	1,4
079. Setting up an experiment		2				2	1,0
091. Number of operators: develop standard guidance on the minimum/maximum number of operators that can be included in a study to ensure the study is robust		2				2	1,0
068. Protocols / biological CAD			2	1		3	0,9
093. Sampling time points: for different types of chip, multiple operators small sample volumes. Process for collecting the sample, including tube storage material and storage conditions/times			2			2	0,4
Leakage							
044. Leakage	3	1				4	13,0

075. Leak-tightness of tubing		1				1	0,3
Symbols							
008. What symbols are being used in OoC that are not covered by ISO standard		1	1	2		4	1,9
007. What ISO symbols can be used		2		1		3	1,7
009. How to use the symbols to visualize an OoC system of experimental setup		2		1		3	1,7
006. Symbols		2				2	1,0
Software							
097. Guidelines for using statistical software tools and tests as well as data analyses		2		1		3	1,7
095. Standards that define the use of software and programming languages, e.g. R, python			1	1	1	3	0,7
027. Software					1	1	0,1
Other							
096. Documentation verifying the use of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)		2	1			3	1,8
078. Characteristic Quality Management	1					1	1,0
029. Security		2				2	1,0
094. Data Management		2				2	1,0
047. Priding access			2			2	0,4
051. Microplate limitations			2			2	0,4
053. Numbering			2			2	0,4
056. Labelling			2			2	0,4
052. Orientation			1	1		2	0,3
017. A standard specifying the information the manufacturer should supply for its product		1				1	0,3
046. Incubators				2		2	0,3
077. Characteristic			1			1	0,1
042. The microchip					1	1	0,1